

Submission of NFDI proposal

National Research Data Infrastructure for and with Computer Science

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List of Abbreviations

Technical specifications or tools that are only relevant for selected sub-disciplines within computer science will not be listed here, though stated in their respective profile descriptions.

AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
ACM	Association for Computing Machinery
API	Application Programming Interface
CDI	Collaborative Data Infrastructure
CEPIS	Council of European Professional Informatics Societies
COBIT	Control Objectives for Information and Related Technology
CS	Computer Science
DFG	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft
DFN	Deutsches Forschungsnetz
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (data)
FIZ	Fachinformationszentrum Karlsruhe
FTE	Full-time Equivalent
FZJ	Forschungszentrum Jülich
GI	Gesellschaft für Informatik
GMA	Gesellschaft Mess- und Automatisierungstechnik
GWDG	Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung Göttingen
HCI	Human-Computer Interaction
HPC	High-Performance Computing
ID	Identifier
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IFIP	International Federation of Information Processing
IT	Information Technology
ITG	Informationstechnische Gesellschaft
ITIL	Information Technology Infrastructure Library
JGUM	Johannes Gutenberg Universität Mainz
KIT	Karlsruher Institut für Technologie
LMU	Ludwig-Maximilians Universität München
LZI	Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik / Schloss Dagstuhl
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur / National Research Data Infrastructure
NFDIxCS	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur für und mit Computer Science / National Research Data Infrastructure for and with Computer Science

OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OSS	Open-Source Software
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
RDMC	Research Data Management Container
REST	Representational State Transfer
RISE	Research Infrastructure Self-Evaluation Framework
RWTH	Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen
SHF@NRW	Software Heritage Foundation Repository Mirror of NRW hosted by UDE
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
UDE	Universität Duisburg-Essen
UHH	Universität Hamburg
UKI	Christian-Albrecht-Universität zu Kiel
UP	Universität Potsdam
UPB	Universität Paderborn
UML	Unified Modeling Language
TA	Task Area
TUD	Technische Universität Dresden
TUDA	Technische Universität Darmstadt
TUM	Technische Universität München
UX	User Experience
VDE	Verband der Elektrotechnik Elektronik Informationstechnik
VDI	Verein Deutscher Ingenieure
VM	Virtual Machine
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

1 General Information

Name of the consortium in English and German

National Research Data Infrastructure for and with Computer Science
Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur für und mit Computer Science
(NFDI_xCS)

Summary of the proposal in English and German

The main goal of the NFDI_xCS consortium is to identify, define and deploy an infrastructure for the operation of services which store complex domain-specific data objects from the vast field of Computer Science (**CS**) and to implement the FAIR principles across the board. This includes producing reusable data objects which contain not only various types of CS data including the associated metadata, but also the corresponding software, context and execution information in a standardized form. These data objects – the so-called Research Data Management Containers – can be of any size, structure and quality. Specifically, we address the following issues:

1. NFDI_xCS will promote the implementation of the FAIR data principles for CS research data and software artifacts, simplify the citation of software and CS data and thus modernize the publication processes and culture of both CS and its applications. NFDI_xCS provides a forum for the discussion of CS research data formats, metadata formats and semantics. It will work towards generally accepted standards, in particular for the sustainable storage, retrieval and availability of CS research data.
2. NFDI_xCS will, in collaboration with other scientific disciplines, support the application of CS methods such as Big Data, Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning. In addition, the operation of these systems generates large amounts of data, e.g. in the areas of high performance computing and computer architecture, which in turn also contribute to the further development of genuine CS methods.
3. NFDI_xCS will share the experience and knowledge of the CS community on system architectures, processes, standards for interoperability, data-oriented scientific publication and communication systems with all interested scientific disciplines / consortia in the NFDI family.

The association GI (Gesellschaft für Informatik) – comprising related specialist groups and communication channels – in combination with other partners at national, European and international level will be used as a basis and starting point to create an open environment to support all researchers in CS with their research data needs. The core principle in NFDI_xCS is to

establish an organizational and technical, cooperative and interoperable, extensible and open infrastructure to bundle the existing forces of relevant services and actors from and for CS. For this purpose, qualitative content analysis from the CS community will be used to empirically derive the requirements of the sub-disciplines from their profile descriptions and transfer them into an open service infrastructure. The developed services will be designed for sustainable operation at minimal cost. Targeted community development for cultural change will support young academics to negotiate practices and norms and to develop the competencies to handle their research data responsibly.

Das Kernziel des Konsortiums NFDIxCS ist es, eine Infrastruktur für den Betrieb von Diensten zur Speicherung komplexer domänenspezifischer Datenobjekte aus der Breite der Informatik zu identifizieren, zu definieren und einzusetzen und die FAIR-Prinzipien flächendeckend umzusetzen. Das schließt wiederverwendbare Datenobjekte ein, die verschiedene Arten von Informatik(CS)-Daten auch die zugehörigen Metadaten und die entsprechende Software, Kontext- und Ausführungsinformation in standardisierter Form enthalten. Diese Datenobjekte können von beliebiger Größe, Struktur und Qualität sein. Konkret sind dies die folgenden Themen:

1. NFDIxCS wird die Umsetzung der FAIR Data Principles für CS-Forschungsdaten sowie Software-Artefakte fördern, die Zitierbarkeit von Software und CS-Daten vereinfachen und damit die Publikationsprozesse und -kultur sowohl in der Informatik als auch in ihren Anwendungen modernisieren. NFDIxCS bietet ein Forum für die Diskussion über Formate von Forschungsdaten, Metadaten und Semantiken. Es wirkt auf allgemein akzeptierte Standards, insbesondere für die nachhaltige Speicherung, das Auffinden und Nachnutzen von Informatik-Forschungsdaten hin.
2. NFDIxCS wird in Zusammenarbeit mit anderen wissenschaftlichen Disziplinen die Anwendung von Informatikmethoden wie Big Data, Künstliche Intelligenz und Maschinelles Lernen befördern. Zusätzlich entstehen im Betrieb dieser Systeme große Datenmengen z.B. in den Bereichen High Performance Computing und Rechnerarchitektur, die wiederum dazu beitragen auch genuine Informatikmethoden weiter zu entwickeln.
3. NFDIxCS wird die Erfahrungen und das Wissen der Informatik-Community zu Systemarchitekturen, Prozessen, Standards für Interoperabilität, datenorientierte wissenschaftliche Publikations- und Kommunikationssysteme mit allen interessierten Wissenschaftsbereichen bzw. Konsortien in der NFDI-Familie teilen.

Die Gesellschaft für Informatik (GI) – ihre Fachgruppen und Kommunikationskanäle – in Kombination mit anderen Partnern auf nationaler, europäischer und internationaler Ebene wird als Basis und Ausgangspunkt genutzt, um eine offene Umgebung zu schaffen, die alle Forscher

in der Informatik bei ihren Forschungsdatenbedürfnissen unterstützt. Das Kernprinzip in NFDIxCS ist, eine organisatorische, technische, kooperative und interoperable Infrastruktur zu etablieren, um die vorhandenen Kräfte relevanter Dienste und Akteure aus und für CS zu bündeln. Dazu werden mittels einer qualitativen Inhaltsanalyse aus der CS-Community die Anforderungen der Teildisziplinen aus deren Profilbeschreibungen empirisch abgeleitet und in eine offene Dienstinfrastruktur überführt. Die entwickelten Dienste werden auf einen nachhaltigen Betrieb zu minimalen Kosten ausgelegt. Eine gezielte Community-Entwicklung für einen Kulturwandel unterstützt den wissenschaftlichen Nachwuchs, Praktiken und Normen auszuhandeln und die Kompetenzen für einen verantwortungsvollen Umgang mit ihren Forschungsdaten zu entwickeln.

Applicant institution

Applicant institution	Location
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Spokesperson

Spokesperson	Institution, location
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Co-applicant institutions

Co-applicant institutions	Location
Gesellschaft für Informatik e.V. (GI)	Bonn/Berlin
Universität Potsdam (UP)	Potsdam
Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT)	Karlsruhe
Universität Hamburg (UHH)	Hamburg
Ludwig-Maximilians Universität München (LMU)	München
Technische Universität München (TUM)	München
Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen (GWDG)	Göttingen
Johannes Gutenberg Universität Mainz (JGUM)	Mainz
Technische Universität Dresden (TUD)	Dresden
Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ)	Jülich
Christian-Albrecht-Universität zu Kiel (UKI)	Kiel
Universität Paderborn (UPB)	Paderborn
Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen (RWTH)	Aachen
Technische Universität Darmstadt (TUDA)	Darmstadt
Schloss Dagstuhl – Leibniz Center for Informatics (LZI)	Wadern
FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz-Institut für Informationsinfrastruktur	Karlsruhe

Co-spokespersons

Co-spokespersons	Institution, location	Task Area (TA)
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	GI Vice President	
Prof. Dr. Anne Koziolk	KIT Karlsruhe	M2, D3, A2
Prof. Dr. Ralf Reussner	KIT Karlsruhe	D1, D3, C2
Prof. Dr. Hannes Federrath	Uni Hamburg	I4, C4
	GI President	
Prof. Dr. Albrecht Schmidt	LMU München	C3, D2
Prof. Dr. Tobias Nipkow	TU München	I1
Prof. Dr. Martin Schulz	TU München	D2, I1, C3
Prof. Dr. Ramin Yahyapour	GWDG Göttingen	I2, A2, D1, D2, D4, I1, A3, M3
Prof. Dr.-Ing. André Brinkmann	JGU Mainz	I1, D2, D4, I3
Prof. Dr. Wolfgang E. Nagel	TU Dresden	I3, D4
Prof. Dr. Dr. Thomas Lippert	FZ Jülich	D4, I3
Prof. Dr. Agnes Koschmider	Christian-Albrecht-Universität zu Kiel	D3 D2
Prof. Dr. Christian Plessl	Uni Paderborn	D4, I3
Prof. Dr. Matthias Müller	RWTH Aachen	D4, I3
Prof. Dr. Christian Bischof	TU Darmstadt	D4
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Prof. Dr. Franziska Boehm	FIZ Karlsruhe	C4, I4

Participants

Participating institutions	Location
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Verein zur Förderung eines Deutschen Forschungsnetzes (DFN-Verein)	Berlin
Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum (DKRZ)	Hamburg
Höchstleistungsrechenzentrum Stuttgart (HLRS)	Stuttgart
Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ)	Garching near Munich

Contribution of DFKI:

Support in standardization processes and Service-Oriented Architectures (SOA)

Contribution of DFN:

Identity and Access Management (IAM) and international integration of the services

Contribution of DKRZ:

High Performance Computing, benchmarking und monitoring; Identity Management of subjects and objects, persistent identifiers

Contribution of HLRZ:

Expertise in metadata, ontologies and vocabularies, repositories and storage management systems

Contribution of LRZ:

Co-development of LRZ service offerings for NFDI x CS, focused on metadata standards for HPC (TA D2), making large data sets FAIR (TAs I1, A3, C2), and user support.

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Prof. Dr. Gregor Engels	Universität Paderborn, Institut für Informatik, Datenbank- und Informationssysteme
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Prof. Dr. Enrico Rukzio	Universität Ulm, Media Informatics
Prof. Dr. Bernhard Rumpe	RWTH Aachen, Software Engineering, Software Engineering

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Prof. Dr. Bernt Schiele	Max Planck Institute for Informatics
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Horst Schirmeier	TU Dresden, Institut für Systemarchitektur, Betriebssysteme
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Dr. Alexander Steen	Uni Luxembourg, Faculty of Science, Technology and Medicine
Prof. Dr. Sven Strickroth	LMU München, Institut für Informatik
Dr. Michael Striewe	Uni Duisburg-Essen, paluno
Prof. Dr. Matthias Weidlich	Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Institut für Informatik

Contribution of Prof. Dr. Florian Alt:

User-centered security; secure human-machine interfaces; behavioral biometrics

Contribution of Prof. Dr. Christoph Benz Müller:

Contact to the Confederation of Laboratories for AI Research in Europe (CLAIRE); formal knowledge modeling; development and standardisation of logic modelling language

Contribution of Dr. Daniel Demmler:

User privacy; software & performance analytics; Open Access for research data; secure long-term archiving and access control

Contribution of Prof. Dr. Gregor Engels:

Link to Informatics Europe; link to Software Engineering and HCI community

Contribution of Dr. Bernhard Fechner:

Expertise on fault tolerance mechanisms and taxonomies in the area of dependability

Contributions of Prof. Dr. Martin Frank:

Link to NHR@KIT on sustainable software development, benchmarking, portability and reproducibility in HPC

Contribution of Prof. Dr. Wilhelm Hasselbring:

Cross-site search/Cross-linking repositories; Citation/attribution/provenance of data

Contributions of Dr. Jens Heidrich:

Expertise in artificial intelligence and machine learning and the quality of research data

Contribution of Prof. Dr. Timo Kehrer:

Version management; Reusable execution environments; International links to SE4Science'19 and SFB FONDA

Contributions of Prof. Dr. Ulf Leser, Prof. Dr. Matthias Weidlich and Prof. Dr. Nicole

Schweikardt: Expertise in standardized metadata; Reference architectures; Sharable and reusable execution environments

Contributions of Dr. Jan Linxweiler:

Scientific software development, computational fluid dynamics (CFD), reusable execution environments

Contributions of apl. Prof. Dr. Thomas Mandl and Prof. Dr. Philipp Schaer:

Expertise in search engines and retrieval systems, Scientific Retrieval, Digital Libraries

Contribution of Prof. Dr. Vera Meister:

Expertise in standards-based modeling of domain-specific knowledge, link to W3C community group schema.org

Contributions of Prof. Dr. Andreas Oberweis and Dr.-Ing. Gunther Schiefer:

Integrated view of the information system life cycle; appropriate storage architecture; links to Working groups in the Science Data Center Baden Württemberg initiative

Contribution of Prof. Dr. Klaus Pohl:

Concepts for managing versions and variants of software artifacts and data, metadata and related semantic aspects, security and privacy, role modelling and accesses control, distributed architecture, and community development

Contribution of Prof. Dr. Tilmann Rabl:

Expertise in designing benchmarks and distributed monitoring; Workshops with SFB FONDA

Contribution of Prof. Dr. Enrico Rukzio:

Design and management of research data in the field of human-computer interaction; Annotation and processing of research data from quantitative and qualitative user studies

Contribution of Prof. Dr. Bernhard Rumpe:

Semantic comparison of models; Model evolution; Development of metadata standards for software artifacts as research data

Contributions of Prof. Dr. Bernt Schiele:

Expertise in version management, metadata and protocols, data for benchmarking, architecture and interfaces, quality management and community development

Contribution of Prof. Dr.-Ing. Horst Schirmeier:

Expertise on metrics, data formats, automated description of experiments, benchmarks and tools in the area of fault tolerance

Contribution of Prof. Dr. Ute Schmid:

Experience in AI and machine learning, explainability of (deep) neural networks, blackbox approaches, design of experiment and reduction of sampling bias

Contribution of Prof. Dr. Peter Sobe:

Deployment of fault tolerant data storage and support in using open-source components;
Institutional links to GI TC FERS and TC PARS

Contribution of Dr. Alexander Steen:

Community building & networking activities; Benchmarking infrastructure; Research data

Contribution of Prof. Dr. Sven Strickroth:

Expertise in E-Learning, version-control systems for tracking changes in source code, open-source software development and open-source licences

Contribution of Dr. Michael Striewe:

Expertise in standardization processes, usage of linked open data, and modelling of quality management processes; Corpora of research data for testing

Names and numbers of the DFG review boards

(DFG-Fachkollegien) that reflect the subject orientation of the proposed consortium:

Area 409-01..10 (Computer Science)

2 Scope and Objectives

The objectives of NFDI \times CS are to create and operate an infrastructure supporting the FAIR principles for the scientific discipline of **Computer Science (CS)** and to build and empower the CS community to run and make use of this infrastructure. This initiative is coordinated by the German Informatics Society (GI) as the relevant professional body for CS in Germany, representing the entire community with well-established participatory structures. This enables a new dimension of sustainable research, increasing quality of and trust in scientific results and research data from CS and their reproducibility as well as reuse which is often unique in several ways: either the data creation or measurement is associated with high costs or the context of its creation/observation cannot be recreated. In addition, publication processes in CS will immensely benefit from NFDI \times CS, as it provides long term storage of replication packages for software as well as data and enables the citation of these artifacts as important research contributions. This is realized by a set of distributed NFDI \times CS services using a central entry point. Its key design element is the **Research Data Management Container (RDMC)**, which is based on established container technologies and encapsulates the aforementioned aspects: the research data, related software and execution context, supporting access structure for reviewing processes as well as measures to support privacy, legal and ethical considerations and reusability at the FAIR level. We reach out nationally and internationally to connect to the worldwide community of researchers in CS and those using CS research methods. The results will also be interoperable with ongoing efforts of international organizations such as the artifact review and badging approach of international CS societies and results of associations like the Fair Digital Object¹ and ReSA², to mention a few.

Remark regarding the evolution of this proposal:

This document is an improved version of the 2020 NFDI \times CS proposal. Main changes are:

- The structure and categorization of sub-disciplines of CS now directly resembles the proposed DFG categorization of our discipline.
- The envisaged design of the business model, principles of business processes including risk management has been redesigned and described in greater detail.
- The overall architecture of NFDI \times CS is now described in more detail, including the metadata and storage aspects. Our unique element is the Research Data Management Container (RDMC) which allows us to sustainably manage dedicated CS research data along with their execution environments.

¹ <https://fairdo.org/>

² <https://www.researchsoft.org/>

- The structure of the Task Areas (TAs) is now presented in five layers to provide better insights into our data management work packages with respect to context and interplay.
- We assembled a growing collection of CS research datasets, including the newly established German mirror of the Software Heritage service, thus pervading the community far more deeply than before. We will connect relevant repositories and services as an indispensable resource in CS research data management.

The general ideas and structure of the proposal remain untouched. The structure of the consortium has been slightly changed with regard to co-applicants and participants. However, we experienced a significant gain in maturity of the CS community when revising this proposal. This was evident, for example, in more expressive and targeted statements in the profile description of CS sub-disciplines.

2.1 Research domains or methods addressed by the consortium, specific aims

CS is a young and still growing discipline. We follow the new proposed DFG categorization of our field³. In the subsequent text, these areas are called **sub-disciplines**:

- 409-01 Theoretical Computer Science
- 409-02 Software Engineering and Programming Languages
- 409-03 Security and Dependability
- 409-04 Operating, Communication, Database and Distributed Systems
- 409-05 Visual Computing
- 409-06 Business Information Systems
- 409-07 Computer Architecture and Embedded Systems
- 409-08 Massively Parallel & Data Intensive Systems
- 409-09 Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning
- 409-10 Interactive Systems

The GI is similarly structured into Special Interest Groups (SIGs) and various additional subgroups / working groups (more than 150) well-covering the entire CS discipline. Despite this breadth, the needs of the sub-disciplines in research data management (RDM) have strong commonalities. Thus, this section examines the fields of actions needed in RDM for CS and how the broad spectrum and heterogeneous dynamics of the CS community can be addressed. Generally, the status quo of RDM in CS needs to be improved since storage and publication of data and software is done but not on a regular basis and in many cases not fully addressing the FAIR principles. Especially, the “Findable” and “Reusable” parts are often not covered

³ as jointly suggested for the upcoming elections to the DFG review boards by FTI (Fakultätentag Informatik / national assembly of CS Faculties) and GI for implementation in the legislative term 2024 to 2028

systematically. As a result, CS research is not yet fully exploiting its inherent potential. Current practice in CS-related publication processes is creating first steps towards awareness that improvements of the standard procedures are necessary. Thus, we first characterize CS research methods and the various roles of research data. Then, the overall needs in CS towards FAIRness are described. Finally, a method to derive the structure which underlies the RDM activities is proposed.

2.1.1 *Structure of research and research data in computer science*

Our starting point are the special characteristics of CS as a scientific discipline which generates findings from research on the changes mediated by technology in our living environment, i.e. considering this as a socio-technical system. Depending on sub-discipline, focus and area of emphasis in scientific practice – including the use and role of research data – may vary. Similarly to mathematics, CS is a very structural discipline, however, in contrast to mathematics, engineering, cognitive and social aspects play a major role in supporting CS research in design of the artifacts as well. For example, in sub-disciplines like Visual Computing, Business Information Systems, and Interactive Systems, the performance of human subjects is a most important factor in research, and empirical methods from social science and the humanities are applied. On the other hand, scientific progress in areas like Computer Architecture, Distributed Systems and Data Intensive Systems depends on patterns of usage of technical components so that research data e.g. in the form of bench marks drive the research processes. Thus, digital artifacts are designed and applied in socio-technical systems. Analyses and models are used both as the basis of this design process and in the results of its experimental or empirical research. Theory and practice constantly cross-fertilize each other in CS research, which is also manifested in the research methods and tools used. An NFDI for CS must take this into account. Below we discuss this at first in a holistic view to cover the entire discipline of CS while in [chapter 4 \(Research Data Management Strategy\)](#) the detailed analysis per sub-discipline is provided.

The research activities can be structured according to the model for **design-science research** proposed by Hevner & Chatterjee (2010). Three fundamental areas are distinguished, following explained using the example of software engineering research (Felderer et al. 2021):

- a) The *environment* is functioning as the application domain of the solution to be developed and deployed. It consists of people, technical ecosystems and organizational structures as well as the resulting opportunities and challenges. This delivers the context for the research and design process. Prototypical artifacts are evaluated, and evidence is fed back.
- b) In the heart is the *design-science research* itself. Produced artifacts are, for instance, models and specifications, prototypical products or systems, descriptions of humans or organizations, or applied methods and tools. At a meta-level, design issues like archiving

techniques for data, software and runtime context and design processes are reflected and evaluated, too.

- c) The underlying *knowledge base* is both a starting and end point for such research. It incorporates research methods, algorithms and theories, experience and expertise from the basis of the design processes, and meta-information about artifacts from previous design processes. Also, research questions for upcoming research are created here.

Considering this structure, three design-science research cycles, each with its own logic, operate across the three identified areas:

- The cycle of requirements elicitation and validation – driven by the question of practical *relevance* – concerns areas a) and b).
- The actual *design* process is covering area b).
- The cycle of applying established principles and supplementing the existing knowledge base – led by scientific *rigor* – addresses areas b) and c).

This varies among the different sub-disciplines, with varying emphases and additions. The manifold and often short research cycles lead to a **publication culture in CS** which especially includes scientific outlets with short preparation times (like conference and workshop proceedings) alongside journals and monographs. The data associated with these research cycles cover the three areas defined above: **application data** from the relevance cycle, created **artifacts** from the design cycle, and the **core objects of knowledge in CS** from the rigor cycle. All have to be handled in their specific relation to each other.

As an example, research on an assembly automation project might be asking for a “smart” application on the recognition of workpieces, which is intuitively associated with Artificial Intelligence and Big Data. Therefore, the research data in this project covers a) the domain-specific context, like topology of the assembly line, current positions of components, lighting conditions etc.; b) the “smart” software including its execution environment and c) trained models, training data and machine learning algorithms for the stochastic approach, or descriptive logics and solver algorithms for the symbolic approach, respectively. Each of them is only useful in relation to the others and thus should be managed in a holistic way.

In more detail, relevant types of research data and forms of data processing will be derived from the characteristics of involved sub-disciplines. We provide these descriptions of their characteristics in separate profiles in chapter [4 \(Research Data Management Strategy\)](#) below.

2.1.2 General quality challenges in CS research

The aim of NFDI x CS is to increase the sustainability and reusability of research results in CS by establishing FAIR research data in CS. This will improve effectiveness and efficiency of CS research (Eymann, Goedicke & Lucke, 2018). Nonetheless, since CS research methods are used in various other research domains, the consortium also aims to include applications of CS within

the scope of CS from a methodological perspective. We give a few examples on how a FAIR culture will help to improve CS research:

- Sharing and reusing data requires a common understanding of formats to be used, procedures to be followed and quality criteria to be applied. Also, for instance, easy to apply practices for citation and attribution of data publications are needed. Although first approaches were developed in some CS sub-disciplines, e.g. in Software Engineering, there is still little knowledge about this in the CS community, let alone broad application of such practices. Therefore, appropriate **standards, procedures and guidelines for FAIR CS research** have to be established, **building upon existing results**.
- Formal descriptions and verification of system properties are important parts of CS research. For instance, proving correctness of an algorithm, assessing code coverage in a software or determining respective run-time characteristics can be automated. Furthermore, theorems and their related proofs become too complex to be handled manually, but can be supported by automated tools. Thus, besides the processed data, the software itself also becomes a kind of research data. There is a strong need to make such **software – as part of the research data – as well as associated execution environments** available in a **containerized** way.
- Design-oriented work in fields like Computer Architecture, Distributed Systems or Database Management delivers artifacts (like models, algorithms or system prototypes) for which increased performance against previous approaches in dedicated experiments needs to be demonstrated (so-called benchmarking). This only succeeds by using appropriate reference data to compare to. Here, contextual data, e.g. usage patterns or attack vectors, are essential as well. That's why **reliable and interoperable data management services** to find appropriate reference data need to be established, **tailored to the needs of the CS community** and **building upon existing results** (data and methods) from CS.
- Research in several CS sub-disciplines becomes increasingly empirical, e.g. in Human-Computer Interaction, Business Information Systems and Software Engineering. Here, user behavior in lab or field studies is of primary interest. Analysing socio-technical systems is highly contextual, and often subjective parameters are involved. Therefore, study designs, environmental conditions and collected data must be thoroughly documented. This is a valuable contribution to **increasing the reproducibility of research results**.
- Research in data-driven fields like Machine Learning requires big datasets to learn, improve and adapt the created models. Data for training and for verification of developed classifiers has to be different. This intensifies the need for quality-assured (i.e. well-structured and annotated) data collections from the respective fields of application. Thus,

mechanisms to **increase the reuse of existing data** are needed, also **beyond subject boundaries**.

- Systematic management of the related data in the research process is essential to compare, discuss and evaluate scientific progress in all of these areas. Further benefits come from integrating research data into education. However, best practices still have to be identified and broadly implemented. **Support is needed for the definition of common standards** for data formats, metadata, quality assurance and management processes. Furthermore, **automated processes** – as far as possible – would promote the implementation of RDM services.

These examples for different data and usage scenarios in modern CS research are only a few highlights. However, the entire community would benefit from mechanisms addressing the **derived objectives** (to be explained in more detail in section [2.2, Objectives and measuring success](#)). As CS is still a young discipline, methods of research are constantly evolving. Notwithstanding this, data will play an ever-increasing role. For example, the upcoming technology of quantum computing will broaden the picture considerably soon. NFDI x CS addresses this by creating appropriately flexible structures for the governance of the overall processes, thus building **openness** into our overall approach.

The common goal is to increase the trust in the findings and the related quality of documentation in the form of high-quality publications that include all information about relevant data, software and additional context. Also related software and software artifacts need to be produced and published according to the relevant best practices in the area, in order to be reusable in a sustainable way (Abramatic, Di Cosmo & Zacchiroli, 2018).

This increase in trust and confidence in the research results is produced by providing necessary evidence, thus producing sustainable research results. This will be achieved – depending on the various research methods and approaches of the sub-discipline in question – in different forms. Depending on the role of the research data involved, this can be the data obtained by various forms of observations up to data in the form of large (semi-)automated proofs of formalized properties/theorems.

2.1.3 *Need for action in CS research data management*

The approach above derives **certain types of CS research activities** from an abstract and conceptual perspective. The profile descriptions of the sub-disciplines given in chapter [4 \(Research Data Management Strategy\)](#) will spread the whole spectrum of CS research from their specific point of view (typical data, related processes and existing infrastructures to handle these data and processes) and identify remaining **challenges with research data**. From an analysis of these profile descriptions we derive common key issues that shall be addressed in a combined effort across our entire discipline. These key issues, as empirically derived from the profile

descriptions and thus representing the standards along which the sub-disciplines share common aspects, constitute the **Task Areas (TAs) of NFDIxCS**. They cover technical aspects (like storage, metadata, data security) as well as social aspects (like community building, (inter-)national outreach, legal and ethical issues). This structure is very much **guided by the FAIR principles**, the status of the research data in question, the related artifacts and metadata and the assessment of RDM instruments and procedures in CS.

2.2 Objectives and measuring success

The major goal of NFDIxCS is to increase sustainability and reusability of research results in CS. Thus, FAIR research data is intended to become an integral element of CS research in general and its publication culture in particular. The core of the efforts is thus to build an infrastructure which addresses the goals of the community as discussed above.

Figure 1 Overview of NFDIxCS Services

The infrastructure of NFDIxCS is a stratified set of services. These services are hosted by service providers within the consortium and centrally managed by the NFDIxCS executive management group.

The **Access Services** (see Fig. 1) provide the direct ability to search, use the search results in form of access to the research data and, in addition, quite a range of (semi-) automated community and management services to NFDIxCS users including central first contact points for help and support. There is also a machine level interface facilitating the outreach to other organisations within NFDI and beyond, nationally and internationally.

In the middle of the architecture, a set of **Core Services** provide dedicated functionality to establish the FAIR principles, to support community processes and necessary management operations like ID management and monitoring.

At the bottom of the architecture, a set of discipline-specific **Data Services** are provided to store and access research data and other related databases and repositories. Here, we will include the services of **dblp**, facilitating the improved CS related publication processes, and the services of the Software Heritage Foundation which are provided as a mirror by the University of Duisburg-Essen to give access to all needed software including all past versions for long term storage (**SHF@NRW**). Other external repositories and services will be integrated in the NFDIxCS architecture to enable cooperation with other NFDI consortia (using the agreed container interfaces) or basic services like DFN-AAI for identity and access management, for example. In section [4.4 \(Services provided by the consortium\)](#), more detail will be given about the services provided by NFDIxCS.

Research data to be included into NFDIxCS will be available in a packaged format: the so-called **Research Data Management Container (RDMC)**, which is a portable object that manages itself in terms of access, specific workflow and all the data, software and further information to describe the data and all the means to access / bring the data back to life. These RDMCs will be hosted by a few service providers initially within the consortium and later on, especially after the funding periods, by trusted (probably also paid) service providers which will possibly be available by EOSC / GAIA-X or similar provisioning schemes. The components encapsulated by an RDMC are sketched in Fig. 2.

We are aware that the **idea of encapsulating research data in a container** gains much attention in the community (e.g. code ocean⁴, GIDA⁵, Fair Data Objects⁶ etc.). We observe a very dynamic situation and currently each of them has a certain profile and is in a different state of maturity. While we address the specific needs of the CS community and don't find a ready-made solution for NFDIxCS, we will provide interoperability to these as far as it is technologically and economically viable.

The CS sub-disciplines will provide – managed by the overall compliance and consultancy processes of NFDIxCS – templates for the different research data types in CS. The ability to store the raw and processed data together with (a reference to) the needed software and execution context has been mentioned already (Strickroth et al. 2021 and many others). In addition to this, the special NFDIxCS feature are the three components (Access Control, Workflows and Filters & Transformation) on top, which rule the access and the work state of the data, including filters and role specific transformation within the container.

⁴ <https://codeocean.com/>, commercial solution, focus on replication packages and collaboration

⁵ <https://www.gida-global.org/care>, FAIR data sharing

⁶ <https://www.go-fair.org/today/fair-digital-framework/>, conceptual framework only

Figure 2 Overall Structure of a Research Data Management Container (RDMC)

Given the envisaged service structure and the RDMC concept, we now go into detail, which aspects of CS RDM we will address in NFDIxCS. Based on such an infrastructure, we support the current research methods and the types of data that typically are generated (as discussed in section [4.1 \(State of the arts and needs analysis\)](#)). This requires us to pursue the following objectives, and we will measure success in achieving these objectives by the key performance indicators (KPIs) listed below each objective:

1. Objective: Establish standards, procedures and guidelines for the various data types used in CS research, building upon existing results

- KPI-1: NFDIxCS results are used by an increasing number of international A* and A conferences and journals in their call for papers or guidelines.
- KPI-2: NFDIxCS results are used by publicly funded research in Germany (measured by analyzing publications: Ratio of papers that refers to research data conforming to NFDIxCS results out of all papers that acknowledge public funding).
- KPI-3: NFDIxCS results are used by an increasing number of PhD projects (measured by analyzing dissertations).
- KPI-4: RDM and FAIR data principles are addressed by an increasing number of CS curricula in German universities (as either mandatory or elective modules).

Realization: The protocols and processes will be supported by workflow management systems provided by the central services in the service layer (see Fig. 1).

2. Objective: Establish a RDMC concept that supports the various data types used in CS research

- KPI-5: The NFDIxCS RDMC concept is used by an increasing number of international A* and A conferences and journals in their call for papers or guidelines.
- KPI-6: The NFDIxCS RDMC concept is used by an increasing number of researchers to share their research data in international conferences and journals.

Realization: The research data is stored in a container with all the information necessary to access, review, publish and reuse the data in the form a specific user role is permitted to do. This includes all the software and context information connected to the creation,

processing, analysing and visualization of the data. Existing services will be reused as far as possible to establish this goal – like the Software Heritage mirror for linking to (past) versions of used software components and dblp for using/providing citation references for publication purposes.

3. Objective: Establish reliable and interoperable data management services and measures tailored to the needs of the CS community, building upon existing results

- KPI-7: NFDI x CS services are used by publications in international A* and A conferences and journals.
- KPI-8: Ratio of supported processes among identified CS research processes covered by NFDI x CS results.

Realization: This is established by a combination of central services (e.g. search) as well as actual research data available through the set of available RDMCs including privacy-friendly monitoring of the usage patterns.

4. Objective: Increase the reproduction of research results

- KPI-9: Increasing number of published studies that include reproduction of results, based on data provided with the help of NFDI x CS.
- KPI-10: Increasing number of reproductions in the review process, like in dedicated artifact review tracks, that use NFDI x CS results.

Realization: This is achieved by the combination of information contained and permanently stored with the research data in the related RDMCs as well as workflows enforced by the community and the NFDI x CS central system to support the appropriate quality control and the ability to perform it.

5. Objective: Increase the reuse of existing data, also beyond subject boundaries

- KPI-11: Data sets published according to NFDI x CS standards, procedures and guidelines are increasingly reused by other research groups from any discipline.
- KPI-12: Research results published according to NFDI x CS results have an above average impact, measured by number of citations relative to the venue where they are published.

Realization: This is achieved by the community services offered by NFDI x CS, through the web based services and the outreach facilitated by the interoperability interfaces contained therein.

In addition, in order to achieve these objectives and evolve with their respective scientific fields, we also need an important derived objective:

6. Objective: Implement best practices: Create automated support for processes in the definition of common standards for metadata, common standards for quality assurance and management processes, services, and service implementation

- KPI-13: Number of users registered for the services and actively using the services.

Realization: This is achieved by the services monitoring the usage of the infrastructure and related services in a privacy-preserving way.

In all KPIs, we do not specify fixed thresholds, but rather want to monitor that the NFDIxCS results are increasingly picked up, i.e. that there is a positive trend in their adoption. KPIs will be specified in detail by TA [M2 \(Quality Management\)](#), monitored by TA [M1 \(Management of the Consortium\)](#), and used by TA [C1 \(Community Development\)](#).

By NFDIxCS results, we mean all FAIR data management solutions the NFDIxCS consortium has contributed to, not only results solely provided by NFDIxCS, because we aim to build upon existing solutions and collaborate with international partners. To achieve the international adoption of NFDIxCS results and FAIR principles, we must and will collaborate with international partners as described in section [3.3 \(International networking\)](#). We do see the increased visibility of German RDM not as an objective on its own, however as a means to achieve the above objectives, which focus on international adoption of NFDIxCS results. Additionally, we will seek synergies with neighbouring disciplines and will work to relate NFDIxCS standards and services to their results or, where possible, define cross-disciplinary standards and establish cross-disciplinary services.

3 Consortium

- Uni Duisburg-Essen is also a member of consortiums KonsortSWD, NFDI4BioDiversity, NFDI4Immuno, NFDI4Ing, Text+, FAIRMat, NFDI4BioImage and InnoMatSafety.
- Uni Potsdam is also a member of the consortium NFDI4Earth.
- KIT is also a member of consortiums NFDI4Cat, NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Ing, DAPHNE4NFDI, FAIRmat, NFDI4Earth, NFDI-MatWerk, PUNCH4NFDI, NFDI4Mobility, NFDI4Energy, InnomatSafety and NFDI4Phys.
- Uni Hamburg is also a member of consortiums BERD@NFDI, NFDI4Earth, PUNCH4NFDI, Text+, NFDI4Microbiota, NFDI4Health and NFDI4DataScience.
- LMU München is also a member of consortiums BERD@NFDI, DAPHNE4NFDI, PUNCH4NFDI, MaRDI, NFDI4Phys, TheoRes, NFDI-Neuro, METHODS.
- TU München is also a member of consortiums NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Cat, GHGA, DAPHNE, Punch4NFDI, NFDI4Earth, FAIRmat, MaRDI, DeBioData, NFDI Neuroscience, NFDI4Mobility and FAIRagro.
- GWGD is also a member of consortiums NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Ing, Text+, NFDI4Phys and NFDI Neuroscience.
- Uni Mainz is also a member of consortiums NFDI4Chem and Punch4NFDI.
- TU Dresden is also a member of consortiums GHGA, NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Ing, NFDI-MatWerk, NFDI4DataScience, Punch4NFDI, FAIRmat, Text+ and NFDI4Earth.
- FZ Jülich is also a member of consortiums DataPlant, NFDI4Ing, TEXT+, FAIRMAT, NFDI4Earth, Daphne4NFDI, PUNCH4NFDI, NFDI-MatWerk, NFDI4Microbiota, FAIRagro, NFDI-Neuro, NFDI4Phys and NFDI4BioImage.
- Uni Kiel is also a member of consortiums DAPHNE4NFDI, NFDI4Chem, NFDI4DS, NFDI4Earth, NFDI4Microbiota, NFDI-MatWerk, NFDI4Memory, NFDI4Objects and NFDI4Patho.
- Uni Paderborn is also a member of consortiums NFDI4Culture, Text+, Daphne4NFDI and NFDI-Matwerk.
- RWTH Aachen is also a member of consortiums NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Cat, Daphne4NFDI, NFDI4DataScience, NFDI4Microbiota and NFDI-MatWerk.
- TU Darmstadt is also a member of consortiums NFDI4Ing, PUNCH4NFDI, NFDI4Cat and Text+.
- LZI is also a member of consortium NFDI4DataScience.
- FIZ Karlsruhe is also a member of consortiums NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Culture, MaRDI, NFDI4Memory, Agri, NFDI-MatWerk, NFDI4DataScience, InnoMatSafety and NFDI4Phys.

3.1 Composition of the consortium and its embedding in the community of interest

The structure of the consortium was designed to reflect two perspectives which are required for providing research data infrastructures (see also Rfil, 2017):

- Relevant researchers of the CS sub-disciplines make sure to meet the actual needs of the community and to bring in all available expertise and solutions.
- Powerful infrastructure providers for storage, computing and publication bring in their services along with their expertise in large-scale operation and maintenance.

Depending on the extent of activities and their own contributions, the partners within the consortium are either listed as co-applicants or participants. However, all partners make valuable contributions and reflect the broad spectrum of the academic CS discipline. This facilitates the evolution of academic IT providers towards regional or national centres of RDM excellence.

Figure 3 The German Informatics Society (GI) acts as a basis and starting point for the NFDIxCS structure, combining academic and operational perspectives.

NFDIxCS is carried by the **German Informatics Society (Gesellschaft für Informatik e.V.)**. GI represents large parts of the German CS community and provides an ideal forum for discussions on RDM and standardisation. In order to support this more specifically, a dedicated board level task force – Präsidiumsarbeitskreis NFDI⁷ – coordinates the related activities within GI.

3.1.1 Representatives of Computer Science sub-disciplines

Reflecting the broad spectrum of the academic discipline of CS, NFDIxCS features relevant researchers from all CS sub-disciplines according to the DFG categorization. A comprehensive discussion of our sub-disciplines is provided in section [4.1.2 \(Specific development stages in the sub-disciplines\)](#). However, over the lifetime of the project NFDIxCS, it is expected to include more sub-disciplines with open or new needs in RDM, as our governance model is designed as an open structure to include new developments, i.e. new sub-disciplines, new services or new task

⁷ <https://gi.de/netzwerk/fachgremien/praesidiumsarbeitskreise/pak-nfdi>

areas. We will also reach out to sister organisations like the ITG⁸ (Informationstechnische Gesellschaft) in areas of common interest.

All NFDI x CS consortium members were selected because of their expected contributions and their impact on RDM. This includes, besides scientific expertise in their related fields, to bring in existing collections of research data and tools and platforms, the willingness to share own and to reuse other research data, an understanding to act as driver of organizational or community development, and broad engagement in national and international academic networks.

Since we understand NFDI x CS primarily as a community development initiative, we rely on the existing organizational structure of our discipline within its professional society, the Gesellschaft für Informatik e.V. (GI). Ensuing technical challenges will be tackled by the entirety of the sub-disciplines involved. All necessary competencies are thus combined to design the components related to developing the broad field of RDM and open science for CS. This includes areas of CS with a strong application-oriented focus – still considered mainstream CS, e.g. connecting to psychology (Human-Computer Interaction), pedagogy (E-Learning), law (IT-Security) or management and economics (business information systems).

3.1.2 *Infrastructure providers*

An overall principle of NFDI x CS is to reuse, configure and assemble existing solutions and services wherever possible. That's why this consortium is characterized by a large number of infrastructure providers as a solid fundament of our work. The infrastructure providers will contribute in two ways:

- On the one hand, they bring in their expertise, tools and data as a huge treasure for those sub-disciplines related to IT architecture and operation (like high-performance computing, fault-tolerant systems and IT security). For instance, log files produced by real-world applications from any disciplines using the infrastructures of scientific data centres are of certain interest here.
- On the other hand, they bring in their powerful offers of compute and storage, publication and retrieval services. We will not only rely on those services when forming an NFDI for the CS community, but also the broad expertise of infrastructure providers regarding issues of efficient and sustainable operation and maintenance is of greatest value to NFDI x CS. This includes also competencies and experiences to run, monitor, size and price a large IT-infrastructure.

An important part of the cooperation within NFDI x CS will be to balance between the valid interests of researchers (to rapidly evolve infrastructure according to their very dynamic needs) and infrastructure providers (to keep installations stable, safe, affordable and maintainable). Several

⁸ <https://www.vde.com/de/itg>

co-applicants of our consortium are well-versed in tackling such challenges from their current or previous positions in between or across scientific and infrastructural institutions.

The infrastructure providers involved in NFDIxCS can be divided into three groups:

1. Data centres (tier 1 and 2, representatives of the Gauß alliance) with a focus on storage and compute resources for scientific tasks as well as federated services provided by DFN/eduGAIN,
2. Repositories (disciplinary like LZI and inter-disciplinary like maintained by FIZ) with a focus on publishing and retrieval of scientific results,
3. Providers of specific tools and platforms (like software heritage foundation, various scientific workflow and database tools, archive of formal proofs etc.) to be integrated into the above mentioned infrastructures.

While we focus on national partners for points one and two, we reach out in the international realm for the third point in order to enhance the infrastructures available in NFDI by available methods and technologies to a larger extent. Corresponding agreements are in the making.

All the aforementioned services as well as our project-related activities will be based on open-source tools (like Git, Docker, Proxmox, LXC Container, Shibboleth, Apache SolR, Indico or RDMO) and open standards and interfaces (like OAI-PMH, REST/SOAP, OAuth) to the maximum extent. The community is well-equipped with competencies to configure and use these tools across the board.

3.2 The consortium within the NFDI

NFDIxCS will be a part of the NFDI family. Some of the NFDIxCS partners are members of the NFDI association (NFDI e.V.) already, notably the applicant and GI as well. As part of this community and association, NFDIxCS will actively take part in the discussions and decision making as required and appropriate. We are ready to offer the specific competencies of NFDIxCS and interoperate with the emerging general NFDI infrastructure as this is an essential part of the overall NFDI approach. This applies particularly to the concerns addressed by the Berlin-Leipzig Declaration (Bierwirth et al. 2020) which was signed by NFDIxCS as well. Within NFDI we will be open to collaborate on equal footing with other consortia.

In addition to these general and obvious requirements a number of topics emerged in discussions with other NFDI consortia. These discussions revealed a considerable interest in cooperating and exchange of ideas and concepts in a number of areas:

1. Joint efforts to implement methods and technologies of RDMCs. This relates to artifacts, metadata, knowledge graphs, benchmarking, and possibly other areas emerging during the project's lifetime. In this context, it is crucial to ensure that the specific technologies developed in the mentioned areas and domains of a NFDI partner consortium are constructed in a conceptual and technical compatible way. Subsequently, either existing

solutions and technologies will be used or own solutions will be constructed to be interoperable with each other and outside NFDI-activities, e.g. Fair Digital Objects⁹, which have similar aims as the RDMC concept sketched in this proposal while NFDIxCS adds further elements / plugins to realize specific CS related properties in transformation and possibly encrypting the research data.

2. Collaboration on cross-domain, informatics-related topics by inviting each other to or jointly organizing community events. Examples are road shows, common webinars, exchange of presentation and demonstration material.
3. Potential cooperation in the area of general infrastructure elements, e.g. user helpdesk in areas of common technical NFDI cross-cutting topics.
4. Exchange of concepts and methods for own implementation of rights management and access protection procedures to sensitive data for satisfying ethical and legal requirements (e.g. general privacy needs, GDPR requirements, general data security).

These topics were specifically discussed and agreed upon with the consortia NFDI4DataScience, NFDI4Mobility, and FAIRagro.

With NFDI4Mobility moreover the following was agreed: NFDI4Mobility is complementary to NFDIxCS as it specifically addresses the domain-specific challenges of ground-based transport data and mobility behavior data. A major concern of NFDI4Mobility is the stepwise refinement of data from raw sensor data via different interpretation tasks to semantically rich, annotated, but also anonymized data. Here, NFDI4Mobility focusses on privacy challenges and domain-specific standards and interfaces for mobility data. NFDI4Mobility places less focus on generic standards for interoperability. Thus, we agreed to collaborate and to instantiate the NFDIxCS RDMC concepts for mobility data. This allows NFDI4Mobility to reuse our RDMC management solutions in their platform and at the same time serves as a case study for our RDMC concept, in particular for how to handle privacy considerations. Co-Applicants involved in both consortia will transfer our solutions for modernized publication processes with support for data publication, semantic annotations, and artifact evaluation to the mobility community.

In the same manner, NFDIxCS will be open to connect to other consortia – either existing or emerging – to address the topics given above.

3.3 International networking

International networking is simply a must-have for CS and is thus an important cross-cutting concern of all our efforts in NFDIxCS. The various sub-disciplines of CS are in different stages of maturity regarding the handling of FAIR principles. In some areas common metadata definitions exist as quasi standards and related repositories (e.g. Information Retrieval). In Software

⁹ see <https://www.go-fair.org/today/fair-digital-framework/>, <https://www.gida-global.org/care>

Engineering and other areas, the ACM artifact review and badging approach¹⁰ is being developed which provides guidelines for reviewing accompanying artifacts in a publication covering some part of the FAIR principles. In other sub-disciplines competitions and benchmarks exist which drive the respective field (e.g. SAT solvers or Graph Transformation engines). In other areas, repositories are maintained by a small set of volunteers.

All these efforts are part of the international community and it is accepted that there is no viable effort to limit these kinds of activities to a country or even a continent. Therefore, NFDIxCS will set out TA [M3 \(International Networking\)](#) which deals with the acquisition and integration of the international community at large.

In general, all the activities require, to varying degrees, international collaboration, discussion and agreement. Due to the diversity of activities and the different schemes and priorities adopted in the national research funding agencies, issues concerning the funding these kinds of activities may arise. They will be solved at least partly by using technology in terms of supporting virtual meetings and collaboration in order to achieve timely reaction and by a high degree of (semi-)automated workflow to avoid tedious manual administrative work.

The general approach is to use the existing network of contacts of the NFDIxCS co-applicants and participants and extend it continuously throughout the lifetime of NFDIxCS. Since GI is a partner in various supra-national associations, a good basis for reaching out at this level is given. Moreover, GI is a member of CEPIS and IFIP and has good contacts with other international organisations. Below, we briefly discuss the main contacts we have and would like to reach out. The areas to collaborate are in general:

- Metadata definition and standardization,
- Common definition and standardization of procedures and protocols,
- Sharing of technology and infrastructure,
- Cooperation in community development.

In terms of organizations, associations or other registered entities we are planning to reach out and collaborate with the following:

- The Research Data Alliance¹¹ (RDA) is an international initiative that focuses on community standards in RDM. The organisation is distributed and has national and European RDA sub-structures. RDA has been successful in bringing large user communities together in their plenaries. It is a natural venue for our consortium. We would participate in relevant groups and evaluate the proposal of new working groups in areas in which there are no community activities yet. This could include standards on execution environments, metadata models, software artifacts.

¹⁰ <https://www.acm.org/publications/policies/artifact-review-and-badging-current>

¹¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

- The Software Heritage Foundation¹² is an initiative whose goal is to collect, preserve, and share software code – both freely licensed and not – in an universal software storage archive. In addition, their aim is to enhance CS publications by making software citable. They have created a simple way to cite software down to the lines of code – level. We will pursue these activities and share and use the related technology. A respective Letter of Intent has been mutually signed. A mirror of the repository is brought up by the applicant (SHF@NRW).
- Informatics Europe¹³ represents the academic and research community in Informatics in Europe. Bringing together research in university and laboratories, it creates a strong common voice to safeguard and shape quality research and education in Informatics in Europe. With over 140 member institutions across 33 countries, Informatics Europe promotes common positions and acts on common priorities. The need for RDM has been recognized as an important area of activity for Informatics Europe and it will help to establish contact and links to foster the European wide collaboration.
- The Council of European Professional Informatics Societies¹⁴ (CEPIS) is the representative body of national informatics associations throughout greater Europe. Established in 1989 by 9 European informatics societies, CEPIS has since grown to represent over 450,000 ICT and informatics professionals in 29 countries. Similar to Informatics Europe, partners for reaching out to academics in CS will be used through this council.
- The International Federation of Information Processing (IFIP¹⁵) is the leading truly international association which joins national CS associations/societies. It is complemented by a strong technical expertise in Technical Committees and working groups. Membership in working groups is based on scientific and technical achievements. IFIP is recognized by the United Nations and other world bodies. It has a formal consultative partnership relation with UNESCO and represents IT associations and societies from over 38 countries or regions. IFIP sponsors numerous scientific CS events per year and has a substantial publishing activity. It runs its own digital library. Software and RDM has been brought forward in the discussion of the IFIP organisation especially in the area of publication and publication processes.
- The relevant international societies ACM¹⁶ and IEEE Computer Society¹⁷ (IEEE CS) are an important partner for global outreach activities. As mentioned above, the ACM artifact

¹² <https://www.softwareheritage.org/>

¹³ <https://www.informatics-europe.org/>

¹⁴ <https://cepis.org/>

¹⁵ <https://www.ifip.org>

¹⁶ <https://www.acm.org>

¹⁷ <https://www.computer.org>

review and badging approach is becoming more and more popular in their conferences and journals. We will address their approach and include and possibly extend these efforts in cooperation with the Software Heritage Foundation working in this area as well. Relevant interest groups are, e.g., SIGSOFT, SIGIR and SIGCHI.

- The Eclipse Foundation¹⁸ provides our global community of individuals and organizations with a mature, scalable, and business-friendly environment for open-source software collaboration and innovation. The integration of our interfaces to use and cite software as well as to support replication of results easily using Eclipse technology will be a collaboration topic with this organization.
- The Software Sustainability Institute¹⁹ addresses the importance of software in the research process. Since software plays an important role in RDM of CS-related data it will be important to reach out to this organisation in order to enhance best practices and deliver better tools for the communities in CS.
- The European Open Science Cloud²⁰ (EOSC) is a natural European partner for our activities and we reach out to this organization as well. Various areas of collaboration can be envisaged here at the levels we have identified here. We expect the NFDI association to establish the relevant links to support our goals. We'll observe the development regarding GAIA-X as well as they seem relevant as well.
- The EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure²¹ (EUDAT CDI) is one of the largest infrastructures of integrated data services and resources supporting research in Europe. It is sustained by a network of more than 20 European research organisations, data and computing centres that in September 2016 have signed an agreement to maintain the EUDAT CDI for the next 10 years. This infrastructure and its services have been developed in close collaboration with over 50 research communities spanning across many different scientific disciplines and involved at all stages of the design process. Similar to EOSC, EUDAT is a natural partner for our activities and we expect to reach out to this organization in the framework of the upcoming NFDI association as well.

These organizations are an initial list we plan to reach out from the beginning; first agreements on cooperation have been reached. Furthermore, we have good relations with neighboring associations/societies, e.g. VDI, VDE, GMA, and ITG. These all will bring our community together with important (national and) international players in the field.

In addition, numerous links for international collaboration and references to existing archives (like software models ReMoDD, Collective knowledge / cTuning or OpenAIRE) are described in section [4.1.2 \(Specific development stages in the sub-communities\)](#) where the various fields and

¹⁸ <https://www.eclipse.org/>

¹⁹ <https://www.software.ac.uk/about/manifesto>

²⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=open-science-cloud>

²¹ <https://www.eudat.eu/eudat-cdi>

sub-disciplines of CS are characterized. Members of the consortium and the CS community at large will provide the related contacts for collaboration. A strategy to structure and organize these collaborations in a systematic way will be part of the early work on management and community building.

3.4 Organisational structure and viability

It is essential that the development of real-world solutions for RDM, including standards and procedures, is driven by computer scientists in their respective research community. NFDIxCS wants to enable discussions by providing fora and aims for catalyzing discussions in and between sub-disciplines. The organisational framework for such bottom-up discussions will be provided by the GI. However, NFDIxCS aims for an open and inclusive RDM community and intends to include and to reach out to related scientific societies and partners on a level playing field. Therefore, NFDIxCS will establish a fair and transparent governance structure consisting of a general assembly, sub-disciplines, TAs, a steering committee, an executive board and three advisory boards. Fig. 4 provides an overview of these components. The governance structure as well as voting procedures etc. will be described in detail in NFDIxCS bylaws (Geschäftsordnung), based on the rules issued by the DFG and NFDI. These bylaws will be created and maintained by the General Assembly and signed by all (co-)applicants and participants.

Figure 4 The governance structure of the NFDIxCS consortium

General assembly: The general assembly consists of representatives (spokespersons and deputies) from all CS sub-disciplines and TAs. It decides on fundamental questions such as an

annual work programme, the final acceptance of research data and procedural standards, the incorporation of new participants and co-applicants, proposes for the creation of new TAs and appoints the members of advisory boards. The general assembly meets twice a year.

Sub-disciplines: Here, for each CS sub-discipline, a representative will be a member of the General Assembly. The task is to bring in the perspective, requirements, and expertise of these sub-disciplines.

Task Areas (TAs): The TAs are technical committees and organized alongside the project architecture, for discussions and work on identified technical and organizational needs for establishing a RDM infrastructure in CS. One representative of the responsible (co-)applicant serves as spokesperson and another representative from the consortium members active in this TA serves as deputy spokesperson at each TA. We foresee new TAs to be proposed in the future and additional activities to be included, or others to be finalized. NFDIxCS can rely on the specialist groups and technical committees of GI and will, through them, bring NFDIxCS services to the CS community. TAs meet frequently on the basis of their work plan and report to the general assembly on request of the executive board.

Steering committee: The steering committee comprises one representative from each TA. It makes fundamental decisions about the formation of TAs. The steering committee with support of the secretarial office observes and evaluates the KPIs and reports them to the general assembly. It also elects the executive board from the co-spokespersons in the steering committee. The steering committee meets at least four times a year.

Executive board: The executive board consists of six seats (one representative of each of the five layers of the project structure, see Fig. 9, as well as the applicant) and allows NFDIxCS to make decisions about the ongoing concerns. These seats will be assigned to specific business areas to be defined. The executive board meets on a regular basis. It is supported by the secretarial office. A representative of the applicant needs to be the chairing member of this board. The executive board reports to the general assembly on a bi-annual basis by which it is discharged. The executive board is, e.g., responsible for the risk mitigation plan and the performance of NFDIxCS.

Advisory boards: Three Advisory boards for the areas (1) strategy, (2) ethics and (3) scientific relations (including interoperability across NFDI & internationally) with up to five experts each are proposed by the executive board and appointed by the general assembly. They are established and staffed with external experts by the general assembly. The advisory boards advise the steering committee and its executive board in their respective areas of expertise. The advisory boards meet once per year and review the work of NFDIxCS. They combine their assessment and recommendations for the advice of the steering committee and executive boards, which is part of the annual report and the discharge of the executive board from liability to the general assembly.

Secretarial office: A full-time secretariat is responsible for the administrative coordination of NFDI x CS. In its role the secretariat supports the executive board, the steering committee, the advisory boards and the general assembly in their respective duties. The secretariat will be hosted by GI. The financial and other reporting to the DFG will be done by the applicant. The secretariat supports the respective functions of the applicant as well. Here, proposals (e.g. to include a new type of research data or a new dataset) and applications (e.g. of new members) will be received and directed to the appropriate body within the organisation of NFDI x CS.

For example, a proposal to incorporate a new repository into the NFDI x CS infrastructure contains information on formats, metadata, technical properties and data quality, and needs to be accompanied by an ethics statement. This will be first processed by an internal review committee checking all important aspects. Ethical issues will be dealt with according to the overall guidelines designed in TA [C4 \(Legal and Ethical Issues in IT\)](#) and agreed upon by the ethics board and the general assembly. In case of inadequacy of these guidelines the ethics board shall attempt to ameliorate or adapt the ethical guidelines. These steps will be supported by a workflow management system in order to address the special cases with the appropriate diligence.

The overall structure is designed for evolution in order to capture actual developments and usage patterns also beyond the funding periods. Thus we prepared the organizational structure accordingly and will design and adopt actual bylaws to support new and emerging sub-disciplines, new services and new types of research data. In the same way the general assembly of NFDI x CS can also decide to phase out specific activities and services. This will be based on the KPIs and their monitoring as well as community feedback and comments by the advisory board.

The entire endeavour of NFDI x CS aims at achieving a high degree of automation in the processes, protocols and services which are needed to run the infrastructure. Thus, it is necessary to always use up to date best practices to employ workflow automation, elicitation of requirements and preparation of decisions not to mention the operation of the core service as well as the support structures.

The overall issues regarding the operating model are discussed below in section [3.5 \(Operating Model\)](#) while the details regarding the related day-to-day management issues are discussed in TA [M1 \(Management of the Consortium\)](#).

3.5 Operating model

Our operating model integrates into future NFDI governance structures and complies with non-profit/public-benefit requirements and provisions. Below, we describe the overall goals and aspects for a sustainable operating model of NFDI x CS. The main goal is to realize the FAIR principles and increase the quality of CS research including the publishing processes.

3.5.1 Open Government Structure and Sustainability

From the start, the consortium consists of academic and non-profit partners. However, we create an **open governance structure** that is not restricted and allows the accessions of further partners to contribute. Thus, all activities and structures are open to the community as well as to other NFDI consortia. Above, we already sketched our collaboration approach to these immediate partners and others joining in potentially later. With respect to the openness requirement, we will also develop models that address specific needs of RDM resulting from research collaborations with companies or other profit-oriented partners, where additional aspects apply in terms of, e.g., specific access methods in the given RDMC respecting intellectual property rights, software licence schemes or privacy requirements of test persons. Details to this specific area will be addressed in TA [C4 \(Legal and Ethical Issues in IT\)](#).

NFDIxCS will create light-weight **service oriented managerial structures** which includes all aspects of support in running the organization (TA [M1 Management of the Consortium](#)). In terms of the day-to-day tasks, the overall effort is to support the goals outlined above by a modern and classic service organisation: Thus, besides the core of receiving and processing proposals and applications, service-oriented offerings like service catalogues, service descriptions with SLAs (Service Level Agreement), help desk and support lines, joint ticket systems or monitoring infrastructures are topics and tools which will be set up and kept in good operational health.

It will also be one major task of the ruling bodies of NFDIxCS (see previous section) during the funding period to develop models for evolving the project structure into an economically stable and long-lasting legal structure. The overall operation and activities of NFDIxCS will stay within the rules of a registered charity (non-profit status) and openness of the entire approach as required by the FAIR principles. To achieve this, the conditions and context have to be organized during the funding periods in such a way that the entire operation of the endeavour can be handed over to organizational structures which run at minimal costs and possibly a small usage fee. A small number of legal formats can be envisaged here which keeps the non-profit status and all the other properties related to openness and FAIR.

There are two possible candidates for a future **organizational model**: one is founding a new association, e.g. NFDIxCS e.V. as a non-profit organization (registered charity), another one is using the existing structures of GI (creating a new sub-structure like cross-sectional committee / Querschnittsfachausschuss) to translate the cooperative effort into the period after funding. The timeline for such a change has to be considered carefully and lies beyond the startup phase of NFDIxCS²².

²² Interesting options for operating models of this kind of collaborating bodies are discussed in <https://knowhow.ncvo.org.uk/organisation/collaboration/consortia/consortium-operating-models> although this page is very UK-oriented.

A sustainable **business model** for the long term will be developed within the funding period. The experiences from the operation of HPC centers will be used to define and evaluate the cost structures for the operation of the RDMCs. In principle, the aim will be to cover the operating costs during the funding phase through the funding or the partners' own contributions. The basis for the cost model is the monitoring (see architecture in Fig. 1) of the use and operation of the RDMCs. Based on the experience from the operation of (HPC) data centers, TA and the sub-disciplines will propose specific cost models to be decided in the General Assembly. We will keep costs as low as possible through the highest possible degree of automation in operating the infrastructure.

3.5.2 *Financial Plan and Performance Management*

Regarding **financial planning**, each partner of the consortium will provide an annual work plan for each TA that will be approved by the steering committee. The executive board will keep track of the performance of each TA and the project as a whole. The work plan refers in terms of milestones and short term goals to the measures laid out in the TA descriptions. An important part of financial planning will be the long term aspect which allows flexible spending and support also for future developments and unforeseen events and circumstances. Thus, certain parts of funding will be reserved for later project phases.

The performance of the project as such will be evaluated through a **performance management** approach: (1) definition of the goals and the KPIs, (2) assessment of the performance / KPIs and (3) readjustment of measures. In alignment with the NFDI initiatives the goals and the derived KPIs of NFDI x CS are described in section [2.2 \(Objectives and measuring success\)](#). Based on these evaluations, the general assembly and steering committee can make propositions and decisions about additional activities or finalization of activities (see section [3.4 Organisational structure and viability](#)). Based on these evaluations, the general assembly and steering committee can make propositions and decisions about additional activities or finalization of activities.

3.5.3 *Evaluation, Risk Mitigation and Quality Assurance*

The successful development of a vibrant and active research data ecosystem in CS critically depends on the quality of the services provided by NFDI x CS (see chapter [5 Work Programme](#)) and the scientific and research data quality. We additionally have to mitigate risks with regard to the project operation itself, the deployed services and the quality of published scientific and research data. For each of those areas, a quality assurance and risk mitigation plan will be developed and executed. Risk mitigation and quality assurance for the project and the services lies in the responsibility of TA [M1 \(Management of the Consortium\)](#). Risk mitigation and quality assurance for the scientific and research data will be executed by TA [M2 \(Quality Management\)](#).

The plans will be worked out by the TAs with support of the secretarial office in cooperation with the executive board and monitored by the steering committee.

Evaluation: NFDI x CS will provide a variety of services to the CS community. The related work is done in the TAs which are structured as outlined in Fig. 9 in section [4.1.3 \(Structuring research data management in CS\)](#). Once the services – as sketched in section [4.4 \(Services provided by the consortium\)](#) – are designed and deployed by the work in the TAs, there will be an annual evaluation of the project, the services and scientific and data quality of NFDI x CS in terms of the KPIs and the general considerations laid down above. The secretarial office will – in cooperation with TA [M1 \(Management of the Consortium\)](#) and TA [M2 \(Quality Management\)](#) and the executive board – develop and apply means to assess the practical implementation and the achieved outcomes of the services provided. The specific instruments will be developed with respect to:

1. the given expectations and assumptions by the community,
2. the individual goals and needs of the partners and
3. the specific nature of individual services.

NFDI x CS will apply different methods for the evaluation of the project, the services as well as the scientific and data quality, using standardized instruments wherever available:

- Qualitative means (e.g. interviews, observations, document analysis) will be dominant in the beginning of the project.
- A shift towards quantitative means (e.g. questionnaires, monitoring data analysis) will be seen in later phases of the evaluation.

A detailed description of all evaluation instruments based on the quality assurance and the risk mitigation plans along with a protocol on how to apply them will be provided to the steering committee. The secretarial office will prepare detailed reports for every TA from the gathered data, including interpretations of the findings and extraction of possible recommendations. Also, the secretarial office will help to fine-tune the evaluation methodology in case any obstacles or insights occur.

Risk Mitigation: In cooperation with the executive board, the secretarial office and TA [M1 \(Management of the consortium\)](#) will develop and implement a risk mitigation plan for the project and the services provided. The procedure is briefly sketched in Fig. 5 below. The risk mitigation plan will address all possible internal and external factors that can influence the project progress and performance. It will therefore provide for possible scenarios and countermeasures in the event that the identified risks materialize. This is the basis for detecting and reporting risks at an early stage and will be instrumental to allow risk mitigation at the management level and/or the ruling bodies of the consortium.

Figure 5 The risk mitigation scheme of NFDI x CS (see Rosu et al. 2017)

In first interviews and workshops the NFDI x CS consortium has identified the following risks as requiring particular attention for the services in place:

- dissatisfaction of users,
- excessively long response times to requests or
- not addressing the pressing needs of the community and individuals.

Updates of the risk analysis will be provided to the steering committee, and the resulting recommendations for the NFDI x CS services will be included in the yearly evaluation reports.

Quality Assurance: NFDI x CS will follow the experience of its service providers with their certification procedures (ISO 9001 and 27001). We will extend this mode of operation, also following ITIL principles, to other fields of service quality in NFDI x CS. Together with the secretarial office, TA [M1 \(Management of the Consortium\)](#) will develop a plan for quality assurance of the services in cooperation with the executive board and monitored by the steering committee. Once all the services are in place, the secretarial office will provide an overall analysis of the quality assurance, which will help to better understand and to improve the services. Means to assure the quality of research data and scientific quality will be devised and realized in TA [M2 \(Quality Management\)](#).

We are aware that quality management, besides the functioning of the project and the suitability of its services, also means to assure quality of published research data itself. Our measures towards this goal are described in more detail in the context of our research data management concept in section [4.3.2 \(Quality Assurance of Research Data\)](#). This implies to activate the community for recognizing quality as an issue and for taking additional efforts, why we pay special attention to measures for community involvement and development as described in section [4.3.3 \(Cultural Change towards FAIR Research\)](#).

4 Research Data Management Strategy

4.1 State of the art and needs analysis

4.1.1 Special requirements of computer science for research data management

CS research – with respect to the three roles mentioned above: processing of data with dedicated soft- and hardware systems, creation of such systems as well as gathering data through usage of such systems – is very diverse and can be assigned to formats of experimental, observational, analytical, interpretive, designing and/or model-building research. Accordingly, the research data generated in CS is manifold:

- strongly structured data (like measurement data in tabular form, graph descriptions, or data from theoretical computer science),
- semi-structured data (like log files from the operation of distributed computer systems, networks and IT security but also types of statements in and about software),
- unstructured data (like annotated image or text databases as a basis for method development in machine learning, empirical data from studies on HCI and e-learning).

The subject-specific processes for generating, managing, processing and publishing this data reflect this diversity. A survey conducted in 2019 among the 14 GI departments showed that the research data produced by computer scientists varies in structure and scope. The overall amount of research data per group covers the full range from small to big data, with a focus on medium-sized data sets. Also, it turned out that most researchers used local storage at their institutions or external storage providers, yet rather no discipline-specific platforms.

Figure 6 The amounts of research data handled by CS groups help to estimate current and future storage requirements.

Figure 7 The current storage locations of typical CS research data reveal a fragmented situation that might benefit from an overarching approach.

The current practice in CS research is to publish research results in classical outlets (proceedings of workshops and conferences; journals). The sharing of research results in terms of the involved data and related artifacts significantly developed during recent years due to the perceived need to not only see written statements about the results but the results themselves. Thus, review processes in some fields started to ask for access to the research data and software used to assess the validity of the authors’ claims. Of course, CS scientists were quick to come up with providing access on their websites to both aspects of their paper in question. However, it was immediately obvious that this approach was neither sustainable (since websites developed or vanished) nor fulfilled the requirements of modern review processes.

In addition, open-source became a tool on its own in research. Repositories were created and now even run commercially like e.g. GitHub²³. Open-source solutions like GitLab²⁴ support the development of complex software projects locally. Although produced and run primarily for “normal” software development, Git repositories provide local and distributed support also for the related research data and not only for software artifacts.

The typical way data and software are handled in CS shall be analyzed in more detail in the following section, in order to derive the special requirements associated with RDM and open science in our community.

4.1.2 *Specific development stages in the sub-disciplines*

NFDIxCS covers all sub-disciplines of CS where research data in various forms is involved. In the following, we present these sub-disciplines in more detail along with their respective

²³ <https://github.com/>

²⁴ <https://about.gitlab.com/>

processes, needs and existing solutions. Also, representatives from these sub-disciplines in the consortium are listed. We provide a characterization of every sub-discipline with respect to the following questions:

- *Representatives in the consortium:* How will they take care of the requirements and existing solutions stemming from this sub-discipline within NFDI x CS?
- *Characterization of the field:* What is the core research interest of this field? What does research in this field typically look like?
- *Examples for research data:* Which information is described? How are datasets structured? Is there an established routine or at least a typical practice of generation, processing and handling of such data? What are common formats or standards?
- *Existing approaches:* Which repositories exist in this field? Are there specific tools or services for data management?

From these profile descriptions of the sub-disciplines 409-xx, structured according to the DFG disciplinary schema, we isolate recurring issues that shall be addressed by an integrated infrastructure for RMD across the entire CS community. Wherever possible, this means to employ existing tools or services that have proven themselves; missing links or features might be developed on top of this. **Please note that in the following profile descriptions, several phrases relevant for RDM are marked with labels {XX} which indicate the recurring issues we identified in these fields.** These labels point to the TAs in NFDI x CS and will be aggregated to build the organizational structure of the project. We refrain from naming the full title of the TA here.

<p>409-01 Theoretical Computer Science</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tobias Nipkow • Christoph Benz Müller • Nicole Schweikardt • Alexander Steen 	
<p>Characterization of the field</p>	
<p>Theoretical computer science (TCS) primarily focuses on mathematical aspects of CS, historically emerging from a specialized sub-field of mathematics addressing basic notions of computability, algorithms and their computational complexity. Modern TCS is a well-established</p>	

field of research in its own right with a large and broad spectrum of topics, including (but not limited to) data structures, computational geometry, cryptography, automata theory, formal methods, parallel and distributed computing and computational logic. Research in TCS is characterized by mathematical rigor, applications of formal mathematical proof techniques, and, usually, its foundational character. In particular, the sub-discipline of automated reasoning and theorem proving can be described in a broader sense as applied mathematical logic. It deals with the theory, implementation and application of software systems for automatic or interactive proofs of formal logical statements from mathematics and CS. The central goal is the automation of formal mathematical reasoning on the one hand and, on the other hand, the practical support of its application to concrete problems from mathematics and CS. The applications hereby range from basic theoretical results, e.g., the proof of Kepler’s conjecture in mathematics, to applied academic and industrial applications, e.g., the verification of software and cyber-physical systems.

Examples for research data

<p>Formal proofs for interactive theorem provers. Each repository is associated with a specific theorem prover {A2}. Repositories are directories of text files {I1}. Current repository sizes are of the order of 1GB. Three widely used repositories {M3} are listed below.</p>	<p>Proofs are generated interactively by researchers with the help of a theorem prover. Proofs are checked by the theorem prover, archived {C2} and referenced {I2, A3} from other proofs and from publications. They can be updated continuously {D1}. Proofs are written in a formal language (specific to the theorem prover) {D2, A1}; the formal language may change from version to version {D1} and the libraries may change {A2}. The repositories are versioned {D1}, online and open access {C2, C4}.</p>
<p>Data for testing, evaluation and training of theorem provers. Proof problems in standardized syntax formats {C3} (e.g. for classical first- and higher-order logic) are used to test and evaluate automated theorem provers {D4, M2}. A prominent library is the TPTP library of proof problems; version v7.5.0 expands into 6.9GB (problems,</p>	<p>Proof problems are submitted by the community. They are assessed according to criteria such as novelty and difficulty (how many provers can solve them) {M2}. Only a portion of submissions is selected for inclusion in the TPTP library {C2}, which is the basis for benchmarking {D4} and yearly ATP competitions {M3}. The problems are analysed and formatted with additional tools from the TPTP infrastructure {A2}. TPTP is maintained and stored at Univ. of Miami, but a long-term solution is currently</p>

<p>axiom sets, documents, and utilities). Such problem repositories {I1} are increasingly being used for training models in automated theorem proving.</p>	<p>sought (one current option includes a move to Germany) {A1}. TPTP is online and open access {C2, C4}.</p>
<p>Theorem proving systems. The distribution {C2} of these software packages typically requires a few GB of space {I1}. This is software, not data, but it is required to interpret the proofs above {A2}.</p>	<p>The software is developed in cooperation by multiple academic groups {M3}. It is available in repositories {I1} that are versioned {D1}, online and open access {C2, C4}. Because both the software and the data are evolving, it is crucial to archive both in a synchronised manner {A2}. Theorem proving systems often maintain their own large test data sets {D4} (in addition to the shared benchmark data provided in libraries such as the TPTP {M2}).</p>
<p>Existing approaches</p>	
<p>existing datasets, repositories, tools and platforms are provided in Annex 1.2</p>	

<p>409-02 Software Engineering and Programming Languages</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Michael Goedicke ● Anne Koziolk ● Ralf Reussner ● Gregor Engels ● Wilhelm Hasselbring ● Timo Kehrer ● Jan Linxweiler ● Klaus Pohl ● Bernhard Rumpe 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Michael Striewe 	
<p>Characterization of the field</p>	
<p>Software engineering and programming languages research studies and develops methods for systematic development of software. Contributions include languages, processes, models, principles and especially advanced tools, such as code analyzers, model checkers or clone detectors or code synthesizers from models, to construct, evaluate, and maintain high-quality software. Research questions range from being exploratory or descriptive over questions about relationships or causality to being design-oriented. Research methods vary and include empirical, experimental, design-oriented and theory-building approaches. Scientific advancement is generated by developing new systematic and automatable methods and their underlying tool-based algorithms that are adopted in practice, as well as by generating insights about existing methods and on factors that influence their success. A particular challenge in software engineering is that the validity of research results is not always straightforward to assess. There is no single kind of research method that should be or can be applied for software engineering research questions. Consequently, several problems arise. First, reviewers in conferences and journals might not agree on the degree of evidence required for sufficient validation {M2}. Second, statements about results may be picked up and cited by other researchers {A3} without a sufficient explanation of the context of results and the validity of the respective study. Here, a better traceability of statements in research papers to the research data providing evidence for this statement is needed for a reliable, mature and reproducible publication culture {C1, C2}.</p>	
<p>Examples for research data</p>	
<p>Artifacts from third party software projects. Data can be source code, log files, requirements, design models, test cases, analysis models, informal user feedback, or any other kind of artifact used in or created during software development. The structure of data sets is arbitrarily chosen by the</p>	<p>Such artifacts have been analyzed with a new method {D4}, e.g. to detect bugs, flaws [I3] and vulnerabilities (e.g. in security) {I4}. Specifications of software languages used to create models (UML, SysML, DSLs, ...) and also the used generators or code synthesizers need to be included when archiving the data {D2}. Sometimes, researchers add annotations to the original data {D2, D3}. Additionally, sometimes authors create such data artificially, e.g. large generated instances of</p>

<p>original developers or data set creators {C3} and they are of varying size. A number of technology-specific data sets exist {I1}, such as the Qualitas Corpus for Java projects.</p>	<p>models or example systems using a new architectural style {D4}. Data might be published on platforms like Zenodo, but no formats or standards {C3} are established. Some conferences have a dedicated artifact evaluation track to review artifacts {M2} or a call for data showcases {C1}.</p>
<p>Data from empirical studies. This includes data gathered from or with human participants {I4}, e.g. solutions to modelling tasks, time to create the solutions, thinking-aloud protocols, or interview transcripts. If participants are asked to create software artifacts, this overlaps with the first data type.</p>	<p>Such data has been collected by CS researchers in dedicated studies and is usually processed by custom scripts {C3} or even manual interpretation. Often, but not always, data is published on common platforms like Zenodo {I1}, but there are no established formats or standards {C3}.</p>
<p>Software tools. These are research artifacts that embody a new algorithm, method or technique {A1, A2}, such as an application of model checking to certain forms of model/code combinations, a reverse engineering tool that extracts an architectural model from source code, a code synthesizer that derives a simulation model from an underspecified requirement etc.</p>	<p>Such data is created by researchers as part of their scientific contribution and published {C2} for use by practitioners, for reproducibility or for reuse by other researchers {A3}, usually on GitHub {I1}. Several conferences have artifact evaluation tracks to review such artifacts {M2, C2}. Authors can request badges {A3} according to the ACM artifact review and badging guidelines²⁵ (or others), e.g. the badge “available”. This requires a DOI for the project {I2}. Suggestions for describing the projects exist, such as the Artifacts Appendix²⁶ {D2}.</p>
<p>Existing approaches</p>	
<p>existing datasets, repositories, tools and platforms are provided in Annex 1.2</p>	

²⁵ <https://www.acm.org/publications/policies/artifact-review-and-badging-current>

²⁶ <https://ctuning.org/ae/checklist.html>

<p>409-03</p> <p>Security and Dependability</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hannes Federrath • Franziska Boehm • Daniel Demmler • Horst Schirmeier 	
<p>Characterization of the field</p>	
<p>Security & Dependability is a cross-cutting discipline with the focus on non-functional aspects of systems to operate securely and in a functionally correct, reliable and predictable way. On the one hand the aim is to provide functionality, performance and availability of complex systems even in the presence of faults, on the other, to ensure confidentiality, authenticity, and integrity of systems and data in the presence of attackers. This also correlates with legal requirements (e.g. data protection, intellectual property rights). Security features and privacy-protecting schemes are implemented, and their performance is evaluated. Strong security guarantees are shown by formally proving and verifying correctness, soundness, and security. The field is also researching usability and communication of security schemes as well as detection and analysis of security problems and their mitigation. Dependable computing is targeting fault-tolerance techniques using redundancy in systems. Working objectives are to assess the reliability of systems, e.g., failure probability and availability; to construct fault-tolerance techniques and to integrate them in target systems; to measure, analyze and evaluate fault-tolerance techniques w.r.t. to number of tolerated faults, coverage of different fault types, degradation of performance in the presence fault, and conformance to real-time requirements.</p>	
<p>Examples for research data</p>	
<p>Empirical Data. Fault analysis, malware samples, network traces etc. are used to analyse a system's</p>	<p>Empirical fault data or fault-injection experiments are used for reliability classification {I3, M2} of system components. Experiment results are accompanied with</p>

<p>behaviour in a faulty state and for tracking down the origin of faults. Network traces can be very large, e.g., several gigabytes or even terabytes of data {I1}.</p>	<p>target-system source code and binaries, execution traces, and fault lists for reproducibility reasons {A2}. Malware samples are delicate and require proper handling and secure storage {I4}. Databases of viruses {I1, C2} are important for analysing countermeasures and improving malware detection {M2}. Network traces {D4} capture the communication of multiple networked entities to analyze attacks or malware, to train and evaluate firewalls and intrusion detection systems, or to evaluate network performance {I3}.</p>
<p>Source Code and Binaries. There are many implementations of secure algorithms in source code {I1, C2} and in compiled form as binaries {A2}.</p>	<p>The source code of implementations of dependable and secure algorithms and programs are often managed through versioning systems {D1} like Git {I1}.</p>
<p>Benchmarks and Performance Measurement Data. System states and performance information {D4} like memory utilization or network throughput are captured to assess the performance of security and fault-tolerance measures {I3}. Profiling data should be as detailed and verbose as possible, leading to large data sets {I1}.</p>	<p>The information is processed and aggregated in order to evaluate and compare a specific measure {I3, M2}. Tools like profilers are typically language-specific {D2, C3}, but store detailed information about executions {D4, A2} that can be used to evaluate performance {I3}.</p>
<p>Existing approaches</p>	
<p>existing datasets, repositories, tools and platforms are provided in Annex 1.2</p>	

<p>409-04 Operating, Communication, Database and Distributed Systems</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agnes Koschmider ● Thomas Mandl ● Tillmann Rabl ● Philipp Schaer ● Matthias Weidlich 	
<p>Characterization of the field</p>	
<p>IT systems need to be dependable, secure, privacy protecting, resilient and scalable. Distributed, networked, and mobile systems research focuses on the principles and practice of engineering systems that meet these criteria. Applications range the field from big data analytics to the Internet of Things. This covers all aspects of information technology, including energy efficient and robust hardware systems, software defined networks, secure distributed systems, data science, and integrated circuits and power electronics. Benchmarking, as a central part of this discipline, gives insight into the performance of a proposed approach or allows to conduct a detailed benchmarking dataset analysis. Mostly, the focus is on collecting, pre-processing and analyzing data. Empirical and competition-driven research as well as user-oriented research is deeply rooted in this discipline. With test collections, developers and researchers create or optimize systems for the specific task. Particularly, in the domain of Information Retrieval, this leads to a result generated by a system for each information need, which is typically represented by a ranked list in decreasing order of probability of relevance. The run files describing the systems' response should also be part of the collections such that the performance of systems can also be analyzed later.</p>	
<p>Examples for research data</p>	
<p>Benchmarking data. These are text collections, which are basically a set of documents, formulations of information needs, and relevant</p>	<p>Data is gathered from real-life hardware and system components, including social media or commercial search engines {I4}. Common formats are BoW, Openlink and CL-XML {C3}. Processing of data follows</p>

<p>judgments of human jurors {D4}. Documents can be very heterogeneous {D2}. Data sets can be structured in terms of graphs in which nodes represent some terms/concepts and edges stand for semantic relations between them {D3}.</p>	<p>design-oriented research or user experiments with prototypes or empirical methods like questionnaires. Currently, re-use is an intensively discussed topic in the international research community {C1, C2, A3}. Often, even well-described experiments cannot be replicated or reproduced {M2}. For large and joined test collections {I1}, versioning, revision {D1} and information about the generation of the data {D2} are relevant.</p>
<p>System descriptions. Typical data consists of models or design artifacts of systems or prototypes as a combination of several components, protocols and algorithms for information handling and exchange in distributed environments {A1}. The run files describing the systems' response should also be part of the collections {A2}.</p>	<p>From these descriptions, the performance of systems can be analyzed later {I3}. This can become relevant for researchers interested in novel evaluation metrics {D4}. Currently, sharing {C2} and re-use {A3} are intensively discussed in the research community {C1}. Often, even well-described experiments cannot be replicated or reproduced {M2}. Ensuring reproducibility is still a major problem because the prototypes that are evaluated in the context of shared tasks are not published on a regular basis {C2, C1, M2}.</p>
<p>Experimental data. This includes logs of user behavior {I4} in either realistic environments or in test situations as well as collections of documents as a result of Web crawling {I4}. Logs are structured data sets {D2}, while information resources are often unstructured (text, images, video, audio etc.) and nested {D3} and may become very large {I1}.</p>	<p>Information needs should be labeled based on their features {D2, D3, I2} (e.g. contains named entities or geographic conditions) to allow specific research. Judgments of several persons (maybe conflicting for complex and subjective assessments {C4}) should be available for system development and re-use {D2, A3, C2}. With test collections {D4}, developers and researchers can create or optimize {I3} systems for the specific task. At the moment, GitHub and Zenodo have gained status as de facto standard {C3} portals to archive research artifacts like code and data.</p>

Existing approaches
existing datasets, repositories, tools and platforms are provided in Annex 1.2

409-05 Visual Computing	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Albrecht Schmidt ● Enrico Rukzio ● Bernt Schiele 	
Characterization of the field	
<p>Visual computing is the key discipline to enable effective and efficient interaction between people or with their environment. The research also considers the impact of system and visual design as well as architectural decisions in the development of information and communication technology on the experience of people’s use of technology. The field includes computer graphics, computer vision, interactive visualization, and human-computer interaction. It is concerned with questions of how information is presented for human users and also how computing systems can acquire knowledge about their context and the situation around them. Novel interaction and interface technologies are researched from a technical perspective (object recognition, 3D registration, efficient rendering) as well as from a user perspective (acceptability, efficiency of interaction, user experience). New knowledge and scientific progress are generated from research into algorithms, from experimental system research, and from empirical research. Systematic studies are used to validate and evaluate visual computing solutions. Such studies can be formative or summative and the approaches can be qualitative or quantitative. The results are new algorithms, methods, tools, and approaches that are experimentally and empirically validated, the development of new interaction techniques and technologies in software and hardware, and theories and models for visual computing.</p>	

Examples for research data	
<p>Datasets for image recognition or activity recognition. This includes, besides the multimodal media (e.g. images, sensor data, videos, audio recordings) itself, descriptions of the data set {D2} and the experimental context {A2} as well as labels for the media data {D3} (e.g. time codes).</p>	<p>In visual computing systems the recognition of the environment is one key challenge, like the classification of images (such as indoor vs. outdoor) or the description of what is shown in a video. Such datasets may also include further modalities {D3} such as sensor value (e.g. gyro, acceleration) or audio recordings. Typically, a research group creates a dataset and initial algorithm, and publishes it {C2} along with the recognition results {D4}. Based on this, other research groups publish superior algorithms {A3} using the same dataset {D4}.</p>
<p>Documentation of research systems and their use. This includes software (e.g. programs in different programming languages and interface descriptions) {D2}, hardware descriptions (e.g. boards, components, architectures) {A2}, descriptions of physical forms (e.g. CAD files, models for 3D printing) and multimedia data (e.g. videos) that document the operation and usage. These data can depend on or relate to each other {A2, D3}.</p>	<p>Experimental systems are developed and functional prototypes are implemented. Besides algorithms, such implementations are often complex {A2} including specific hardware (e.g. power wall display, tangible interaction controller, GPU computing setup), newly developed or adapted system software (or firmware), as well as test applications {I3}. Such prototypes are set up and operated for the specific research project or for a study and they are not permanent {C2}. Hence it is required to document and reproduce these setups {M2}. There are no standards yet {C3}, often researchers conserve this information as an add-on to publication {C2} in a ZIP-archive.</p>
<p>Data recorded from user studies. This includes a description of the apparatus {D2}, a precise study protocol including criteria for selection of participants {D2}, recording (video, audio, sensors, interactions, times etc.) of the usage {I4} as well as statistical analysis of</p>	<p>Prototypical systems are evaluated and tested {I3} with human users {I4}, using different technologies to fulfill given tasks (e.g. two different visualizations are used to make a decision). The procedure follows a precisely defined study protocol {M2}. Such studies can also be used to investigate behavioral patterns. This results in demographic data of the participants {I4}; usage data, such as speed of task completion and error rate; usage</p>

<p>the data collected, including the anonymized data {I4} and the scripts. The data is partly structured (e.g. usage data) and partly media data (e.g. audio or video) {D2}.</p>	<p>observations (protocols, audio and video recordings); biometric data (e.g. eye movement) {I4} as well as further sensor data. The collected raw data is processed {D3}, often anonymized {I4}, and statistically analysed {D4}. Up to now there are no standards for this {C3}, but such data is critical for the reproducibility of the results {M2}. The data is typically stored by the researchers themselves {I2}, and abstracted data (e.g. usage times, interaction data) may be included in or attached to publications {C2}.</p>
<p>Existing approaches</p>	
<p>existing datasets, repositories, tools and platforms are provided in Annex 1.2</p>	

<p>409-06 Business Information Systems</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agnes Koschmider • Vera Meister • Andreas Oberweis • Gunther Schiefer 	
<p>Characterization of the field</p>	
<p>On the one hand this field analyses information systems as phenomena with the aim of discovering cause-and-effect relationships and refers to behavior-oriented information systems research. On the other hand this field aims to develop and provide instructions for action that allow the design, construction and operation of information systems and their innovative concepts, referring to design-oriented research. Ideally, the knowledge process related to the research process is composed of four phases. In the <i>analysis</i> phase the design gap and related research questions and influencing factors are elicited using a rich portfolio of research methods (e.g., observations, expert interviews, case studies, deep systems analysis). In the <i>design</i></p>	

phase, the artifacts are derived using approved methods (tool-based modeling and reference modeling, construction of demonstrators, development of prototypes and method engineering), justified in the best possible way and distinguished from existing solutions. The *evaluation* of the artifacts against the defined objectives ensures scientific rigor using the following methods: Lab experiment, piloting, simulation, expert testing, field experiment. Finally, design-oriented science is interested in the greatest possible *diffusion* of results. An essential part of the scientific progress of this sub-discipline consists in the structuring and integrating of existing knowledge.

Examples for research data

<p>Model descriptions. Typical data in this field is Business Process Models or Models of Information Systems. Some specifications are formalized on XML basis {D2} and therefore the models are well-structured data and ideally interoperable {C3} between different tools {A2}. Dataset are typically rather small {I1}.</p>	<p>Since modeling is usually iterative, the model artifacts must be versionable {D1}. Usually, there are no special requirements in research data preparation {M2} for the publication process {C2}. There is no openly accessible {C4}, structured and sustainably maintained infrastructure for model artifacts {I2, C1}. Free data publication is established only in some sub-disciplines {C1, M2}. Models are stored in common or proprietary formats without specific documentation {D2} or direct links to an execution environment {A2}. Access restrictions can be important in cooperative research with industry {S1}. As long as open standards are used, licenses {C2} are not a restriction.</p>
<p>Knowledge bases. Typical data in this field is used to design or innovate an information system. Data has no common structure {C3} and is of rather small amounts {I1}.</p>	<p>There are five main forms of data processing: (1) informal sketch (hands on), (2) tool-based iterative modeling and model enhancement, (3) technical implementation, test & bug fixing, (4) publication & documentation {C3}, and (5) archiving {C3}, reuse {A3} & review {M2}. Data is mostly stored in GitHub {C2} without specific documentation {M2} or links to an execution environment {A2}. In commercial infrastructures, powerful BPM suites with repositories {I1} and social features {C1} are used. The open-source code {C4} of the modelers builds a</p>

	<p>foundation to design new research prototypes {A3} related to different aspects of business processes.</p>
<p>Empirical data. This is mainly raw and pre-structured data gathered from human participants {I4}, i.e. audio recordings, transcripts, or protocols of expert interviews, video recordings of software tests, event logs, results from questionnaires or other statistical data. Data sets are not necessarily large {I1}, but are usually very heterogeneous {C3}.</p>	<p>Usually, there are no special requirements in research data preparation {M2} for the publication process {C2}. The free publication {C4} of research data is only in some sub-disciplines part of the research culture {C1}. A positive example with regard to FAIR principles is Linked Open Vocabularies, publishing knowledge models but not raw data.</p>
<p>Existing approaches</p>	
<p>existing datasets, repositories, tools and platforms are provided in Annex 1.2</p>	

<p>409-07 Computer Architecture and Embedded Systems</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● André Brinkmann ● Christian Plessl ● Thomas Lippert ● Peter Sobe ● Bernhard Fechner 	
<p>Characterization of the field</p>	
<p>This research area studies the design, development, and evaluation of hardware and software components for computing systems, spanning the full spectrum from special purpose embedded to general purpose systems. Usually, the objective is to design well-balanced</p>	

computing systems that are able to meet target domain-specific goals (e.g. performance, data throughput, reliability) under design and operating constraints (e.g. cost, energy consumption, manufacturability). In addition to optimizing the basic components (processors, storage, networking, I/O) the consideration of system-level aspects provides challenges in modeling and evaluating the interaction of the constituting parts. Typically, research in this field follows a classical “computing systems approach”, that is, the developed components are integrated in a physical or computer-simulated prototype that implements or approximates the complete system. This prototype is then used for an empirical evaluation with scenarios that mimic expected use cases or particularly challenging edge cases. A main challenge in this field is the reproducibility of results {M2} and a fair comparison between different architectural approaches and implementations {I3}, as the artifacts cited in research papers {C2} are often not publicly available {C4} and benchmarks have been in many cases chosen ad-hoc {D4}.

Examples for research data

<p>Circuit descriptions. This includes netlists, hardware description languages and high-level specifications, that are used for evaluation {M2} of electronic design automation tools. Data sets are stored as source code {A2} or standardized text formats {C3}, such as EDIF, BLIF, or structural Verilog. Datasets range from MByte to GBytes {I1}.</p>	<p>Electronic design automation tools rely strongly on the ability to mix and match specialized tools {A1} that integrate, combine and process their input data stepwise from a behavioral technology-independent notation to a very technology-specific implementation description {A2}. Therefore, the individual tools in this toolchain are typically very flexible in reading and writing a wide range of data formats {C3}. Smaller benchmark specifications {D4} are extracted from commercial or academic design projects, full system benchmarks are taken from open-source hardware projects {C4}.</p>
<p>System traces. For instance, traces of storage system access patterns are provided as tuples {D3}, where each tuple includes, e.g., information about the accessed storage device, access time, operation type, anonymized</p>	<p>Traces are typically collected from production systems of huge Cloud providers {I4}, HPC centers, or medium sized academic institutes {D4} using built-in tools {A1} from operating systems or monitoring libraries {I3}. Data typically has to be anonymized {I4} before it can be published and the data is typically stored in a row-based format {D2} where each row describes one operation.</p>

<p>file or block information {I4}. Traces can grow up to several TBytes {I1}.</p>	<p>There are only very few archives available {C2} and no standards established {C3}.</p>
<p>Software artifacts. These contain source code or binaries of system-level software, which is often closely tied to specific use-cases {D2} and hardware environments {A2}. Size might be between several hundred up to millions of lines of code {I1}.</p>	<p>Embedded software often depends on specific hardware and I/O-structures {A2}. This bears additional challenges for replication studies {M2} exacerbated by short VLSI development cycles. The development and publication of software for embedded systems takes place in the same manner as for general-purpose systems, yet with special tools for single tasks. Software sources start to be regularly provided as part of the artifacts evaluation process {M2} of top conferences {C2}. Currently, these artifacts are typically published using GitLab or GitHub repositories {I1}.</p>
<p>Existing approaches</p>	
<p>existing datasets, repositories, tools and platforms are provided in Annex 1.2</p>	

<p>409-08 Massively Parallel & Data Intensive Systems</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Martin Schulz ● Ramin Yahyapour ● Wolfgang E. Nagel ● Matthias Müller ● Christian Bischof ● Michael Resch ● Martin Frank ● Stephan Hachinger ● Hendryk Bockelmann ● Hannes Thiemann 	

<p>Characterization of the field</p>	
<p>Computational Science has established itself as the third pillar of science, next to theory and experiments. High Performance Computing is its foundation and without it many recent scientific discoveries would have been impossible. Massive Parallel & Data Intensive Systems are at the core of a strongly interdisciplinary field, where computer scientists from computer systems, computer applications and software engineering provide fundamental components to enable their efficient use. Research includes the development of new models and parallel algorithms, the scheduling of processes, large-scale and parallel data management, networking protocols, the visualization of huge data sets, as well as parallel architectures geared toward high data throughput and the needed middleware. The evaluation of new methods is typically coupled to experiments scaling these methods to thousands of nodes, while the resulting data sets combine data which can be directly gathered by the application itself, or by log traces of the system. Coupling both data sources enables researchers in parallel and data-intensive computing to understand the impact of the underlying architectures on their new methods and protocols. Performance engineering often uses logs and profiling information (both on the application and the system level). Most data sets are time series. However, concrete data formats {D2} and meanings of metrics {D3} may be different from center to center and possibly from architecture to architecture {C3}. Often the collected data represents characteristics about a specific application {A2}. Reproducibility of results and open data are important {M2, C4}.</p>	
<p>Examples for research data</p>	
<p>Sensor and log data. These are typically fine-grained time series and include tracing data about storage accesses, network requests, CPU usage, energy data or environmental sensors. Most data is proprietary {C3}, and tracing tools rely on a different syntax {D2} and semantic {D3}. The data sets are often large {I1}.</p>	<p>A number of tools emerged for joint data and metadata standards {C3}. This, e.g., led to the development of the Open Trace Format OTF2 {D2}. Other solutions rely on open protocols from other domains {C3}. Additional information {D2} on software and OS versioning {D1} could be integrated into the data streams; in fact, some logging environments already provide such data. A general tradeoff is the logging granularity in contrast to the size of the resulting data sets {I3, M2}, as HPC applications can scale to millions of compute cores.</p>

<p>Batch system data. This includes information on which jobs have been submitted to which cluster at which time, on which resources and for how long these jobs have been running on how many nodes. It also contains information on which nodes of a cluster have been operational when and which users/groups {I4} have used which access quotas. Data sets are rather small {I1}, as the number of jobs is in the order of a few thousands per day.</p>	<p>This data {D4} is used in simulators to analyze the performance {I3} of novel scheduling tools or to predict performance {I3} of future machines at design-time. The batch data represents a benchmark {D4} to compare different algorithms. Some of these data are publicly {C4} available to the community {C2} on individual web pages by the authors {C1}. There is the Parallel Workload Archive, that is suggesting the common SWF format {C3}. However, this archive has no institutional support and lacked activity in recent years {C1}.</p>
<p>System Metrics: Many system metrics are collected on the level of filesystem, I/O, network access {D4}. For instance, each parallel file system typically provides tracing capabilities {D2}, while higher-level logging tools try to generalize file system accesses. Such information can easily lead to TBytes of log files {I1}. Log data is therefore typically stored in a (tool-specific) compressed binary format {C3} that can be extracted using tool specific extensions {D2}. In addition, node descriptions {D2} include textual or lightly structured log files. Information is organized as time-series data and collected independently of applications {D3}.</p>	<p>Most HPC applications access data through a parallel file system like Lustre or GPFS. To analyze and predict the application and system performance {I3}, it is essential to have representative data on I/O workload {D4}. HPC centers collect and store node-level monitoring data {I1} to complement facility-level information for operational data analytics {I3}. It can be mapped {D3} to compute jobs and applications again using indexing information from the batch system data {D2}. In addition to the statistics of network interfaces generated and collected at the node-level, network switches typically provide accumulative counts of passed packets' counts and sizes. By polling these counts, sites collect a time-series of transmission rates and bandwidth in local repositories {C2}. Solutions are typically internal to individual data centers, curated in their own formats {D2} and, for security reasons, accessible only by selected users {I4}.</p>

Existing approaches
existing datasets, repositories, tools and platforms are provided in Annex 1.2

409-09 Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ramin Yahyapour • Jens Heidrich • Ulf Leser • Ute Schmid • Wolfgang E. Nagel 	

Characterization of the field

Data Science and Artificial Intelligence is an interdisciplinary research field comprising methods for managing and analyzing (large) data sets that requires techniques from data engineering, data analytics, data prediction and machine learning, including data storage, transfer, protection, archiving, curation, indexing, and visualization of data. Popular analysis methods are, for instance, regression, classification, predictive analytics, outlier detection, recommendation algorithms, or clustering of data. The research can be distinguished in (a) the application-oriented and domain-specific adaptation of general methods and (b) the development of new methods in the respective fields, such as new architectures for deep learning or new algorithms for efficient data management. In NFDIxCS, we target method development as a genuine research field with strong links to RDM. Artificial Intelligence is a key research discipline which leads to new curricula for teaching and training but also to new research institutes as organizational entities {C1}. Research cannot only be seen in the application of its methods in other disciplines but also needs a solid foundation and continuous innovations in its underlying basic methods. This, in turn, requires access to large collections of relevant data sets {M2, C2} for evaluation and training {C1}. Such tools and frameworks are developed and adapted to specific domains. Specific, resource-hungry models of data analytics are often co-designed with specific hardware architectures and/or with distributed and parallel

<p>systems {A1, A2}. To deal with large data sets, these models often require special computing infrastructure like HPC or GPU clusters {A2}. This limits the ability to reuse methods {M2}.</p>	
<p>Examples for research data</p>	
<p>Training data. Annotated training data sets for supervised training {D2, D4}. The structure depends on the data type {C3}. These could, for instance, be images or other media data {D2} and thus easily reach TB size {I1}. Metadata is usually well structured in XML or JSON {C3}.</p>	<p>Research on new methods in data analytics often requires access to training data {A3}. In the ideal case this data is annotated {D2} to serve as a ground truth for comparative studies and benchmarking {D4}. Access to large and high-quality data sets {M2} is essential. Typical data sets deal with object recognition in images, natural language or sensor data processing to develop new algorithms. There is often a distinction between primary data and the associated metadata in many application cases. Metadata {D2} is as essential for data science as the primary data itself, as it contains information on provenance {A3}, classification {D2, D3}, quality {M2} and context {A2}. There is significant research work on metadata {D2}.</p>
<p>Knowledge Graphs. These data sets are a common method to represent information through relations between real world entities. Many of these graphs {D3} are large in the plus 100 TB scale and also pose an infrastructure challenge {I1}.</p>	<p>Historically, knowledge graphs were often manually generated {M2} by experts, nowadays they are automatically generated {C1} based on analysis of large data sets, e.g. from the web, social networks {I4}, text or metadata analysis {D2}. These graphs are constantly extended and updated {D1}. As such, it is a challenge for referencing {A3} and comparing work {D4}.</p>
<p>Benchmarking Datasets. This data is used to compare the performance {I3} of a new approach with existing ones {D4}. The type and nature depends on the specific</p>	<p>Research in data management and analytics requires the ability to compare algorithms and to evaluate the performances {I3, M2} in view of the state of the art. Beyond training data sets {A3} it is essential to have relevant benchmark data {D4} available and support reproducible {M2} comparisons on performance.</p>

application case or modality {C3}. There are common cases available.	
Existing approaches	
existing datasets, repositories, tools and platforms are provided in Annex 1.2	

409-10 Interactive Systems	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ulrike Lucke ● Florian Alt ● Antonio Krüger ● Sven Strickroth 	
Characterization of the field	
<p>This multidisciplinary field is concerned with the interaction between users and systems consisting of software and/or hardware components. This includes the conceptualization, implementation, and study of new forms of human interaction with these systems, but also how existing systems can be improved for human usage. Research considers human capabilities & limitations as well as psychological, technical, and design aspects of interfaces. The goal is to support existing or enable novel processes, human-to-human and human-to-system communication, and user experiences, potentially personalized to individual users. Research can be formative and summative, yielding qualitative and quantitative data, often generated in a user-centered design process. Common methods include experimentally exploring possible design solutions, prototyping, model building, empirical studies, design-oriented research, feasibility studies, and performance investigations. The results are new methods, procedures, theories, models, artifacts and systems, which are validated against objectives (e.g., educational, performance-based, experience-based etc.) experimentally and empirically. This includes the investigation of how new forms of human interaction with digital systems and data; how specific (e.g., educational) processes can be supported or even made possible through interactive systems; and how such systems or interfaces should look like on the technical level</p>	

<p>and the design level. The research also considers the impact of design and architectural decisions on the experience of people's use of technology.</p>	
<p>Examples for research data</p>	
<p>Empirical data. This includes, for instance, data from surveys, observation notes and audio/video recordings of human participants {I4}. Data can be either highly structured or raw / annotated recordings {D2}. The amount of data ranges from short texts to large video collections {I1}.</p>	<p>This kind of data is usually processed with statistical (quantitatively) or with annotation (qualitatively) software {A2}. Other tasks such as transcribing or aggregation might be required. Such processing usually takes place manually {M2}. No standard exists {C3} and raw data is often not shared {C2}. Anonymization of data might be required for sharing {I4, C4}.</p>
<p>Experimental data. This includes logs or traces of user and system behavior. Typical sources are physiological sensors (e.g., EEG), eye tracking, typing data, or click streams. Such data is often well-structured, yet formats are diverse and use-case specific {C3, D2}. Depending on the time period, a significant amount of data may occur {I1}.</p>	<p>Such data is typically produced in lab and field studies or with models in simulations for evaluation of prototypical systems {D4}. Analysis is manually {M2} or with special scripts {A2}. First standardization approaches exist {C3}, for instance, in learning analytics with the Experience API; however, vocabulary is not yet standardized {C3}. Data and scripts are often not yet shared {C2}, but archived locally {I1}. Some journals allow publishing of supplementary data {C2}. There is a high demand for common datasets {A3} in the design of adaptive systems.</p>
<p>Design artifacts. This is the mere content of multimedia applications. The data might be placed in a system by researchers prior to a study (e.g., 3D models) {D2} or actively created by users while using a system (e.g., educational content) {I4}. The data can be very</p>	<p>For specific types (e.g., educational content) exchange standards do exist {C3}. For sharing created artifacts {C2}, versioning {D1}, licensing {C4} and referencing {A3, D3} are required. Data might require further processing {A2}, curation or quality assurance {M2} before it can be shared (e.g. anonymization {I4}). Sharing of data allows others to reuse the content (e.g. for their own teaching or studies {A3}), to replicate studies (e.g., for verification</p>

diverse in type, size {I1} and format {C3} depending on the respective application field.	{M2}), or as a ground truth to test and benchmark new algorithms (e.g. for automatic grading) {D4}.
Existing approaches	
existing datasets, repositories, tools and platforms are provided in Annex 1.2	

These profile descriptions show that the maturity level of CS sub-disciplines regarding FAIR management of their research data varies. In some areas, mechanisms are still missing. In others, they have already been developed but are not yet widely established. However, the need for sharing and reusing research data and for a systematic approach to reach this goal is well-aware in all sub-disciplines. Also, collections of research data exist in all fields to a greater or lesser extent. Finally, tools and/or platforms for RDM are partially available or at least under development. Thus, the current window of opportunity is favorable to push forward the intended development of the CS community towards the FAIR principles. Also, there are **recurring approaches and needs** for RDM (marked {XX} above) **in all sub-disciplines** that are subsequently combined into a consistent RDM architecture and project structure, overcoming the currently dominating isolated solutions and achieving an integrated environment.

4.1.3 Structuring research data management in computer science

In summary of the profile descriptions of our sub-disciplines presented above, the CS community is dealing with a large variety of data types that is or has to be considered for sharing, archiving and publishing. Besides **(1) traditional datasets** (usually originating from a specific field of application), our work focuses on **(2) software as research data**, and the preservation of its **(3) environmental conditions** (context) as a third category of CS data. Data can be related to each other, e.g. several datasets are linked to the same software for production or processing, or a software requires a certain execution environment. Moreover, data can be associated not only with **(4) metadata** (as familiar from other disciplines) but also with different forms of **(5) documentation** (e.g. admin, developer or user manuals as well as abstract level design artifacts).

Figure 8 The conceptualization of CS research data in NFDI x CS addresses the characteristics of the discipline in the variety of data types involved.

Independently of the respective sub-discipline, this conceptualization of CS research data (see Fig. 8) can be considered a general model for data handling across CS. Against this background, a project structure is needed to address the objectives and to implement the architecture, systems and services proposed in section [2.2 \(Objectives and measuring success\)](#). Such a structure must align the approaches already in place in the community with the needs still existing elsewhere. Thus, we derived the NFDI x CS project structure from the profile descriptions of the sub-disciplines as follows.

In a qualitative content analysis (Mayring & Fenzl, 2014) of the profile descriptions presented in section [4.1.2 \(Specific development stages in the sub-disciplines\)](#), **recurring issues** were identified, aggregated to general concepts and marked in the profiles. This included existing approaches as well as stated needs for all these issues, forming the Taks Areas (TAs) of NFDI x CS. By matching the capabilities and the requirements of our sub-disciplines we are able to develop and deploy the respective services and processes for the entire CS community by experienced service providers. For a better overview, we grouped the TAs – which are packages of work for NFDI x CS – in a layer structure (see Fig. 9). The technical issues on the three lower layers will be organized in an automated mode as far as possible. They are grouped according to the subject of the work: basic data layer, core IT layer and NFDI application layer. The remaining TAs in the two upper layers rely on interactions between humans. They are grouped according to the nature of the work: community layer and management layer. In summary, this leads to the overall **structure of the consortium** presented in Fig. 9 – derived from the profile descriptions of the sub-disciplines and their declared RDM needs and solutions– for shaping and re-organizing RDM in CS.

Figure 9 The project structure of NFDI x CS assigns the identified Task Areas (TAs) to five layers, forming the operative basis of the consortium.

We identified the following aspects related to basic handling of data (labeled as {D_i} in the profiles) occurring across all sub-disciplines:

- D1 – Version Management
- D2 – Metadata and Protocols
- D3 – Semantic Aspects
- D4 – Data for Benchmarking

These issues form the TAs in the **Basic Data Layer** (TAs D1-D4) of NFDI x CS.

Based on such data and specific to the CS community, a number of recurring core IT services were identified from the profile descriptions (labeled as {I_i}) of the sub-disciplines:

- I1 – Storage and Repositories
- I2 – Persistent Identifiers
- I3 – Performance Management
- I4 – Security and Privacy

These issues form the TAs in the **Infrastructure Layer** (TAs I1-I4) of NFDI x CS.

Moreover, we identified three additional IT services with certain relevance for open science and FAIR data exchange and reuse from the profile descriptions (labeled as {A_i}):

- A1 – Architectures and Interfaces
- A2 – Reusable Execution Environments
- A3 – Citation and Attribution

They form the TAs in the **NFDI Application Layer** (TAs A1-A3) of NFDI x CS.

Certain issues recurring across the profile descriptions (labeled as $\{C_i\}$) cannot be addressed by technical means but require a cultural change (DFG, 2018) in how the CS community is doing research and developments:

- C1 – Community Development
- C2 – Publication Processes
- C3 – Standardization Processes
- C4 – Legal and Ethical Issues in IT

These issues form the TAs in the **Community Layer** (TAs C1-C4) of NFDIxCS.

Additionally, we identified two top-level issues (labeled as $\{M_i\}$) in the profile descriptions. We also foresee a management structure for NFDIxCS:

- M1 – Management of the Consortium
- M2 – Quality Management
- M3 – International Networking

These issues form the TAs in the **Management Layer** (TAs M1-M3) of NFDIxCS.

Each of the key issues listed above forms a TA and is described in more detail in the respective sub-section of chapter [5 \(Work Programme\)](#).

4.2 Metadata standards

The challenge of the data infrastructure NFDIxCS is to integrate a variety of heterogeneous resources, each of which follows its own paradigm, structure and language. This requires machine-readable metadata for automated information extraction and data analysis. Though a number of data collections do already exist, there is no common metadata standard for CS research data. Existing repositories (like Git for software) rely on rather superficial descriptions of, for instance, name, author and date of origin for that piece of software. This makes it hard to search for, as an example, software that follows a certain design pattern, uses a certain technology, may run on a certain hardware, complies with a certain policy or fulfills a certain purpose.

Existing general-purpose metadata schemes (for instance, based on Dublin Core²⁷ in the library domain, and DataCite²⁸ or FAIR digital objects²⁹ for publication of research data) do not cover discipline-specific aspects of CS research data. Even for simple text files basic issues like the applied encoding schema – which has a huge impact on reusability of that data – are not specified. However, existing schemata can and will be used as a starting point for further refinement. This has been done, for instance, for specification of the LOM³⁰ (Learning Object Metadata) standard, which is widely accepted in sub-discipline [409-10 Interactive Systems](#) and

²⁷ <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dces/>

²⁸ <https://support.datacite.org/docs/schema-40>

²⁹ <https://www.go-fair.org/today/fair-digital-framework/>

³⁰ https://standards.ieee.org/standard/1484_12_1-2020.html

builds a basis for the catalogues and search engines of common educational repositories. Also, there is lots of experience in closely related fields, like the EMBL-EBI initiative³¹ in bioinformatics, which we are willing to learn from for setting up similar activities in CS.

We are well-aware that it is a huge challenge and effort to collect requirements for such metadata schemes, to agree upon a common vocabulary and taxonomy, to adopt this as a standard and to implement it in scientific practice. That's why we defined a separate TA ([C3 – Standardization Processes](#)) for these activities. Regarding metadata, this will be done in close cooperation with TA [D2 \(Metadata and Protocols\)](#) and TA [D3 \(Semantic Aspects\)](#). We expect to end up with not a single specification, but with a hierarchical set of metadata schemata to meet the diverse requirements of our sub-disciplines. Besides the disciplinary structure, there are also dedicated requirements to be considered originating from certain tools or schools of thought. Also, to agree on a common specification is a matter of distribution of power. That's why our aim is to intertwine our measures for community development TA [C1 \(Community Development\)](#) towards an open science culture in CS research and those for international networking TA [M3 \(International Networking\)](#) with these measures for standardization TA [C3 Standardization Processes](#) especially of metadata TA [D2 \(Metadata and Protocols\)](#) and semantic aspects TA [D3 \(Semantic Aspects\)](#).

The CS community is methodically well-prepared to specify abstract-level descriptions of an entity. There are plenty of formal description languages to model, for instance, domain-specific data structures (syntax and semantics), system components (structure and behavior), environments (input from and output to human and/or technical context) etc.. These vocabularies will be a valuable basis to derive metadata standards by a) categorization of possible dimensions and features of different CS research data and b) relating them to each other within a taxonomy. For this, TA [D3 \(Semantic Aspects\)](#) will rely on previous work on the Open Research Knowledge Graph³² (ORKG). It is still quite abstract and more at the level of publications and experiments. However, it can be used to e.g. link papers with the datasets used in the paper. Structures in the ORKG are extensible, which we intend to use for CS-specific approaches to characterize our dedicated types of research data (as sketched in section [4.1.3 – Structuring Research Data](#)) according to the identified needs of the sub-disciplines.

The challenge of metadata management in NFDI x CS is the availability of vocabularies optimally reflecting necessary technical specifications, formats, languages, notations etc. for all categories of data in CS. Some effort is undertaken by the Research Data Alliance (RDA). Table 4.2.1 compiles a selection of relevant approaches for these categories of data and thus exemplifies the range of items to be covered by metadata vocabularies to be developed for CS.

³¹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/>

³² <https://www.orkg.org/>

Table 4.2.1 Dimensions for specification of selected CS data (sub)categories
(only samples given in no way a claim for completeness)

Data Category	Data Subcategory	Examples for technical specifications, protocols, formats, languages etc.
Data sets	strongly structured	SQL, RDF, SPARQL, GraphQL, JSON, XML
	semi-structured	CSV, TSV, NetCDF, HDF5, Apache Parquet
	unstructured	txt, mp3, mp4, jpg
Software	formal models	UML, BPMN, DMN, ArchiMate, ERM
	scripts	Python, R, MatLab, Visual Basic
	web/microservices	HTTP, REST, JSON, AMQP, MQTT
	complex systems	YAML
Context	operating systems	MS Windows, macOS, iOS, Android, various Unix versions and derivatives
	Programming models & runtimes	C, C++, Fortran, Java OpenMP, MPI, CUDA
	supporting services	CI, CD, container services, server virtualization
	hardware	Configuration files, specifications, emulators if available/necessary
	Physical location	GPS, Address, location in rack, room number

The task of the consortium is to identify and evolve existing standards as well as to develop new ones in case there is no standard available in a dialogue with the community and its sub-disciplines, and to promote their usage. The starting point for proper metadata definition and management will be existing schemata. NFDIxCS will raise awareness for metadata issues in CS, improve the visibility and thus findability of CS resources and link information across different repositories.

Ontologies are a fundamental pillar of enabling linked FAIR research data. The following three actions will be taken to build a semantically rich ontology (see TA [D3 Semantic Aspects](#)). First, we will determine which upper ontology to base our semantic descriptions on and extend this ontology with additional common entities, relations, classes, functions and axioms of CS research data. This will be done in a modular way, so that domain-specific parts can be attached easily and on-demand. Second, the domain-specific ontology parts will be designed as modules. The

resulting ontologies will be implemented in standard ontology languages, such as RDFS or OWL. Third, a knowledge graph based on the defined ontology will be provided and filled as part of this work, including automated support in the publication process to fill the knowledge graph (see [TA C2 Publication Processes](#)).

It is important to strengthen process-oriented metadata management along the data lifecycle and the re-usability of metadata to reduce the burden of documenting data as well as to assure quality of that metadata. Researchers must be encouraged in their roles as data users and data producers by supporting the documentation of data as early as possible during the preparation of the data collection using custom metadata-tools, which is also a task of the consortium. NFDI x CS will institutionalize a stable community of practice and establish continuous improvement processes. The improvement processes will take into account international standards in the field, with a focus on harmonising, internationalising and standardising current developments e.g. in the context of RDA and other related policy-making bodies.

4.3 Implementation of the FAIR principles and data quality assurance

Based on our understanding of the FAIR principles in their application to CS we discuss the implementation of the principles by measures across the project. Then, our approach to quality assurance for research data is described. Finally, we outline planned activities to involve the community and to drive a cultural change towards FAIR research by NFDI x CS.

4.3.1 Measures to Implement the FAIR Principles across CS

The FAIR principles are the guide and compass for the work within NFDI x CS. The design of the infrastructure, the services and the processes will always carry the FAIR principles as general requirements. As has been discussed in various places^{33,34} these requirements have to be complemented with possible conflicting requirements e.g. in terms of legal, intellectual property rights or privacy requirements, and not all FAIR principles can be realized to the utmost extent. We foresee creating separate views on the metadata and data that satisfy the varying requirements. The use of a specific view is then controlled by the role a user has. Also a number of rule sets, process models etc. have been set forth to guide RDM in general (see e.g. RISE³⁵ and Diamant³⁶) and support ways to implement the FAIR principles within scientific practice. Here, we address the measures at an abstract level to support and guide the work within NFDI x CS to use these knowledge sources. We walk through the principles to point to the planned measures and

³³ <https://www.force11.org/fairprinciples>

³⁴ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

³⁵ The RISE-DE Reference Model <https://zenodo.org/record/3585556#.X3DX5C-21VQ>

³⁶ The DIAMANT-Model 2.0 Reference Process <https://ubt.opus.hbz-nrw.de/frontdoor/index/index/docId/1432>

discuss them briefly at the level of specific TAs mainly addressing the above-mentioned topics. It is worth noting that the realization of FAIR is cross-cutting for all TAs without further mentioning.

- To be **Findable**: This principle addresses the role and properties of identifiers and metadata which are part of a search infrastructure identifying the data and related context. The general related concepts for CS research data as characterised in the profiles above will be specifically addressed in two TAs: [D2 \(Metadata and Protocols\)](#) and [I2 \(Persistent Identifiers\)](#). Specific emphasis will be on the NFDI and international aspect of this principle. In order to be able to connect to and interoperate with other partners, specifications need to be standardized between stakeholders beyond NFDIxCS also internationally. One task of TA [M3 \(International Networking\)](#) will be to establish links for standardization discussion and decision making (see also section [3.3 International networking](#)).
- To be **Accessible**: This principle addresses the way research data is actually stored and can be accessed through the metadata and identifiers via a search infrastructure. Related open protocols using open authorization and authentication will be key for this topic. In NFDIxCS specific TAs will address its realization. The TAs [I1 \(Storage and Repositories\)](#) and [D2 \(Metadata and Protocols\)](#) provide realizations in terms of the required open protocols and the store and search infrastructure. TA [A1 \(Architectures and Interfaces\)](#) provides an overall architecture to implement the protocols and the technical interfaces providing the access to the resources. Roles and Access are addressed in TA [I2 \(Persistent Identifiers\)](#).
- To be **Interoperable**: Interoperability has to be realized at all levels of our research data management architecture (see Fig. 9). The metadata and related protocols need to be open and shared among the community at large and also need to be integrated into the general infrastructure of NFDI. This particular challenging part will be addressed by TA [A1 \(Architectures and Interfaces\)](#) as well as TA [D2 \(Metadata and Protocols\)](#). It will also need effort by TA [C1 \(Community Development\)](#) and [TA C3 \(Standardization Processes\)](#) which implements specific workflows for discussion and decision making addressing the topic that the metadata itself needs to FAIR as well.
- To be **Re-Usable**: This principle addresses the way the research data can be reused easily and openly. Plurality of attributes, access license(s), provenance and community standards are the aspects addressed specifically by the TAs [D2 \(Metadata and Protocols\)](#), [C4 \(Legal and Ethical Issues in IT\)](#), [A3 \(Citation and Attribution\)](#) as well as [C3 \(Standardization Processes\)](#) and [C1 \(Community Development\)](#). A specific aspect supporting reusability will be addressed in TAs [A2 \(Reusable Execution Environments\)](#) and [A1 \(Architectures and Interfaces\)](#). While the former will provide concepts and implementations of the RDMC concept (see Fig. 2) the latter TA addresses the whole

structure where instances of RDMCs can be maintained and provided for storing and accessing the data via the appropriate role based interfaces.

Also, the composition of the ruling bodies of the consortium (see section [3.4 Organisational structure and viability](#)) as well as the operating model (see section [3.5 Operating model](#)) are formed in such a way that the continuous observation of the FAIR principles guides the monitoring, discussion and decision making within NFDI x CS as well. We will design a specific **code of conduct for NFDI x CS** to explicate our common understanding of the FAIR principles against our disciplinary background. This approach will be based on the existing GI statutes³⁷ and ethical guidelines³⁸, and will be considered in defining the NFDI x CS bylaws.

The project management (TA [M1 Management of the Consortium](#)) in NFDI x CS will be guided by ways to separate out the FAIR principles as specific concerns for the definition of work in terms of milestones and goals for (sub-)work packages and combine and integrate them according to the overall architecture specified and maintained in TA [C1 \(Community Development\)](#).

4.3.2 Quality Assurance of Research Data

To make research data truly beneficial for the scientific community, **data quality** needs to be kept at a high level. Related shared definitions and processes of the specification of data quality as well as related processes to define, evolve, monitor and report quality of data and their connected additional resources is part (in varying degrees) of actually all TAs.

Specifically, TA [M2 \(Quality Management\)](#) will develop and extend mechanisms to assure data quality:

- Top-down measures are targeting overall criteria or data repositories as a whole. We will collect requirements for quality management and quality criteria of research data from the sub-disciplines. From this compilation, we will identify the needs that are shared by many. Subsequently, we will design quality indicators and guidelines and provide technical solutions that will benefit many. Later, these can be applied by single bodies for decision on the quality of a single asset, as described below. This also refers to board-level work of, for instance, the ethics board (which might be inspired by and should decide on suggested guidelines) and the technical committee that decides on the inclusion of new repositories in NFDI x CS (as described in section [3.4 – Organisational structure](#)). Moreover, developed criteria, procedures and services are picked up by the NFDI x CS communication strategy in order to promote a broad implementation of these principles in the community. This includes, among others, to align awards regarding FAIR data management with the mechanisms designed here, and so adjust selection criteria for these distinctions with the defined quality criteria.

³⁷ <https://gi.de/ueber-uns/organisation/unsere-satzung> (amendment intended for autumn 2020)

³⁸ <https://gi.de/ueber-uns/organisation/unsere-ethischen-leitlinien> (renewed in 2018)

- Bottom-up measures are directly targeting single datasets and their handling within scientific practice. We will hook up with the current trend at several CS conferences to conduct artifact evaluation³⁹ or even to call for data showcases⁴⁰. In such tracks, research artifacts, including data, are reviewed by a program committee for quality criteria such as consistency and completeness (both with respect to the research results presented in the respective conference publication) as well as reusability (in terms of being well documented and structured to facilitate reuse)⁴¹. Published papers that are accompanied by such a reviewed research artifact are subsequently marked in the conference proceedings, e.g. in the ACM digital library or in IEEE Xplore. This approach helps to ensure that both data and software required to verify and reproduce research results of publications become available with a certain agreed minimum quality. However, artifact evaluation is yet optional for submissions to these conferences and artifact evaluation is a time-consuming effort for the program committee. Thus, to support this trend, we will develop technical solutions in NFDI x CS to ease review processes of research artifacts, including data. With this, we aim to help make artifact evaluation a de-facto requirement, if not eventually mandatory, for conference and journal submissions. Additionally, these solutions can be used for pure data publication, independently of technical papers. At the same time, this approach ensures that the appropriate interpretations of quality criteria for each field and sub-discipline are formulated and checked.

Measures are carried out in close cooperation with TA C1 ([Community Development](#)) for top-down and with TA C2 ([Publication Processes](#)) for bottom-up measures with managerial support from TA M1 ([Management of the Consortium](#)).

4.3.3 Cultural Change towards FAIR Research

Implementing the FAIR data principles requires an overall cultural shift towards openness in research as well as some additional capabilities of researchers in applying certain procedures or using certain tools. Researchers in the various CS sub-disciplines need to be addressed appropriately. The structures and activities of the German Informatics Society with its more than 16.000 members provide valuable instruments and resources for reaching out to the CS community. This is the subject of TA [C1 \(Community Development\)](#). Various measures will be taken to address the entire community, raise awareness towards a sustainable RDM and to reform previous strategies and ways of working within the CS discipline:

³⁹ e.g. the ACM conference on Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems <http://ctuning.org/ae/asplos2022.html> or the IEEE/ACM International Conference on Software Engineering <https://conf.researchr.org/track/icse-2022/icse-2022-artifact-evaluation>

⁴⁰ e.g. at the Mining Software Repositories conference, see <https://2021.msconf.org/track/msr-2021-data-showcase>

⁴¹ Criteria from the ACM policy on Artifact Review and Badging, Version 1.1 <https://www.acm.org/publications/policies/artifact-review-and-badging-current>

- **establish information channels and networking platforms** in pull-mode (like web-site, central help-desk and groupware as the consortium's platform and single point of contact) and in push-mode (like newsletter, mailing list, social media, publications like professional journals of the GI⁴² and beyond) including editorial maintenance
- **perform an NFDIxCS virtual event series** (monthly web talks by experts on hot topics; annual young talents conference with proceedings) and **dedicated events** on single topics (discussion boards with other TAs, like quality management or standardization; road-shows to promote good practice – also as joint events with other NFDI consortia)
- **execute training workshops** (for junior and for senior researchers) on the FAIR principles, RDM tools and practices, ethical and legal issues, standards conducted in NFDIxCS and services provided to the CS community in order to stimulate proper usage of NFDIxCS infrastructures and tools
- **roll-out FAIR-CS certification programs** (based on the ACM⁴³ and NISO⁴⁴ reproducibility initiatives, the Carpentries⁴⁵ lessons etc.) across the established scientific platforms (conferences, workshops, journals) based on existing mechanisms like artifact review and badging as well as data showcases
- **establish competitions and awards** to identify outstanding examples and to stimulate innovative approaches of FAIR data and open science practices in CS
- **create offers for CS students and young scientists** (mentoring-program, CS RDM camps etc.) together with the very active young GI network⁴⁶ and promote the inclusion of RDM topics in the CS curricula of german universities

NFDIxCS sees itself as a debate catalyst and facilitator of discussion and dialogue on FAIR principles and RDM within the CS research community. These activities are the responsibility of TA [C1 \(Community Development\)](#). This is supported by TA [M1 \(Management of the Consortium\)](#) by providing technical infrastructure and fed with requirements by TA [A1 \(Architectures and Interfaces\)](#). Cooperation with others will arise in particular with the help desk, where – beyond this first point of contact – second-level support might be requested from the providers of NFDIxCS services, who will then be involved.

Implementation of the activities has already begun in some cases, like the virtual event series⁴⁷ the website and the email list. Discussion with other consortia showed promising interest in combining community development efforts in several of these areas, like trainings, help-desk and road-shows.

⁴² <https://gi.de/service/publikationen/fachzeitschriften>

⁴³ <https://www.acm.org/publications/policies/artifact-review-and-badging-current>

⁴⁴ <https://www.niso.org/standards-committees/reproducibility-badging>

⁴⁵ <https://carpentries.org/>

⁴⁶ <https://junge.gi.de>

⁴⁷ <https://nfdixcs.org/veranstaltungen/archiv>

4.4 Services provided by the consortium

In the following sections, we describe the implementation of the architecture as sketched in section [2.2 \(Objectives and measuring success\)](#) and the services provided, grouped by the three layers of this architecture. Our overall approach to service delivery in the NFDIxCS infrastructure is to use and configure existing platforms and frameworks, and to create new elements where necessary. Below, we use the notation (g) for Grundfinanzierung, (a) for additional outside NFDI funding, (oss) for open source software or platforms, and all other contributions are by NFDI funding within this project. In all of these cases, a good deal of specific configuration as well as additional software development will be inevitable. The work regarding the detail of this will be done in TA [A1 \(Architectures and Interfaces\)](#).

From the start of the project a first version of the portal will be created and run by the GI. This minimal product will be giving a first home for the infrastructure of the community and management services. We adopt an incremental approach to cover the whole architecture in an agile development and deployment process.

The actual research data will be stored together with all related information in a portable and easily reusable execution environment, the so-called RDMC. It provides the abstraction which will serve as the basis for a systematic research data management for all types of CS related research data. A brief explanation how this interoperates within the architecture will be given below from the top to the bottom level.

4.4.1 User Access Services in NFDIxCS

The entire NFDIxCS presents itself to the user as a central webportal. Alternatively access is also possible via web service access. The rest of the system is then structured into a distributed system which is provided by a few service providers. Below we discuss these services of the related infrastructure briefly from top to bottom level.

The figure below sketches the top section of our architecture defined in Fig. 1 in section [2.2 \(Objectives and measuring success\)](#):

Figure 10 NFDIxCS Portal Architecture, User Level

The central point of presence is a web server (extending the existing presence at www.nfdixcs.org) which gives human users the ability to search, access and use the stored research data as well as to connect themselves across the community. This can be accomplished by registered users of NFDI x CS or by the outreach mechanisms as denoted in Fig. 10. Both connect to the digital services below using the Service Interoperability bus which provides interconnection facilities for the various entities which are known to the system. The User Level services provide access to the search engines, (identified) research data, administration functions (e.g. ID management, role management, statistics and performance management, statistics and performance management) and also access to the community processes like meeting support and other community building processes as described in TA [C1 \(Community Development\)](#) also including services like help desk, and ticket system.

Contributions to the User Access services:

- Web server, CMS (Typo3) provided by GI (g), web portal framework (e.g., Liferay, oss)
- Scalable web service interface for online machine access (Apache Kafka, oss)
- Service Bus (e.g., Apache Synapse, oss)
- Help desk, ticket system (existing services by service provider or OTRS, oss)
- DFN-AAI for metadata management of user information (g)
- authentication services via Shibboleth (g)

4.4.2 NFDI x CS Logic Services

Next level below – the logic services – provide a number of central NFDI x CS digital management functions to support an integral view to NFDI x CS services as provided by the Service Interoperability bus. In the figure below the relevant excerpt from the architecture Fig. 1 in section [2.2 \(Objectives and measuring success\)](#) is used here:

Figure 11 NFDI x CS Portal Architecture, Service Level

The various research data management containers (RDMCs, discussed in the next section) provided by NFDI x CS need to be managed in terms of their specific life cycle management aspects. The RDMC Management component takes care of this (will be discussed below with the container concept). This is mainly addressed by TA [A2 \(Reusable Execution Environments\)](#). By

starting a new container the metadata of the encapsulated research data is provided also to the other central NFDI x CS logic services components.

Among the NFDI x CS Core Services, there are four components to manage the NFDI x CS infrastructure:

- First, search functionality is provided by metadata based search Engine(s). These provide services to implement the F in FAIR and deliver related results to the users' search requests. This also relates to the work performed in TA [D2 \(Metadata and Protocols\)](#).
- Then, there are various services for ID and Access management which are related to users and the data including the other artifacts needed here, like persistent identifiers for data and software as well (see TA [I2 Persistent Identifiers](#)). There is also the need to comply with international standards in terms of IDs related to publications provided by related services here (see TAs [C2 Publication Processes](#) and [A3 Citation and Attribution](#)).
- Workflow infrastructure and related event management supports the specific processes for RDM in CS. Each RDMC instance embodies a specific workflow related to the type of research data stored in the container (see next section below). There is also the workflow support for the community building processes (see TA [C1 Community Development](#)) and various management processes (see section [3.5 Operating model](#)).
- Last but not least, there is support for monitoring and accounting. Since all the components are potentially distributed, a comprehensive logging and respective accounting and monitoring will be necessary. This helps to support the abiding of the compliance rules, to execute related business rules including billing and to keep track of the success factors of the consortium. While basic means are implemented in the RDMC themselves, additional measures for collecting, archiving, visualizing and analyzing for day to day operation will be allocated here. The monitoring data will be instrumental for the cost model discussion and decision later on in the project.

As the third main component in the service level, the Service Broker Management component's task is primarily the management of all invoked services from other sites, and thus is a more technical component to allow flexible inclusion of any appropriate service.

Contributions to NFDI x CS Services:

- Workflow Engine and management of workflow definitions (e.g. Camunda, oss)
- Search engines standard metadata based search based on Apache SOLR (oss)
- Complex metadata structures based on various approaches to knowledge graphs (not standardized yet, oss, community source),
- Persistent ID management brought in by GWDG (g)
- RDMC Management is container management and depends on the chosen container version. If the likely solution Docker (oss) is used for the containers, the Kubernetes (oss)

solution will be chosen for the management task as well. To support this development, the service providers will bring their expertise and resources partly (a) partly (g).

- Monitoring with Prometheus (oss), log file analysis tools (oss)
- GI digital library (g), dblp, drops for (g) for publication support
- SHF@NRW (UDE a) software repository for referring to all known free software components, frameworks and systems

4.4.3 Data Management Services in NFDIxCS

The bottom level of the architecture comprises the services which actually store and deliver research data in form of (instances of) RDMC and additional services like dblp, GI digital library, services from within our project and also cooperating NFDI consortia or other partners nationally or internationally. Also, ancillary services like DFN-AAI are allocated here for access from the levels above.

Figure 12 NFDIxCS Portal Architecture, Data Level

The Data Interoperability service bus integrates the distributed services in this level and provides a homogenous interface for the NFDIxCS Logic services.

A centerpiece of the storage and management of the actual research data management is the concept and realization of the **Research Data Management Container**. This provides an encapsulation facility to support and execute the rules which will be designed by NFDIxCS to achieve the goal of the project for each specific research data set being eligible for storage and access by the consortium's resources.

The RDMC contains everything to encapsulate the research data in question, the software components (or reference the specific version or variant in a separate repository as, e.g., the Software Heritage repository) and information on the run-time execution environment and further context necessary to support common tasks like the replication of the creation, purging, analysis and visualization of the data.

Essential features of a RDMC include role-based access control to the encapsulated resources. Additionally, there are plug-ins included to provide proper protection of IPR, privacy and security and potential transformation, depending on context, role and purpose of the access in question. If needed, different specific views have to be provided to realize possibly divergent requirements. The general structure of a RDMC is sketched in Fig. 13 below.

Figure 13 General Structure of Research Data Management Containers (RDMCs) and their management across the levels of the NFDI x CS architecture

For each type of research data identified and described by a CS sub-discipline a type of RDMC is defined and created as a template to collect, store and index a certain dataset with all its belongings as sketched above. We will provide services and tools to work on such common templates and promote the use of these templates for higher re-usability. Depending on this type, the components as depicted in Fig. 13 might slightly adapt their behavior to the characteristics of the respective data:

- The RDMC Access Layer restricts the access to the container's resources according to the user's permissions. It uses the same service for access control as the infrastructure.
- The container's workflow defines its possible use cases, e.g. review or reuse processes. The related workflow execution uses the workflow engine from the infrastructure, but the state of the workflow is encapsulated in the container.
- Filter and transformation are plugins which get configured and used on the basis of the use case realized in the container, for instance to implement pseudonymization, anonymization and/or differential privacy. Other transformations, e.g. aggregation of data in case of IPR protection or measures to implement simple privacy protection by eliminating personal data in log files, can be implemented as a plugin here as well.
- User Data Access Services provides consistent access to the various forms of research data to comply with the given privacy rules defined for the general type of research data

and for the specific container in question in addition. Of course, in order to support review in exceptional cases (e.g. a legal inquiry) or finishing a RDMC off at the end of its defined life cycle, admin access is provided as well - secured by additional means like four eyes principle or adequate alternatives.

- Further components help to run the software to access the data using the components privacy services, virtual execution services and additional libraries. This can also include hardware emulation services like Qemu⁴⁸.

Additional considerations are necessary for management of such RDMCs. For instance, it is compulsory for each specific RDMC that the metadata will be made available through the search engines sketched in the overall architecture above. This applies also to the data which needs to be collected to record the usage of resources while accessing a given RDMC. The RDMC Management implements the services to realize the RDMC lifecycle from its inception, registration in the various repositories of the NFDI x CS infrastructure to find it, make it accessible and interoperable and reuse it. Thus, by this management it is ensured that the services of each RDMC instance are registered in the metadata search engine and other related structures.

We support joint work on common standardized RDMC environments by cooperating in national and international working groups to foster interoperability. This includes common metadata schema models and common sets of software components for re-usable RDM containers (see section [3.2 The consortium within NFDI](#) above).

Contributions to RDMC, RDMC Management and data level:

- GI digital library (g), dblp, drops for (g) for publication resources
- Repositories like SHF@NRW (UDE, a)
- Additional special repositories brought in by partners. The list is given in [appendix 1.2](#).
- Metadata Schema Registry for promoting common schemata in CS communities, t.b.d.
- Policy Management to define data retention, accessibility, certificates, checksum management etc. (partly DFN-AAI, g)
- Access Management through a role and group models (DFN-AAI, g)

4.4.4 *Sample User Story of the RDMCs*

To illustrate the technical considerations above, we provide a sample user story of how the RDMC concept can be used in the realm of the NFDI x CS infrastructure.

In studies on human-machine interaction research data is collected in the form of measurements over time. Typically, human participants have to perform a given task for testing the given hypotheses, e.g. on the performance of different interaction techniques. This may be

⁴⁸ <https://www.qemu.org>

done by capturing data in the system (events like changing a viewpoint, selecting an object or manipulating its characteristics, along with the related timecode) as well as data on the participants (spatial data like movements of the person and his/her hands or head, sensor data like direction of gaze, skin conductance or heart rate). The nature of this data and such studies brings up a number of aspects to be considered when publishing the data. To name just three:

- Gathered data is closely related to the environment that was used in the study. This includes software aspects, e.g. the used 3D engine or 3D model, the integrated measurement component or the applied analysis tool. Moreover, this in turn includes execution environments, e.g. the used host computer (hardware, operating system, graphics frameworks and libraries) and virtual reality equipment. For replication of the study to either verify the results or modify the parameters, availability of this software and hardware (at least in an emulated way, as far as this is possible) is a necessary condition. Thus, our RDMC approach encapsulates the data along with these components in order to publish them as a whole.
- Involvement of human participants and capture of motion data or physiological data require additional efforts for conservation of privacy. As an example, biometric information could be obtained from typical movement or gaze patterns, making it possible to identify this person. Other physiological signals could allow conclusions to be drawn about alcohol or drug consumption. Thus, the data must be anonymized before publication. The required effort needed – pseudonymization, anonymization, additional differential privacy – depends on the actual study and experimental design as well as the scenario of use for this data. Our RDMC approach is equipped with specific plugins and workflow models to implement transformations and filters on the data. Thus, e.g. for quality assurance in the publication process, reviewers might get full access to the raw data. Upon acceptance for publication, data is only accessible in an anonymized way. Which transformation is necessary for this, depends on the nature of that data and thus is directly contained in the RDMC.
- The developed technology or interaction technique might be associated with certain intellectual property rights. Thus, authors might refrain from publishing the whole dataset to the broader public. However, selected parts of the data or an aggregated version (reducing the broader dataset to a smaller, maybe less informative one) might still be worth publishing beyond academic reuse. This depends on the license to be issued for the data and is associated with, again, dedicated transformations of the dataset for publication and reuse.

The following figure depicts these possibilities using the example from human-machine interaction sketched above in accordance with the layers of the RDMC as familiar from Fig. 2.

Figure 14 Example of Interaction Data and Plugins in an RDMC

This way, a trust relation is established between the various stakeholders (authors, reviewers and users of the data) in the research process to ensure that the scientific contribution fulfils the community standards. Authors get their results published in high quality form without harming the privacy of their study participants or their own exploitation interests. and Reviewers are able to perform a quality check. Users are able to check and replicate the results to a greater or lesser depth, depending on their role in the academic system – without getting access to the raw data.

Thus, the RDMC is a versatile envelope which provides a great range of configuration possibilities for fulfilling the identified RDM requirements for CS.

5 Work Programme

Table 5.0: Overview of Task Areas (TAs)

TA	Measures	Responsible Co-spokespersons
D1 – Version Management	D1.1 Survey version control systems D1.2 Federated versioning model D1.3 Schema for versioning information D1.4 Service for version definition	Reussner (KIT)
D2 – Metadata and Protocols	D2.1 Survey of data formats and specifications D2.2 Area specific information D2.3 Metadata catalog	Schulz (TUM)
D3 – Semantic Aspects	D3.1 Design and implementation of an ontology D3.2 Implementation of a Knowledge Graph D3.3 Linking Publications and Evidence	Koschmider (UKI)
D4 – Data for Benchmarking	D4.1 Benchmark maintenance and development D4.2 Benchmark methodology D4.3 Enrichment and collection of benchmark results D4.4 Outreach activities	Müller (RWTH)
I1 – Storage and Repositories	I1.1 Reference repository architecture I1.2 FAIR access to distributed repositories I1.3 Cost efficiency and reliability study and corresponding reference implementation I1.4 Adoption of optimized WAN protocols	Brinkmann (JGU)
I2 – Persistent identifiers	I2.1 PID services and workflows I2.2 Teaching and training on PIDs I2.3 Data type registry I2.4 Cross-NFDI integration	Yahyapour (GWDG)
I3 – Performance Management	I3.1 Automated metadata collection I3.2 Standardizing data and metadata formats for performance and energy efficiency data I3.3 Anonymization / pseudonymization I3.4 Performance data exchange portal	Nagel (TUD)
I4 – Security and Privacy	I4.1 Access control and role management I4.2 Legal Privacy Aspects I4.3 Privacy-Preserving Techniques	Federrath (UHH)
A1 – Architectures and Interfaces	A1.1 Basic packaging and distribution concept A1.2 Elicit principal functions and services A1.3 Definition of the overall architecture A1.4 Specification of subsystems/components A1.5 Connection to international collaborators	Goedicke (UDE)
A2 – Reusable Execution Environments	A2.1 Definition of container models A2.2 Metadata standard for execution environments A2.3 Hosting services for execution environments A2.4 Versioning and archiving functions for execution environments A2.5 Collaboration with other NFDI consortia	Yahyapour (GWDG)
A3 – Citation and Attribution	A3.1 Expanding the dblp data model A3.2 Building flexible NFDI data wrappers A3.3 Sustainable integration into dblp	Ackermann (LZI)
C1 – Community Development	C1.1 Information channels/networking platforms C1.2 Event series C1.3 Training workshops	Lucke (UP)

	C1.4 FAIR-CS certification program C1.5 Competitions and awards C1.6 Offers for students C1.7 Monitoring of quality criteria	
C2 – Publication Processes	C2.1 Extended publication workflow C2.2 Automatically importing articles C2.3 Community annotation C2.4 Support for literature reviews C2.5 Annotating existing articles with NLP	Wagner (LZI)
C3 – Standardization Processes	C3.1 Definition of terms of best practice C3.2 Tooling and machinery for standardization C3.3 Definition of services and support C3.4 Performance indicators and monitoring C3.5 Service enhancement measures	Schmidt (LMU)
C4 – Legal and Ethical Issues in IT	C4.1 Legal assistance for RDM C4.2 Open-Source Software (OSS) compliance C4.3 Legal assessment of AI and data policy	Boehm (FIZ)
M1 – Management of the Consortium	M1.1 Basic management facilities M1.2 Basic community services M1.3 Service management M1.4 Risk management	Goedicke (UDE)
M2 – Quality Management	M2.1 Moderate collection of needs M2.2 Flexible realization M2.3 Quality levels in semantic layer M2.4 Monitorable refinement of KPIs M2.5 Managing review process M2.6 Integration with reusable execution environment M2.7 Reporting claims and evidence M2.8 Support for conference chairs M2.9 Automated quality checks	Koziolok (KIT)
M3 – International Networking	M3.1 Profiles for international outreach M3.2 Elicitation of requirements M3.3 International support processes M3.4 Collaboration agreements M3.5 International exchange meetings M3.6 Running internal exchange	Goedicke (UDE)

Please note that the financial planning is based on the DFG personal cost rates as of 2021 plus an expected tariff increase by 3% per year (i.e. we start with 2023 as the first project year). In some TA descriptions the category “Other Staff” was used which is – according to the DFG rules – calculated according to the local rules of the organisation in question. Also: the costs of travel, subcontracting, reserves for future use etc. are calculated and indicated in the cost category “Direct project costs” in the *second* table of each TA description. These costs are assigned to the TA leader which is given in the *first* row (co-applicant) of the *first* table in each TA description.

5.1 Basic Data Layer

This layer consists of four TAs: D1 – Version Management; D2 – Metadata and Protocols; D3 – Semantic Aspects; D4 – Data for Benchmarking.

D1 Task Area – Version Management

Versioning is a challenge mentioned in almost all CS sub-disciplines above. While we have sophisticated systems available for source code versioning today (e.g. Git), there is no solution how to version research data in general. The main challenge here is that one “version” of research data involves multiple data types. For example, a certain version of research software may be applied to a certain version of data to produce raw results, which, when analyzed with a certain version of analysis scripts and supporting libraries, are turned into, e.g., a single plot in one publication. To reproduce this research result in the form of a plot, other researchers need to know exactly which versions were involved in its production. Furthermore, depending on the research data, the version of the used component stack like operating system or virtual machine as well as the hardware “version” may influence the results. A simple approach to this problem would be to store a set of persistent identifiers such as DOIs or ePIC PIDs as one such version. However, such an approach would lose the history of the involved versioned research data.

In this TA, we strive to develop a federated versioning model to cover these different data types. We will build on results from the area of distributed version control. At the same time, using a single distributed version control system like git is not sufficient, as the solutions need to support different version control systems used for the individual data types. Thus, the federation also requires information from individual version control systems (in themselves distributed or not). In addition to a sequential evolution over time leading to different versions “in time”, research data may also be varied for different purposes (called versions “in space” in the software product line community). These relations shall be captured by the federated versioning model as well.

As a result of this TA, we will provide a federated versioning model as well as a service that users, i.e. researchers, can use to define such versions.

- D1.1** Survey existing version control systems used for research data of different types and publish results (KIT, GWDG, UDE)
- D1.2** Develop a federated versioning model for research data in space and time (KIT, GWDG).
- D1.3** Define a schema for storing and exchanging the versioning information across repositories and other storage providers and services (KIT, GWDG).
- D1.4** Develop a service that allows users to define and store such research data versions by providing DOIs or links of the involved research data. The service will extract versioning information from the underlying version control systems used (e.g. Git) and resolve relations to previously registered versions. This service will be integrated in the workflow of TA [C2 \(Publication Processes\)](#) and thus also be integrated with services to request DOIs and to persistently store data. (KIT, GWDG, UDE)

This TA is closely linked with the TAs [I2 \(Persistent Identifiers\)](#) and [C2 \(Publication Processes\)](#). After the initial survey (D1.1), a team of doctoral researchers from KIT , GWDG , and UDE will

work on the above measures D1.2 to D1.4 concurrently in an iterative and incremental fashion with early drafts for versioning model and schema as well as an early prototype of the supporting service to avoid the risk of misunderstanding requirements from users and other stakeholders. Afterwards, we will iteratively improve and extend the results, following agile software development practices like short iterations, frequent stakeholder feedback, and continuous integration. The risk of not covering all relevant used versioning systems will be mitigated by providing the means to manually specify versioning information as a fallback mechanism.

D2 Task Area – Metadata and Protocols

Providing the right metadata information and associating it with the actual data is critical for implementing the FAIR principles. Metadata, however, can be very diverse, data set specific and must be connected to the necessary semantic information. This diversity and the associated challenges have been highlighted in section [4.2 \(Metadata standards\)](#).

A key point of NFDIxCS is therefore to investigate the breadth of possible metadata, find the necessary descriptors for it, standardize where necessary and connect to other TAs where needed, e.g., ontology and semantics or unique identifiers. The actual work will thereby have to be a three step process:

- D2.1** First, we will conduct a survey of all data formats and needed data specifications across all NFDIxCS areas and collect needed metadata terms/attributes and concepts. Based on this, and a first coordination with other NFDIs (via, e.g., a common special interest group) and international partners, we can then devise a NFDIxCS metadata framework, ensuring basic compatibility with other NFDIs.
- D2.2** This is then followed by Phase 2, which aims at comprehensively including area-specific information. This, however, will only be possible via direct interactions; for this purpose, we will engage the individual CS sub-disciplines for feedback and input, to help further refine the metadata approach and its vocabulary. We will then compile this information and integrate it into an evolving metadata schema, which includes classifications and semantic definitions. At this stage, we will combine equivalent tags, match representation types, and identify suitable storage formats.

Once we have reached a critical mass with NFDIxCS, we will go through a harmonisation process with other consortia that have expressed an interest in exploring joint metadata formats, representations or usage. Examples for this are metadata for software, which is widely used across all consortia, and metadata for HPC jobs, which can help associate user data (the research data from other consortia) with performance computing traces and logs. Contacts of our

members to numerous other NFDI consortia (and co-memberships) will help to find the right discussion platform on this within the NFDI landscape and its efforts on cross-cutting topics. The harmonisation will also include international partners and platforms like EUDAT.

D2.3 The result will be a comprehensive metadata catalog, which covers the needs of the CS community. This catalogue, already in its earliest form, but even more so when complete, then forms the core vehicle to adopt or newly design necessary storage formats, data representations, metadata to data mappings and cross-community interactions. This final phase will therefore include the implementation of the necessary libraries and usage scenarios that will realize this metadata as part of NFDIxCS in specific and NFDI in general.

D3 Task Area – Semantic Aspects

This task's overall goal is to establish a semantic layer. Beyond a syntactic level, a semantic level in the data layer is inevitable. Whereas metadata standards enable syntactic interoperability, semantics go a step further and transition information to knowledge, as highlighted in section [4.2 \(Metadata standards\)](#). Ontologies are a semantic, generalized data model and allow carving out implicit knowledge, whereas metadata can only transport explicit knowledge. The sub-disciplines (especially Software Engineering, High-Performance Computing, Dependability & fault tolerance, E-Learning) will provide use-cases for the design and evaluation of the semantic layer and the ontology. The use cases will include, but are not limited to, searching for state of the art on a topic (publication- and data-wise), reviewing artifacts, reviewing technical submissions, comparing results, collecting evidence on a research question and will be worked out and complemented in the project. The work on metadata in TA [D2 \(Metadata and Protocols\)](#) will be complemented by the means of an ontology to achieve a semantically richer description of the research artifacts than given by a mere metadata model.

D3.1 As the first part of the process, it has to be evaluated which entities, relations, functions and axioms hold for all the sub-disciplines and will define the upper ontology level. Existing upper ontologies have to be evaluated regarding their suitability. Then, specific domain-level ontologies for the sub-disciplines must be designed. Specific design tasks include entities (the relevant entities must be defined), classes (sets and categories of entities must be defined), attributes (the properties of entities and classes must be carved out), relations (the way how entities and classes are related to each other have

to be defined), functions (structures derived from relations), axioms (assertions to define) and events (definition of changing components). Last, the formalized model has to be implemented in an ontology language. It is planned that RDFS, OWL or JSON-LD will be used. (UKI)

D3.2 The ontology defined will be used as a schema layer for a knowledge graph. The knowledge graph will then act as an instance of the ontology, which is filled with research data and artifacts gathered. A possible preliminary work thriving towards semantic scholarship is the Open Research Knowledge Graph⁴⁹ (ORKG) proposed by Jaradeh et al. (2019). In this approach, the publications, which are at the center of scientific reasoning, will be completed by communicated content. This can either be links to research data or other research works, but also conceptualizations of terms like trust, evidence or a reasoning mechanism. It is envisioned that the outcomes of this TA will serve as a use case for the ORKG. (UKI, KIT)

D3.3 For readers, it is often difficult to assess the validity of statements in scientific papers, mainly because it is difficult to understand and compare what exactly was validated. To address this issue, we will introduce statement-level annotations that link statements in publications to their evidence in the form of research data and that specify the role the research data plays in the publication, including used research methods and context information. To achieve this, we will work on a classification of research questions and applicable research methods to provide informative attributes for these links. With metadata according to this classification, trust in research results in papers will be improved in two ways: First, links to research data can be provided. Second, claims about the relation can be made explicit and thus can be easily validated by reviewers and readers. (KIT)

D3 meetings should be held with co-applicants and participants at least once a year, since ontology design needs a huge coordination and harmonization effort. The risk of the semantics task area to find an ontology that is generic enough in term so extensibility and reuse.

⁴⁹ <https://www.orkg.org/orkg/>

D4 Task Area – Data for Benchmarking

Standardized benchmarks evaluate modern computing systems' performance and their characteristics, such as energy efficiency. They provide not only the foundation for the procurement of all kinds of computing infrastructure, but they are also a necessity for the CS community to judge and compare the value of scientific contributions, including work on compilers, system frameworks, system middleware, and programming languages and models. Benchmarking remains a challenging task because it usually involves numerous runs of different applications with different configurations, potentially in different environments. It results in a large amount of unstructured data that has to be collected and analyzed.

The requirements of the CS community go beyond the sole existence of benchmarks. They range from creating a central point of contact for best benchmarking practices to the support for reproducibility. For example, the high-performance computing community demands better benchmarks and more detailed benchmark metadata in its quest to ensure the reproducibility of simulations and performance measurements to support the results' relevance. Application areas that solve optimization problems (e.g., data science, business information systems) need training data for machine learning and benchmark data to develop metrics to judge application results' quality and explore runtime vs. quality tradeoffs. NFDIxCS will address these demands on multiple levels, based on the idea of providing a central point of contact and guided by the FAIR data principles. In summary, this will result in extended benchmarking tools and data formats, structured in four tasks.

D4.1 Benchmark maintenance and development: Partners in this consortium are active members of different benchmark standardization activities and develop or contribute benchmark codes and input configurations; for instance, RWTH, TUD and UPB are members of SPEC (Standard Performance Evaluation Corporation). NFDIxCS will leverage synergies between the different activities and ensure that functionalities will be developed only once. Additionally, new codes from different application domains will be collected and new benchmark configurations will be defined to represent problem instances for important applications. This is enabled by the involved computing centers serving different user bases and system types; for instance, UPB focuses on customizable computing and JGUM on HPC storage systems.

D4.2 Benchmark methodology: The partners' expertise will be offered by the central point of contact to consult on selecting benchmarks for a given purpose and the execution of benchmarks to ensure the reproducibility of the measurement results. In addition, existing tools for benchmarking will be maintained and extended to support new usage requirements. Partners in this consortium are active in developing such tools; for instance, FZJ maintains JUBE. D4.2 will also maintain anonymization/

- pseudonymization standards and tools when incorporating codes and datasets into collections.
- D4.3** Enrichment and collection of benchmark results: NFDI x CS will investigate the potential to outfit benchmarks with a more precise and complete recording of the execution environment. This will increase the informative value of results, support the result verification process and enable the reproduction of results under different configurations. Furthermore, it will allow the use of the benchmark results in new data science application areas.
 - D4.4** Outreach activities: Tutorials and workshops will make different communities familiar with these methods and approaches. The aim is that many researchers and users can contribute results or are at least able to interpret the current results and use the insights to select the most efficient implementation available for the solution of their scientific problem.

5.2 Infrastructure Layer

This layer consists of four TAs: I1 – Storage and Repositories; I2 – Persistent Identifiers; I3 – Performance Management; I4 – Security and Privacy.

I1 Task Area – Storage and Repositories

TA I1 is responsible for the storage and archive infrastructure for this project and builds and maintains the repositories for the CS subdisciplines. Every sub-discipline therefore participates in I1 to ensure the proper alignment of the repositories with discipline-specific requirements.

- I1.1** Storage and archive capacity: The sub-disciplines will collect and access very different kinds of research data, including software, log-files, databases, object code, execution environments, videos, and images. It is therefore necessary to provide a combination of different long-term archiving services to combine the benefits of specialized data repositories like git, video streaming platforms, or image galleries with general RDM solutions. Besides specifying reference repository implementations, work package I1.1 integrates individual archives for NFDI x CS and offers access to them through CLI and Web-interfaces. The management of the underlying storage and archive technologies will be provided by the NFDI x CS hosting sites as in-kind contributions, while new data management services on top will be provided by I1.1 and I1.2.

- I1.2** Repository infrastructure and FAIR data: In German CS, as in similar communities, research data is scattered across various storage systems/federations as well as full-fledged repositories. I1.2 will make these “data silos” comply with FAIR standards by adding respective federation, metadata-indexing and dissemination layers. The resulting repositories will support PIDs (with TA [A3 Citation and Attribution](#)) and a rich metadata description as well as ontologies (with TAs [D2 Metadata and Protocols](#) and [D3 Semantic Aspects](#)). The repositories must attach various storage backends, creating a data federation with a common metadata index. I1.2 will therefore provide reference implementations of mandatory interfaces (e.g. OAI-PMH for metadata exchange) and standards (e.g. regarding metadata and PIDs) and offer consulting and documentation. Thus, I1.2 will help to harmonise the repository landscape within each CS sub-discipline and make sure that a distributed, FAIR repository is available to scientists of all sub-disciplines. I1.2 will also implement a federated presentation and data-search layer, based on open standard solutions such as Elasticsearch. This will be able to integrate and present – besides data repositories – also code repositories, image repos etc. The necessary collation of metadata for this layer will heavily rely on suitable interfaces, such as the widely-accepted OAI-PMH mentioned above. As metadata are appropriately collected, the presentation layer will also provide data-product information pages, suitable, e.g. as landing pages for DOIs. This will also include the integration of existing archives like the archive of formal proofs at TUM.
- I1.3** Cost Efficiency and performance of NFDIxCS Storage and Archives: The scalable, cost-efficient, reliable, and accessible provisioning of storage capacity is the foundation to build FAIR data repositories. TA [I1 \(Storage and Repositories\)](#) therefore also actively improves storage and archival technologies for the NFDIxCS use cases and aligns with other NFDI consortia. Data objects inside NFDIxCS repositories will be of very different sizes and will therefore have different requirements concerning storage capacity and performance. Open-source object stores like Ceph and Swift already provide the foundation to build Exabyte data repositories. Nevertheless, they are only partly optimized for performance and do not include the processing capabilities of client computers, therefore leading to an inefficient use of hardware resources. Examples are the implementations of deduplication and compression in object stores, which are handled in the storage nodes and therefore require processing power, which could be easily outsourced to client nodes. The resulting reduced network traffic between clients and servers would additionally reduce hardware overheads. I1.3 therefore will investigate to include client capabilities in storage processes in scenarios with a very high data ingest rate, e.g. when collecting monitoring information from HPC systems. Cost efficiency also has to include reliability to prevent loss of data in case of failures

(storage failures, software malfunctions, disasters) and for long-term accessibility of relevant data sets. Existing data repository systems cover reliable storage, e.g., by using fault-tolerant backend storage. However, the sole application of existing solutions would not take specifics of NFDIxCS data into account and would not profit from its distributed infrastructure. I1.3 will therefore include NFDIxCS specific constraints to assess reliability when providing cost optimized repositories.

- I1.4** Wide-area network traffic for replication and caching: Several open-source data management environments are already wide-spread in the CS community, while different sub-disciplines historically rely on different tool sets. I1.4 will work together with sub-disciplines that have focused on optimizing data transfers and data caching to ensure that functionalities and optimizations are not developed multiple times within the NFDI. As an example, NFDIxCS will investigate the potential to transfer (sub-)solutions from PUNCH4NFDI to improve data transfer rates and to include data caching for sharing of huge data sets into NFDIxCS.

I2 Task Area – Persistent Identifiers

A crucial core functionality is the ability to reliably find and access information resources through the adoption of persistent identifiers. All digital objects need a unique and long-term available reference that can be used to cite and track use of references. NFDIxCS does not intend to develop new solutions but to adopt existing solutions in this area. For individuals and data authors, ORCID is a common identifier. For published objects, Document Object Identifiers (DOI, as an ISO 26324 standard) provide a long-term stable referencing based on the common Handle system, coordinated by Digital Object Numbering Authority (DONA). NFDIxCS plans to adopt DOIs for its publication processes. In addition, we see ePIC PIDs as a relevant complement to support the full data management lifecycle beyond the sole publication. ePIC PIDs also use the Handle system and complement DOIs, as it allows referencing of fine granular data, even if its future publication is not clear or intended. We follow the approach to use ePIC PIDs early in the scientific data workflow and convert to DOIs when certain data objects are published. With GWDG and DKRZ, we have two partners who are members in the European EPIC consortium which can provide the necessary expertise and existing services.

For user management, we plan to build upon the existing DFN-AAI services and its international federation in eduGain. We will enrich this in the areas of access and role management in collaboration with [TA I4 \(Security and Privacy\)](#).

- I2.1** The TA will adapt and provide the PID services and workflows. Based on the existing ePIC and DOI service infrastructure, we plan to implement links from the data management workflow of our sub-disciplines and their use-cases, and associate ePIC PIDs early in the lifecycle and process to DOI in a later publication/citation step. By this we follow best practices as recommended in RDA and already implemented by DKRZ in Earth System Sciences. We plan to embed this into our overall service infrastructure of the consortium, especially on user and security management ([TA I4 Security and Privacy](#)).
- I2.2** We provide the necessary teaching and training for the CS sub-disciplines in cooperation with [TA C1 \(Community Development\)](#). This includes general skills and awareness on PIDs as well as consulting on how to embed these services in the individual research process.
- I2.3** As we need to support different data types in NFDIxCS, we will also work on the development of a data type registry that can be used in conjunction with the PID service. ePIC PIDs support flexible metadata schema and can benefit from adopting common metadata schema for our considered data types.
- I2.4** We will contribute and link our activities to the overall NFDI structure, as we foresee that persistent identifiers are key for other consortia as well. We already participated in cross-NFDI discussions, how this can be integrated and federated to support a common NFDI vision.

The measures are foreseen for the whole duration of the NFDIxCS. Consulting, teaching and training will be available from the start. The adoption of the PID services is ongoing and will provide first usage scenarios after one year. GWDG is MPA for Germany and member of DONA.

This TA is closely linked to TA [D2 \(Metadata and Protocols\)](#), TA [A3 \(Citation and Attribution\)](#), and TA [C2 \(Publication Processes\)](#).

13 Task Area – Performance Management

Performance management is crucial for efficient use of hardware resources, human effort, and scalability. It is most pronounced in High Performance Computing (HPC) but not only there. There are data-intensive approaches for monitoring and analyzing the performance behavior where the free exchange of data sets is challenging but would be beneficial for multiple parties including (i) computer scientists developing computational methods, (ii) application area scientists applying those methods for their scientific fields, and (iii) computing centers operating the hardware

resources. There are quasi-standards for data formats including metadata description for application-centric performance data (OTF2 and CUBE) developed and maintained by the partners in this TA. For system-centric and job-centric performance data there are similar systems in production at many HPC centers including the partner centers (e.g., “PIKA” at TU Dresden). Yet, they lack established data and metadata standards.

The main contribution of this TA and the corresponding tasks are:

- I3.1** Automated metadata collection in OSS tools and infrastructures for collecting performance management data
- I3.1a Add automated metadata extraction from hardware, software components, build environment, and execution environment to the OSS tool Score-P and the data format standards OTF2 and CUBE (TUD, FZJ)
 - I3.1b Integrate existing metadata from the application areas into application-centric and job-centric performance data collection, design interfaces with application-area NFDI partners (TUD, FZJ, RWTH, UPB, JGUM)
 - I3.1c Verification between performance data and benchmarks (TUD, RWTH, TUDA, JGUM)
- I3.2** Standardizing data and metadata formats for performance and energy efficiency data
- I3.2a Standardize metadata categories and formats for application-centric performance data, integrate them into the existing OTF2 and CUBE data formats (TUD, FZJ, RWTH)
 - I3.2b Standardize metadata categories and formats for system-centric and job-centric performance data, define metadata formats (TUD, FZJ, RWTH, UPB, TUDA, GWDG, JGUM)
 - I3.2c Annotate results from analysis, correlation and ML categorization as additional metadata categories for job-specific performance data (TUD, UPB, TUDA, FZJ, GWDG, JGUM)
- I3.3** Specific anonymization/pseudonymization standards and tools
- I3.3a Collect requirements for anonymization / pseudonymization and confidentiality levels for performance data (TUDA, UPB, in coordination with TA [I4 Security and Privacy](#))
 - I3.3b Implement automatic filter tools to apply anonymization / pseudonymization to the data and metadata formats (TUDA, UPB, TUD, in coordination with TA [I4 Security and Privacy](#))
- I3.4** A performance data exchange portal for collaborative access to highly voluminous performance data sets and metadata beyond the executing user or the local center

- I3.4a Design a joint performance data exchange portal with centralized metadata and search functionality but distributed storage resp. data accesses. (TUD, RWTH, FZJ, TUDA, UPB, GWDG, JGUM)
- I3.4b Design and implement automated, on-the-fly anonymization resp. pseudonymization during remote accesses according to I3.3 (TUDA, UPB)
- I3.4c Implement and operate the performance data portal (TUD)

I4 Task Area – Security and Privacy

Security and privacy are two core aspects when storing and processing research data. In scenarios where possibly sensitive research data is outsourced to an external infrastructure, it is essential to control access to this data. Identity management and access control techniques are solutions from the domain of CS that provide the necessary tools to manage access to data. Encryption ensures that data at rest (in storage) and data in transit cannot be accessed by parties without sufficient access permissions. Furthermore, data stored within repositories needs to be protected against modification using cryptographic authentication mechanisms (digital signatures to ensure accountability and message authentication codes to ensure integrity of data). Moreover, logging of system events within NFDIxCS allows for providing accountable uploading into repositories and monitoring misuse of the research data infrastructure. The use and the management of these techniques will be an important task in NFDIxCS, has implications to all other TAs and also affects other NFDI consortia, because all NFDI initiatives face the issue of secure and authenticated access to research data. The focus of TA I4 is thus to use existing techniques and expertise to manage and ensure secure access and storage of research data and offer this know-how to other TAs and NFDI consortia.

As many research data sets will contain personal data and need to respect fundamental rights of natural persons, we will provide services within NFDIxCS for lawful and privacy-respecting storage of this kind of data. Data sets will be analyzed – before storage within NFDI repositories – for their privacy implications. Techniques like pseudonymization or anonymization, but also differential privacy can help to mitigate the privacy impact that a certain data set has. Promising techniques that allow privacy-preserving processing of data in a protected or encrypted form are homomorphic encryption or secure multi-party computation, which might be viable solutions for certain kinds of computations or analyses. These techniques, however, are computationally comparably expensive and require a powerful infrastructure to be executed in a practical fashion. We will closely follow the research progress in this area and evaluate the viability of these techniques for use in NFDI services and infrastructure.

Privacy-respecting storage of data is closely related to legal and ethical concerns. In conjunction with TA [C4 \(Legal and Ethical Issues in IT\)](#) we will evaluate privacy implications of creating, processing and storing certain datasets, and we will design compliance methods for the lawful publication process of research data which meet the legal guidelines from a privacy perspective.

TA I4 will focus on the following measures:

- I4.1** Together with TA [I2 \(Persistent Identifiers\)](#) we will provide access control and role management by building upon the existing DFN-AAI infrastructure and its international federation in eduGain. We will implement privacy-respecting logging functionality to monitor and detect misuse of the research data infrastructure.
- I4.2** With the goal of identifying and handling privacy issues from a legal perspective we will closely collaborate with TA [C4 \(Legal and Ethical Issues in IT\)](#) and provide services for anonymization and pseudonymization of data. We provide the necessary teaching and training for the CS sub-disciplines in cooperation with TA [C1 \(Community Development\)](#). This includes general awareness on security and privacy as well as consulting and education on how to anonymize and pseudonymize research data before publication and to use NFDIxCS services provided by TA I4. We will coordinate with TA [I3 \(Performance Management\)](#), particularly with I3.3 regarding the development of anonymization and pseudonymization services.
- I4.3** Technical measures that allow security by design and privacy by design and that allow secure storage and can enable privacy-preserving computation are currently under development. We will evaluate the practicality of results from recent research and will provide adequate services for safe and secure storage of research data.

These measures are expected to cover the entire duration of NFDIxCS.

5.3 NFDI Application Layer

This layer consists of three TAs: A1 – Architectures and Interfaces; A2 – Reusable Execution Environments; A3 – Citation and Attribution.

A1 Task Area – Architectures and Interfaces

The infrastructure which is to be deployed and operated as part of NFDIxCS needs a well designed so called architecture in order to implement the FAIR principles. This architecture is sketched in section [2.2 \(Objectives and measuring success\)](#) and presented in more detail in section [4.4 \(Services provided by the consortium\)](#). It is important to maintain and evolve the infrastructure in a sustainable way. It also provides the basis to access this infrastructure which

is basically a highly distributed information system, interacting peer to peer and providing open protocols & interfaces to other consortia and international partners. During the ramp-up phase of the project the various requirements from within and beyond the project's borders need to be collected in detail. The core of the architecture is the management of the Research Data Management Containers (RDMC) which provide the conceptual unit of distribution and combined storage of all forms of data and related context in terms of software, execution, metadata (see TA [A2 Reusable Execution Environments](#)).

- A1.1** The basic conceptual unit of packaging and distribution is the portable Research Data Management Container (RDMC), encapsulating all the necessary access and management functions to store and access research data of the various CS research data types, connected additional artifacts, metadata and context information. RDMC is the implementation of the “conceptualization of CS research data” (see Fig. 8) and will offer configuration capabilities which allow specific formation of an instance, e.g. depending on the data's privacy concerns the appropriate pseudonymization functions are configured, otherwise, the respective layer will be a passthrough (see also section [4.4 Services provided by the consortium](#)). This will be realized in collaboration with TA [A2 \(Reusable Execution Environments\)](#).
- A1.2** The requirements engineering stage will be planned in detail to elicit the principal functions and services to host and deploy instances of RDMCs, to deploy and connect additional services for managing and using metadata, related search engines and additional services from the service catalogue (see also section [3.5 Operating Model](#) and [4.4 Services provided by the consortium](#) e.g. helpdesk, event management, ticket system, community services). In particular, access to containers and rights and roles are an important ingredient of this process which is also based on other TAs' results ([I2 Persistent Identifiers](#), [I1 Storage and Repositories](#), [I4 Security and Privacy](#), [C2 Publication Processes](#)).
- A1.3** The overall architecture will be defined in such a way that the aforementioned services and components resulting from the requirements stage can be defined, implemented and evolved due to new requirements resulting from the ongoing requirements engineering. This is part of a process to ensure the sustainability of the efforts defined herein beyond the funding period. This includes specifically the technical interfaces and protocols and well defined user interfaces for human usage. These will be continuously maintained and published to allow collaboration partners nationally and internationally to cooperate.
- A1.4** Detailed specification of subsystems and components which allows publication for collaborators where necessary. Also implementation / configuration of all necessary

components and their evolution in conjunction with the requirements engineering process is continuously maintained.

- A1.5** An additional effort is directed to connect to the international research community to communicate and disseminate services and processes of NFDIxCS and to incorporate their feedback.

TA A1 realizes “Findable” by interfaces to related search engines for RDMC locating, “Accessible” by providing interfaces and components for role and rights management in a federated context, “Interoperable” by following metadata standards, standardized protocols and interfaces and “Reusable” by related interfaces which provide reproducibility of items (data, software context). A risk is that the overall complexity of the infrastructure will become difficult to manage. In that case better modularization and less coupling between subsystems by prioritizing the importance of aspects will guide the architecture evolution process.

A2 Task Area – Reusable Execution Environments

Special but not limited to CS is the close relation of data, software and the specific execution environment that has been used. Reproducibility can often not be achieved if the execution environment is not taken into account. It is well known, for instance in the HPC field, that different hardware, operating systems or system configurations can lead to different results with reproducibility problems. As such, the annotation as well as the reproduction of the execution environment has been under discussion for several years in the software and data management domain. Through the advent of virtualization and container technology, we now have reasonable means to also consider the execution environment a managed entity that can be stored, archived and hopefully recreated in the future.

This TA will work in collaboration with the sub-disciplines and the service providers, i.e. data and computer centers, to identify a common container format as well as a standard metadata model for it. Currently, we see hypervisor-based virtual machine images as well as Kubernetes-based container hosting as a suitable basis for portable execution environments. The initial use cases in our consortium showed that such execution environments are suitable to satisfy the requirements. Thus, we will first focus on such hosting models and develop reference cases to version, publish and archive such execution environments.

NFDIxCS has large data and computing centres as partners and contributors, who naturally offer execution services for VMs and containers. They can serve as reference points for such

reusable execution environments. This will be extended to public and academic cloud services who already expose common interfaces for managing VMs and containers. The specific measures in this area are:

- A2.1** Definition of common container models, fulfilling the requirements of the sub-disciplines and their processes
- A2.2** Design and implementation of a common metadata standard for such execution environment
- A2.3** Design and implementation of reference hosting services for such execution environments
- A2.4** Design and implementation of versioning and archiving functions for such execution environments and integrate them with the common NFDIxCS processes for publication, access management etc.
- A2.5** Collaborate with other NFDI consortia to promote and support the approach for their software

This TA collaborates closely with TA [D1 \(Version Management\)](#), TA [D2 \(Metadata and Protocols\)](#), TA [I1 \(Storage and Repositories\)](#), and TA [C3 \(Standardization Processes\)](#).

A3 Task Area – Citation and Attribution

Only recently, research communities have begun to give proper credit for data publications as valuable contributions in a researcher's bibliography. Collecting and opening up contributor metadata and interlinking it with existing attribution resources (such as ORCID or dblp) helps to incentivize open sharing of data for the benefit of reuse and reproducibility. Only sound, semantically meaningful linkage of research datasets with their creators, relevant publications, and use cases (instead of isolating them in data silos) will signal that research data has indeed become a true first-class citizen of the scientific community.

For 25 years now, the *dblp computer science bibliography* of Schloss Dagstuhl LZI is among the most comprehensive and most widely used infrastructures for high-quality bibliographic metadata in CS. Today, dblp is listing more than 5.8 million publications from more than 1000 structured and unstructured metadata sources. However, data publications have been barely indexed yet. In this TA, we will adopt and expand the quality-oriented, semi-automated and semi-manual dblp curation workflow to research data publications.

Whenever possible, research data metadata will make use of persistent identifier schemes like DOI, ORCID or ROR, and will be linked to semantic knowledge graphs like ORKG and WikiData.

In the absence of persistent identifiers or in the case of ambiguities, dblp's data curation process will be employed in order to identify the creators and semantically enrich the metadata. All indexed metadata will be made openly available under *CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication License*. All data will be embedded in an open-by-design ecosystem, consisting of open metadata, open citation data, and open abstracts.

- A3.1** We will conceptually expand the existing dblp data model to accommodate for data publications and implement the expanded model into the live dblp computer science bibliography system. This is a non-trivial task due to the differences in versioning, volume and velocity of research data publications.
- A3.2** We will build a framework of flexible metadata wrappers for NFDI data sources. This measure will build on the existing data wrapper framework of dblp.
- A3.3** Traditional challenges for curating bibliographic metadata (such as author disambiguation) are amplified in the context of handling research metadata. Hence, careful consideration needs to be given to build a sustainable and scalable integration into the quality-oriented indexing workflow of the dblp computer science bibliography. This integration will allow for a continuation of the indexing task well beyond the funding of this project.

This TA will make use of the metadata standards defined by TA [D2 \(Metadata and Protocols\)](#) for indexing. Furthermore, metadata will be semantically linked to the knowledge graph entities from TA [D3 \(Semantic Aspects\)](#). These knowledge graphs will also be exploited as sources of further and more meaningful metadata and will play a significant role in metadata curation and author disambiguation tasks. Repositories from TA [I1 \(Storage and Repositories\)](#) are first-hand sources for indexing, while persistent identifiers from TA [I2 \(Persistent Identifiers\)](#) will be used for unambiguous citation and attribution whenever possible. Furthermore, this TA will coordinate with TA [C2 \(Publication Processes\)](#) to make indexing an integral part of the publication lifecycle.

5.4 Community Layer

This layer consists of four TAs: C1 – Community Development; C2 – Publication Processes; C3 – Standardization Processes; C4 – Legal and Ethical Issues in IT.

C1 Task Area – Community Development

The targeted cultural change towards implementing the FAIR data principles across the CS community will be addressed by this TA. We will follow the RISE reference model to drive this process on two levels: First, we address institutions (especially co-applicants and organizations represented by or connected to members of the consortium) by a series of workshops to support them in implementation of the FAIR principles according to the RISE model. Second, we target researchers (senior staff members as well as junior scientists) in the CS community each with targeted measures. Here, the networks of participating institutions are used, especially the GI structures and communication channels and international partners with their experience in FAIR research and in community development. The ongoing measures in this TA, as described in more detail in section [4.3.3 \(Cultural Change towards FAIR Research\)](#), are:

- C1.1** information channels and networking platforms in pull-mode and push-mode based on requirements defined by TA [A1 \(Architectures and Interfaces\)](#) and infrastructure provided by TA [M1 \(Management of the Consortium\)](#)
- C1.2** event series (web talks; conference and proceedings) and dedicated events on single topics (discussion boards, road-shows)
- C1.3** training workshops (for junior and for senior researchers) on the FAIR principles, RDM tools and practices, ethical and legal issues, standards and services of NFDI x CS
- C1.4** roll-out FAIR-CS certification program (as offered by other associations) across established platforms (conferences, workshops, journals)
- C1.5** competitions and awards on FAIR data and open science practices in CS
- C1.6** offers for students and young researchers (mentoring-program, CS RDM camps etc.) and inclusion of RDM topics in CS curricula
- C1.7** monitoring of quality criteria (automated where possible) based on indicators from TA [M2 \(Quality Management\)](#) as an objective and control instrument

While the responsibility for the TA and for the scientific and methodological issues lies with the UP, the GI will support in communication towards the community as well as in organization and distribution of the events and material (in close cooperation with the TAs [M3 – International Networking](#) and [M1 – Management of the Consortium](#)). A possible risk of missing participation in the above-mentioned measures will be countered by the GI's 50 years of experience in community management. Risks resulting from unsuitable orientation of the offers will be targeted by using a verified procedural model (see section [3.5.3 – Evaluation, Risk Mitigation and Quality Assurance](#)) and experienced trainers.

C2 Task Area – Publication Processes

Scholarly articles are the main form of science communication between researchers to advance their disciplines. While research data should receive a more prominent place and should count as a contribution on its own, scholarly articles will remain a main form of science communication. Natural language presentation of research results is likely to stay. However, with the increasing amount of publications, it seems that we need more rigor in making statements about research results and relating them to evidence to increase trust and confidence in the research results. Research results are still primarily stored as papers in PDF format and the evidence is described in e.g. tables in the paper. Here, digitization offers new opportunities of interlinking to the original research data and thus increasing verifiability of and confidence in the results. In this TA we will work with the community to fill the knowledge graph from TA [D3 \(Semantic Aspects\)](#) with information, considering both the process for future publication and a bootstrapping process to fill the graph with existing data.

- C2.1** Extended publication workflow for scholarly papers: Ideally, the annotation and cross-linking of scholarly papers, research data, software and other research artifacts already happens during the initial publication of one of them. However, this would require authors to be aware of different public standards/best practices for the publication and citation of research artifacts (e.g. developed in TAs [I2 Persistent Identifiers](#), [D2 Metadata and Protocols](#), [I1 Storage and Repositories](#)). To bootstrap this and to take the burden from the authors, appropriate support should be provided within the publication workflow of scholarly papers. This ideally already includes the detection of missing links in the text of a scientific paper, the publication of previously unpublished artifacts (e.g. on Zenodo) up to the correct archiving of referenced artifacts (e.g. on Software Heritage) within the publication process. As a result of this work package, a best practice guide for the redesign of the publication process for scientific papers will be developed and implemented exemplarily within the publication system of the LZI. The implementation shall be published open-source.
- C2.2** Automatically importing existing articles: Obviously, annotating already published articles with semantic information is problematic, as researchers may not be willing to spend the effort or may even be unavailable. Thus, we will extend an import mechanism from established digital libraries (e.g. the ACM digital library) for a basic import based on existing metadata (e.g. based on the ORKG open-source project).
- C2.3** Community annotation: Additionally, we will devise and implement a web service for

the community so that other researchers may extend and correct an initial classification.

C2.4 Support for systematic literature reviews: We will offer consulting for authors of systematic literature reviews that aim for high-ranked conferences or journals to encourage them to use our knowledge graph as their database for reviewing publications.

C2.5 Annotating existing articles with natural language processing techniques: We will explore the use of natural language processing techniques to extract annotations (semi-)automatically from article PDFs. The results will not be perfect, but will be a starting point for manual additions and corrections (see C2.2). Additionally, manual additions will be training data to improve the NLP .

A risk of this TA is that we envision a publication process which does not fit to the requirements of researchers or which is too cumbersome to follow. To mitigate this risk, we will regularly collect feedback on the envisioned process and work towards a high automation to ease adoption.

C3 Task Area – Standardization Processes

Standardization processes are essentially an elicitation and negotiation process between the relevant stakeholders of a given standardization endeavour. The relevant area of expertise is Requirements Engineering. Such processes arise in the context of RDM in a number of areas, such as metadata type definition and producing definitions. Agreeing on application level protocols for storage, access and retrieval of the research data, context and execution environment is key for this consortium. The latest research results and best practices for the activities of this TA constitute the basis for working in it.

In requirements engineering three phases are commonly distinguished: elicitation, negotiation and documentation (also specification). In recent years, research has placed emphasis on collaboration, particularly, under consideration of spatial distribution of stakeholders. This development is challenging for requirements engineering as most techniques rely on an intensive direct exchange between the requirements engineer and the stakeholders.

The challenges arising during elicitation and negotiation of requirements for standardization of research data are similar to those in distributed software development projects. They are comparable to the coordination and negotiation of data type meta information and protocols in a collaborative, distributed project. Thus, established approaches and tool support are adopted and applied. De Angelis et al. adopted a collaborative requirements engineering approach for eliciting

and negotiating requirements for the European research project Learn PAD⁵⁰. The approach has been used to negotiate project requirements and tasks.

Principal findings show that there is a need for a digital communication infrastructure to allow for elicitation and negotiation in collaborative distributed contexts. This communication infrastructure must be centrally managed, moderated and mediated. A good approach for a communication infrastructure is the use of social network like systems. Open-source tools efficiently support the elicitation and negotiation in collaborative contexts. For instance, tailored tools to support the WinWin approach to requirements elicitation and negotiation exist.

The overall frame of reference is created in TAs [D2 \(Metadata and Protocols\)](#) and [D3 \(Semantic Aspects\)](#) and the processes and especially the support is organized here.

- C3.1** Basic definition of terms of best practice for the standardization processes in question
- C3.2** Acquisition of appropriate tooling and workflow machinery to create and configure the infrastructure elements for standardization support
- C3.3** Definition of services and related support (helpdesk etc) to make work effective
- C3.4** Definition and implementation of specific performance indicators and monitoring capabilities to measure the usability of the standardization support process service
- C3.5** Setting up service enhancement measures to achieve best use of resources

This includes cross-disciplinary processes in dialogue with other NFDI consortia. In addition, the dialogue with specialist journals and conferences on the publication practice of data and software will be conducted. The GI is a long-time experienced carrier for such negotiation processes.

C4 Task Area – Legal and Ethical Issues in IT

TA C4 will help with implementing the requirements for open data for NFDI x CS from a legal perspective. For research data and software, compliance with legal requirements is essential. In particular, there are challenges in data protection law (e.g. identifiability of natural persons, legal basis for data processing, information obligations, privacy by design and privacy by default etc.), IT law and software license law, intellectual property law (protection of property rights) and discrimination issues of algorithmic decision making. The legal requirements for licensing law, the development of a procedure for general compliance when dealing with open-source software,

⁵⁰ Model-based Social Learning for Public Administrations: <http://www.learnpad.eu/>

as well as the legal requirements for machine learning and its future regulatory framework are of equal importance.

TA C4 will deliver expertise in education and training of computer scientists through workshops, publication of legal guidelines and recommendations for computer scientists, legal monitoring of projects in CS with regard to data protection law, IT law and IP law. We will support researchers and institutions in keeping research data as open and easily accessible as possible to comply with the FAIR principles by clarifying legal issues and avoiding legal uncertainty. This will enable legal expertise to be developed based on actual requirements.

C4.1 Legal assistance for research data management: Legal requirements for handling research data are already a focus of many NFDI consortia. However, the legal options for making such data available according to the FAIR criteria often differ. Depending on the specific (sub-)disciplines, different case types can be identified. While in cultural studies, for example, copyrighted intangible goods are often subject to IP rights, research data in CS are usually not protected by IP law as pure facts lack the required originality to be legally protected. The compilation, linking etc. in a database can, however, give rise to property rights (database protection *sui generis*); likewise enrichment of data sets, for example through extensive metadata descriptions. In order to examine the legal requirements, typical case/use case constellations should be identified. TA C4 will develop a license management system for the sub-disciplines that meets the requirements for the typical data records in each case.

C4.2 Open-Source Software (OSS) Compliance: OSS compliance is an important topic for NFDI x CS. It must be ensured that researchers do not violate copyleft licenses when they distribute their software. If license obligations are violated, software developers or other rights holders can assert contractual or copyright claims against the infringer. In addition, chains of liability are conceivable, which must be prevented through OSS compliance. The large number of different software licenses makes legal expertise necessary because the licenses sometimes differ in details, but each of these licences can have a significant effect on the legal obligations that result from them. TA C4 will develop processes for compliance management and good practices from the outset. First, it is important to identify the open-source components that have been used and to document licenses in order to ensure whether and how open-source obligations relate to the researchers' own developments. This is achieved through guidelines, check- and instruction lists training for employees and those responsible, information guides or Q&As as well as workshops and trainings. In addition to the aspect of license compatibility, the requirements under which FAIR availability of software represents a distribution will be examined to identify whether the obligations of OSS licenses apply or not.

- C4.3 Legal assessment of AI and data policy:** Selection processes for the input data of machine learning should be accessible to democratic control. This is due to the fact that automatic decision-making processes will continue to gain in social relevance. Individuals cannot be required to examine the decision-making processes. Rather, specific obligations must be laid down in the chain of responsibility, to prevent discriminatory and ethical concerns already during the system design phase. We will therefore develop recommendations and guidelines as to the extent to which the processes of selecting the input data should be comprehensible. TA C4 will therefore
- deliver an assessment of AI and data policy in terms of discrimination effects of generated outputs, requirements on anonymization and pseudonymization
 - We will collaborate with TA [I4 \(Security and Privacy\)](#) in developing data protection and privacy compliant services and processes for secure and legal data access
 - publish a quarterly newsletter on the latest legal developments in AI regulation to accompany the EU's take on the regulation of AI alongside a data strategy
 - draft good-practice recommendations and guidelines e.g. on a risk dependent documentation on the origin of meta and training data as well as input variables

Before and during their development, services, infrastructure and processes need legal support to comply with data protection and privacy requirements. We will assist the consortium, and here in particular TA [I4 \(Security and Privacy\)](#), by developing legal recommendations and guidelines to fulfill this task. These measures are expected to cover the entire duration of NFDIxCS.

5.5 Management Layer

This layer consists of three TAs: M1 – Management of the Consortium; M2 – Quality Management; M3 – International Networking.

M1 Task Area – Management of the Consortium

The task of managing the consortium with quite a number of partners, outreach to international communities etc. is divided into a (a) conceptual and financial part and an (b) operational / secretarial level. The level (b) includes also support for national and international outreach. These two levels are addressed by the applicant and the co-applicant GI.

The conceptual level (a) is characterized by all tasks and activities to support the applicant to fulfill the leadership duties in terms of the goals of the consortium, the financial obligations towards the partners in the project and (financial) reporting to the DFG. The financial and contract management is performed by the applicant's administration through the usual channels wrt. the

DFG and to the partners' administrations as well. The goals and performance indicators are defined in section [2.2 \(Objectives and measuring success\)](#). It will be crucial to observe the consortium's performance according to these KPIs and the general goals. It needs profound knowledge of the field CS in order to accomplish the supportive task which is essential for achieving the goals. This includes the analysis and interpretation of the reports from the various ruling and working bodies of NFDI x CS and the results from monitoring the consortium's activities (from [M2 Quality Management](#) and [C1 Community Development](#)) as well as the infrastructure's actual performance (see also section [3.5 Operating Model](#)). In turn, this process will be the basis of the preparation of the respective next steps in the governance and operation procedures laid out in sections [3.4 \(Organisational structure and viability\)](#) and [3.5 Operating Model](#). At this level, the workflows will be defined and the related automated processes to share and distribute information and documents and support decision making etc. will be implemented. This includes managing the stakeholders as well as their expectations and the offered service portfolio within these processes.

The operational part (level b) of the management is to run the infrastructure for the processes of the consortium. These are briefly sketched in section [3.5 \(Operating Model\)](#) and relate to the operational part of monitored data from TA [C1 \(Community Development\)](#). This applies also to the workflows keeping the processes of the consortium alive with minimal manual intervention and preparation/running of (video) conferences and other related event management services (e.g. education & dissemination related) for the consortium.

- M1.1** Definition and configuration of basic management facilities esp. wrt. the creation and operation of the ruling and working bodies of NFDI x CS. This includes basic monitoring and management of the financial funds and related contract management and managing the contact to the DFG. This also includes the long term management and support of NFDI x CS as a community-driven set of activities
- M1.2** Creation, deployment and operating basic community services e.g. workflow and event management, help desk, ticket system. Special focus is on services which allow agile and prompt reaction of members of NFDI x CS as well as members of the community at large (see also TA [C1 \(Community Development\)](#)). We will use open-source solutions like Camunda⁵¹ for workflow or indico⁵² for event management.
- M1.3** NFDI x CS has also to be seen as an organisation which delivers services. Thus the usual essential products need to be defined, configured and run for the community. These include a service catalogue, definition of service levels and managing related contracts, and last not least to monitor service usage. In addition, it will be important to

⁵¹ <https://camunda.com/>

⁵² <https://getindico.io/>

collect this information in order to develop organisational and financial structure for operating NFDI x CS beyond the funding period.

- M1.4** Risk management is important for NFDI x CS. There are numerous types of risks which need to be addressed. An initial task is to identify all these and use as much of the monitoring infrastructure and basic services as possible to detect early warning signs and start mitigation activities. The main risks to be addressed which cannot be easily detected by technical means are people related. Thus, regular meetings and “open door” policies have to be in place to detect and manage staff turnover especially in key areas of operations and conceptual development.

M2 Task Area – Quality Management

Research data made available via NFDI x CS results will be more useful the higher its quality is. In this TA, we will work on selected mechanisms for increasing CS scientific quality and research data quality, as described in section [4.3.2 \(Quality Assurance of Research Data\)](#). As there are numerous research data types in the various CS sub-disciplines, we follow a combined top-down and bottom-up approach: First, we will investigate *quality management* needs across the identified data types and sub-disciplines in a top-down fashion to determine needs that are shared by many, and subsequently we will design quality indicators and provide solutions that will benefit many. In addition, we will refine the KPIs introduced in section [2.2 \(Objectives and measuring success\)](#) to make them monitorable. Flexible funds will be reserved to address these needs. Second, we are working bottom up and will combine existing solutions to better support *artifact evaluation* tracks at conferences, which are a current development to improve scientific quality in terms of accessibility, verifiability, reproducibility and reusability of results. By providing means to ease artifact evaluation, we work towards more conferences and journals adopting FAIR research data principles for artifact submission and even paper submissions.

Top-down: Quality management. We will discuss needs, identify existing solutions, and derive models and indicators.**M2.1** Moderate top-down collection and discussion of quality management needs and quality levels (including quality indicators) (ongoing)

- M2.2** Flexible realization of technical solutions for identified needs and indicators (with flexible funds)

- M2.3** Incorporation of identified quality levels in the metadata and semantic layer (TA [D2 Metadata and Protocols](#) and TA [D3 Semantic Aspects](#)), in TA [C1 \(Community Development\)](#), and in TA [M1 \(Management of the Consortium\)](#).

M2.4 Monitorable refinement of KPIs (by both UP and KIT).

Bottom-up: Artifact evaluation platform. We will provide an artifact evaluation platform that allows reviewers to partially reproduce research results more easily and we aim to provide an ontology for reporting claims and their evidence .

M2.5 Web service for managing review processes, which initially integrates with Zenodo and GitHub as common current code sharing platforms but will be built to be extensible for other code sharing platforms.

M2.6 Integration with reusable execution environments (TA [A2 Reusable Execution Environments](#)) and research data containers (TA [A1 Architectures and Interfaces](#)).

M2.7 Ontology for reporting claims and their evidence, building upon results from TA [D2 \(Metadata and Protocols\)](#) and TA [D3 \(Semantic Aspects\)](#).

M2.8 Support for conference chairs and others to adopt the platform.

M2.9 (optional) Tool support for automated quality checks preceding manual review,

A potential risk is that the artifact evaluation platform does not meet the review processes envisioned by stakeholders. To mitigate this risk, we will work with organizers of existing artifact evaluation tracks to collect their requirements and regularly request their feedback.

M3 Task Area – International Networking

Reaching out to international organisations and institutions is a key point for the NFDI x CS's activities. I.e. nearly all the actions, services and infrastructure are created and run in such a way that the international dimension is considered and implemented as well. Thus, it can be foreseen that all the relevant documentation, definitions and specifications will be available in English and where necessary have to be translated professionally.

However, the most relevant part of the activities here addresses the reach out to other organisations, associations, CS societies and institutes working in this or related areas. Many of these are listed in section [3.5 \(Operating Model\)](#), and some have already agreed to cooperate or expressed a serious interest in at least sharing and discussing the results. On a global level there will be a very close cooperation e.g. with the International Federation of Information Processing (IFIP) – where GI is on the board and engaged in several Technical Committees – and the Association for Computer Machinery (ACM) – with which the GI has a close cooperation. On the European level the GI is e.g. on the board of the Council of European Professional Informatics Societies (CEPIS) and closely cooperating with Informatics Europe.

M3.1 Definition of CS research data profiles for reaching out internationally and matching profiles

- M3.2** Elicitation of requirements from the other activities regarding international collaboration and interoperation; i.e. how to connect to similar RDM projects abroad
- M3.3** Setup support processes to connect to the international and national organisations and institutes abroad
- M3.4** Set up collaboration agreements and manage these.
- M3.5** Support the operation by running regular exchange meetings between NFDIxCS and international partners
- M3.6** Support the operation by running internal exchange about the international reach out and define / enhance best practices

Appendix

1 Bibliography and list of references

1.1 Cited literature

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Strickroth, S.; Bußler, D.; Lucke, U., (2021). Container-based Dynamic Infrastructure for Education On-Demand. In: Kienle, A., Harrer, A., Haake, J. M. & Lingnau, A. (Hrsg.), DELFI 2021. Bonn: Gesellschaft für Informatik e.V.. (S. 205-216). <https://doi.org/10.1365/s40702-021-00771-7>

1.2 Cited repositories

We break down our compilation below into cross-sectional platforms and deployments specific to single sub-disciplines. The underlined entries are own contributions by members of the NFDI x CS consortium.

409 Computer Science

First and foremost, there is a number of repositories (including data collections besides the mere functionality) that are used across the entire CS community:

- dblp computer science bibliography: <https://dblp.org/>
- Dagstuhl Research Online Publication Server (DROPS): <https://drops.dagstuhl.de/>
- GitHub: <https://github.com/>
- local GitLab and Subversion platforms, for instance: <https://git-ce.rwth-aachen.de/>, <https://git.uni-due.de/>, <https://gitup.uni-potsdam.de/>, <https://gitlab.gwdg.de/> and many more
- SHF software archive: <https://www.softwareheritage.org/>
- local SHF.NRW mirror (currently under development)
- Dataverse, Open-source research data repository software: <https://dataverse.org/>
- local Dataverse nodes, for instance: <https://data.goettingen-research-online.de>
- koala long-term archiving: <http://koala-docs.gwdg.de/>
- SourceForge: <https://sourceforge.net/>
- Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/>
- Figshare: <https://figshare.com/>

Moreover, several tools and frameworks exist to support RDM. These are candidates to be used by or integrated in NFDI x CS:

- Open Science Framework: <https://osf.io/>
- Invenio OSS framework for open science: <https://invenio-software.org/>
- iRODS OSS for data management: <https://irods.org/>
- CDSTAR, a framework to build tailored research data repositories: https://info.gwdg.de/docs/doku.php?id=en:services:storage_services:gwdg_cdstar:start
- Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG): <https://www.orkg.org/orkg>

- EMBL-EBI, an ontology lookup service: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/>

Also, a couple of approaches for the creation and management of identifiers, which is a constant challenge for large-scale initiatives, already exist. Partially, they include authentication and authorization mechanisms:

- DFN-AAI, authentication & authorization infrastructure for research facilities in Germany: <https://www.aai.dfn.de/>
- edu-ID infrastructure for persistent identifiers: <https://doku.tid.dfn.de/de:aai:eduid>
- ePIC infrastructure for persistent identifiers: <https://www.pidconsortium.net/>
- ePIC PID local node: <https://www.gwdg.de/application-services/persistent-identifier-pid>
- ORCID: <https://orcid.org/>

In this list, we intentionally included general-purpose tools and platforms (required for broad and sustainable use of such repositories) in those cases where we intend to use for or integrate with our solution.

409-01 Theoretical Computer Science

repositories and datasets:

- Archive of Formal Proofs (AFP): <http://isa-afp.org/>
- Coq Package library: <https://coq.inria.fr/packages/>
- Lean mathlib2 library: <https://github.com/leanprover-community/mathlib/>
- Mizar Mathematical Library (MML): <http://mizar.org/library/>
- TPTP problem library (classical logic): <http://tptp.org/>
- QMLTP proof problem library (quantified modal logics): <http://www.iltp.de/qmltp/>
- ILTP proof problem library (intuitionistic logic): <http://www.iltp.de/>

platforms and tools:

- “System on TPTP” infrastructure for solving and processing problems: <http://www.tptp.org/cgi-bin/SystemOnTPTP/>
- “System before TPTP” infrastructure for preparing problems: <http://www.tptp.org/cgi-bin/SystemB4TPTP/>

409-02 Software Engineering and Programming Languages

repositories and datasets:

- PROMISE: <http://promise.site.uottawa.ca/SERepository/>
- Repository for Model-Driven Development (ReMoDD): <https://www.cs.colostate.edu/remodd/v1/>
- Lindholmen Dataset, an index of UML diagrams in OSS: <http://oss.models-db.com/>
- Collective knowledge (CK): <https://cknowledge.org/>
- the cTuning Foundation: <https://ctuning.org/>

platforms and tools:

- the collection of software engineering tools at <https://sselab.de/>

409-03 Security and Dependability

repositories and datasets:

- IACR Cryptology ePrint Archives: <https://eprint.iacr.org/>
- Git repositories of data and software with developer cooperation: <https://github.com/>
- Online malware and virus database: <https://www.virustotal.com>
- OpenSSL library: <https://www.openssl.org/>
- Networking and Cryptography library: <https://nacl.cr.yp.to/>
- arXiv and sub-category for Cryptography and Security: <https://arxiv.org/list/cs.CR/recent>
- Open-access literature archive for Cryptography and Security: <https://arxiv.org/list/cs.CR/recent/>

platforms and tools:

- Wireshark captures network traces in the pcap format: <https://www.wireshark.org/>
- GNU profiler: <https://ftp.gnu.org/old-gnu/Manuals/gprof-2.9.1/>
- Google Performance Tools: <https://github.com/gperftools/gperftools>

409-04 Operating, Communication, Database and Distributed Systems

repositories and datasets:

- Text REtrieval Conference (TREC) archive: <https://trec.nist.gov/data.html>
- Cross Language Evaluation Forum (CLEF): <http://clef.isti.cnr.it/>
- Distributed Information Retrieval Evaluation Campaign: <http://direct.dei.unipd.it/>

platforms and tools:

- Open-Source IR Replicability Challenge (OSSIRC): <https://osirrc.github.io/osirrc2019/>

409-05 Visual Computing

repositories and datasets:

- many different data set are published by the authors, e.g.:
<https://www.dfki.de/en/web/research/projects-and-publications/publications-overview/publication/6556/>
- SFB-TRR161: <https://darus.uni-stuttgart.de/dataverse/TR161/>
and https://www.sfbtrr161.de/Resources/openscience_software/

409-06 Business Information Systems

repositories and datasets:

- business process model repositories like Signavio::
<https://www.signavio.com/post/process-model-repository-of-the-future/>

- or Camunda Modeler: <https://camunda.com/products/camunda-platform/modeler/>
- process mining event logs: <https://www.tf-pm.org/resources/logs/>
- case studies: <https://www.tf-pm.org/resources/casestudy/>
- Linked Open Vocabularies, publishing knowledge models but not raw data:
<https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/>

platforms and tools:

- Cognitive Process Designer for modelling and generation of process variants:
https://www.aifb.kit.edu/web/Cognitive_Process_Designer/en
- Free tools for modeling business processes and decisions are available (e.g. Camunda modeler).

409-07 Computer Architecture and Embedded Systems

repositories and datasets:

- Electronic circuit repositories, like OpenCores: <https://opencores.org/>
- MCNC: <https://www.cbl.ncsu.edu/>
- VTR: <https://docs.verilogtorouting.org/en/latest/vtr/benchmarks/>
- HPC Challenge Benchmark for FPGAs: https://github.com/pc2/HPCC_FPGA
- Paderborn FPGA Database: under development, expected completion Feb 2022
- SNIA I/O Trace Data Files: <http://iota.snia.org/traces>
- Failure Trace Archive: <http://fta.scem.westernsydney.edu.au/> (mostly active before 2014)

409-08 Massively Parallel & Data Intensive Systems

repositories and datasets:

- SNIA/IOTTA: <http://iota.snia.org/>
- Failure Trace Archive: <http://fta.scem.westernsydney.edu.au/>
- Parallel Workloads Archive: <https://www.cs.huji.ac.il/labs/parallel/workload/>
- PIKA, continuous HPC performance data collection:
<https://hpcmon.zih.tu-dresden.de>, <https://gitlab.hrz.tu-chemnitz.de/pika>
- Standard Performance Evaluation Corporation (SPEC) repository of benchmarks:
<https://www.spec.org/>

platforms and tools:

- Common simulation tools are GridSim: <https://sourceforge.net/projects/gridsim/>
- or CloudSim: <https://github.com/Cloudslab/cloudsim>
- Profiling data is often collected with likwid perfctr: <https://github.com/RRZE-HPC/likwid>
- or Vampir: <https://vampir.eu/>
- or OTF2: <https://www.vi-hps.org/projects/score-p/> or vendor tools
- IEEE/ACM Supercomputing Conference reproducibility initiative:
<https://sc18.supercomputing.org/submit/sc-reproducibility-initiative/>

409-09 Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning

repositories and datasets:

- DAWNBench: <https://dawn.cs.stanford.edu/benchmark/>
- ResNet-50: <https://github.com/neuralmagic/>
- DBPedia from Wikipedia: <https://www.dbpedia.org/>
- Google Knowledge Graph: <https://developers.google.com/knowledge-graph>
- Geonames: <http://www.geonames.org/>
- YAGO: <https://yago-knowledge.org/>

platforms and tools:

- Spark: <https://spark.apache.org/>
- Tensorflow: <https://www.tensorflow.org/>
- Neo4J: <https://neo4j.com/>

409-10 Interactive Systems

repositories and datasets:

- Zurich Cognitive Language Processing Corpus: <https://osf.io/q3zws/>
- CMU Multi-Modal Activity Database: <http://kitchen.cs.cmu.edu/>
- Manipulation actions (atomic and chained) Dataset: <https://alexandria.physik3.uni-goettingen.de/cns-group/datasets/maniac/>
- KIT Whole-Body Human Motion Database: <https://motion-database.humanoids.kit.edu/>
- Human Activity Recognition Using Smartphones Data Set:
<http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Human+Activity+Recognition+Using+Smartphones>
- Open Images Dataset V6 + Extensions:
<https://storage.googleapis.com/openimages/web/index.html>
- A Mobile App Dataset for Building Data-Driven Design Applications:
<http://interactionmining.org/rico>
- AIM – Aalto Interface Metrics service, Compute how good your design is:
<https://interfacemetrics.aalto.fi/>
- Observations on Typing from 136 Million Keystrokes:
<https://userinterfaces.aalto.fi/136Mkeystrokes/>
- Open Educational Resource repositories:
<https://www.bildungsserver.de/>
<https://open-educational-resources.de/>
including local OER repositories at universities:
<https://oer.uni-due.de>
- LearningOnline Network with Computer-Assisted Personalized Approach (LON-CAPA):
<https://vita.ostfalia.de/adm/coursecatalog>

- definition repositories for xAPI verbs and activities:
<https://gitlab.com/learntech-rwth/xapi>
<https://xapi.elearn.rwth-aachen.de/>
<https://registry.tincanapi.com/>
- repositories of E-Learning data and software,
for instance on learning programming: <https://systemsreview.strickroth.net/>
- Repositories to collect and compare different approaches for a certain field,
like on 3D selection and manipulation techniques:
<https://s3dit.cs.uni-potsdam.de/>

platforms and tools:

- Learning Record Store/Learning Locker: <https://docs.learninglocker.net/>
- single design artifacts, like for a haptical VR controller design manual:
<https://github.com/AndreZenner/shifty>
- or for dedicated research software like: <https://github.com/AndreZenner/hand-redirectation-toolkit>
- open-source toolkits for users studies and data management / analysis, like:
<https://github.com/immersivecognition/unity-experiment-framework>
- Toolkit for assessing subjective measurements in VR:
<https://github.com/MartinFk/VRQuestionnaireToolkit>
- toolkit for psychophysical detection threshold experiments:
<https://github.com/AndreZenner/staircase-procedure>

2 Curricula vitae and lists of publications

3 Letters of commitment by the participants

Letters of commitment from each of the participants (person and/or institution) are submitted in separate documents.